

Efficient Edge-to-Cloud Workload Management

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Content

- 1. Executive Summary 15**
- 2. Introduction..... 15**
 - 2.1 Purpose and scope of the deliverable 15
 - 2.2 Relation to other WPs and tasks 17
 - 2.3 Structure of the deliverable..... 17
- 3. Methodology..... 18**
 - 3.1 Key topics definition and work distribution 18
 - 3.2 State of the Art collection and analysis methodology..... 19
 - 3.3 ENACT platform specifications methodology 19
 - 3.4 Use Cases definition and specifications methodology 21
- 4. State of the Art analysis and beyond22**
 - 4.1 Computing continuum modelling and visualisation 22
 - 4.1.1 Research directions and related work..... 22
 - 4.1.2 Market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards..... 25
 - 4.1.3 Beyond State of the Art 29
 - 4.2 Distributed storage and data spaces..... 31
 - 4.2.1 Research directions and related work 31
 - 4.2.2 Market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards 33
 - 4.2.3 Beyond State of the Art 34
 - 4.3 Risk and compliance 34
 - 4.3.1 Research directions and related work 34
 - 4.3.2 Market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards 38
 - 4.3.3 Beyond State of the Art 41
 - 4.4 Zero-touch provisioning services..... 43
 - 4.4.1 Research directions and related work 43
 - 4.4.2 Market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards 44
 - 4.4.3 Beyond State of the Art 45
 - 4.5 Edge-cloud orchestration 46
 - 4.5.1 Research directions and related work 46
 - 4.5.2 Market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards 48
 - 4.5.3 Beyond State of the Art 49
 - 4.6 AI Algorithms and training environments 50

- 4.6.1 Research directions and related work 50
- 4.6.2 Market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards 54
- 4.6.3 Beyond State of the Art 56
- 4.7 Application programming models 58
 - 4.7.1 Research directions and related work 58
 - 4.7.2 Market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards 59
 - 4.7.3 Beyond State of the Art 60
- 4.8 Application control 61
 - 4.8.1 Research directions and related work 61
 - 4.8.2 Market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards 62
 - 4.8.3 Beyond State of the Art 63
- 4.9 Software development kits 65
 - 4.9.1 Research directions and related work 65
 - 4.9.2 Market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards 65
 - 4.9.3 Beyond State of the Art 66
- 4.10 Quality and security for distributed applications 67
 - 4.10.1 Research directions and related work 67
 - 4.10.2 Market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards 68
 - 4.10.3 Beyond State of the Art 70
- 4.11 Overview of technologies and projects 71
 - 4.11.1 Relevant components and technologies 71
 - 4.11.2 Relevant projects 72
- 5. ENACT platform specifications 73**
 - 5.1 Virtual Training Environment (VTE) component 74
 - 5.1.1 Model Manager module 82
 - 5.1.2 Execution Engine module 85
 - 5.1.3 General module 89
 - 5.1.4 Federated Learning module 92
 - 5.2 Application Controller component 94
 - 5.2.1 Application Adaptation Engine module 97
 - 5.2.2 Application Adaptation Strategies module 98
 - 5.2.3 Data Manager module 99
 - 5.3 Graph Neural Network (GNN) Models component 100
 - 5.4 Dynamic Graph Modeller (DGM) component 103

- 5.5 CCC Models..... 107
 - 5.5.1 Application/ Service Model..... 109
 - 5.5.2 Resource/ Device Model..... 109
 - 5.5.3 Telemetry Data Model 110
- 5.6 Data Access and Sharing Interfaces component..... 110
 - 5.6.1 APIs module..... 113
 - 5.6.2 Data Connector module 114
- 5.7 Data Manager component 115
 - 5.7.1 Data Store module 118
 - 5.7.2 Metadata Manager module 119
 - 5.7.3 Security & Access Control module..... 121
 - 5.7.4 Monitoring Services module 123
- 5.8 AI forecaster component..... 123
 - 5.8.1 Data Analysis module 125
 - 5.8.2 AI Forecaster module 125
 - 5.8.3 Data Exchange module 126
- 5.9 Deep Reinforced Learning (DRL) Agent component 126
 - 5.9.1 Data Analysis module 128
 - 5.9.2 AI Scheduler module 128
 - 5.9.3 Data Exchange module 129
- 5.10 Orchestrator component..... 129
- 5.11 AI Act Compliance Check component 135
 - 5.11.1 ComplianceLogic module..... 137
 - 5.11.2 AIActKnowledgeBase module 137
- 5.12 Application Programming Model (APM) component..... 138
 - 5.12.1 APM Data Service module 140
 - 5.12.2 APM Dynamic Querying Layer module..... 141
 - 5.12.3 APM Abstraction Layer module 141
- 5.13 Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine (TDCME) component 142
 - 5.13.1 Quality Monitoring module 144
 - 5.13.2 Policy Monitoring module 144
 - 5.13.3 Log Exporter module 145
 - 5.13.4 Query Engine module 146
 - 5.13.5 Alert module 146
- 5.14 Zero-Touch Provisioning (ZTP) component..... 146

- 5.14.1 ZTP Manager for Devices module 148
- 5.14.2 ZTP Manager for K8 Clusters module..... 149
- 5.15 Security Risk Modeller (SRM) component..... 150
 - 5.15.1 Interface module 152
 - 5.15.2 System Model module 154
 - 5.15.3 Risk Treatment Plan (RTP) module 156
- 5.16 Software Development Kit (SDK) component 157
 - 5.16.1 SDK Libraries..... 159
 - 5.16.2 Development Tools 159
 - 5.16.3 Documentation module..... 160
- 5.17 Application Policy Model component 160
 - 5.17.1 Network Policies module 162
 - 5.17.2 Storage Policies module 163
 - 5.17.3 Computational Policies module 164
 - 5.17.4 Locality Policies module..... 165
 - 5.17.5 Policies Datastore module..... 166
 - 5.17.6 Policy Manager module 167
- 6. ENACT Use cases analysis and specifications.....169**
 - 6.1 Hyper-distributed Media Content Processing..... 169
 - 6.1.1 Overview 169
 - 6.1.2 Use Case Scenario..... 172
 - 6.2 Hyper-Distributed Data Processing for Fujitsu’s Mobility Digital Twin Initiative..... 181
 - 6.2.1 Overview 181
 - 6.2.2 Use Case Scenario..... 185
- 7. ENACT Vision.....202**
 - 7.1 ENACT platform goals and aspirations..... 202
 - 7.2 Hyper-distributed Media Content Processing 204
 - 7.3 Hyper-Distributed Data Processing for Fujitsu’s Mobility Digital Twin Initiative..... 205
- 8. Conclusions.....206**
- 9. References207**

List of Tables

Table 1: Key Topics.....	18
Table 2: ENACT Component Functional Specification Template	21
Table 3: Module Functional Specification Template (if applicable).....	21
Table 4: Function Specification Template.....	21
Table 5: Relevant components and technologies.....	71
Table 6: Relevant projects.....	73
Table 7: Virtual Training Environment Component specification.....	81
Table 8: Model Manager module specification.....	82
Table 9: Data Ingestor function specification.....	82
Table 10: Data Pipelines function specification	83
Table 11: ML Library function specification	83
Table 12: Model Uploader function specification	84
Table 13: Model Configurator function specification	84
Table 14: Model Validator function specification	84
Table 15: Model Registry function specification	85
Table 16: Model Orchestrator function specification.....	85
Table 17: Model Deployer function specification	85
Table 18: Execution Engine module specification	86
Table 19: Model Executor function specification.....	86
Table 20: Model Executor Metering function specification	87
Table 21: Model Monitor function specification	88
Table 22: AI Explainability function specification.....	88
Table 23: Data Sink function specification	89
Table 24: General module specification	89
Table 25: Web UI function specification	90
Table 26: User Management function specification	90
Table 27: Security function specification.....	91
Table 28: Visualisation function specification	91
Table 29: Model Reporter function specification.....	92
Table 30: Federated Learning module specification	92
Table 31: Initialisation function specification.....	93
Table 32: Local Training function specification.....	93
Table 33: Model Aggregation and Update function specification	94
Table 34: Validation and Testing function specification.....	94
Table 35: Deployment and Monitoring function specification	94
Table 36: Application Controller Component specification	97
Table 37: Application Manager function specification	97
Table 38: Application Adaptation Engine module specification	97
Table 39: Graph Neural Network Component specification.....	102
Table 40: Inference function specification	102
Table 41: Retraining function specification	102
Table 42: Evaluate function specification	102
Table 43: Data converter function specification	103
Table 44: Dynamic Graph Modeller Component specification.....	106

Table 45: Data Requester function specification	107
Table 46: Graph Modeller function specification.....	107
Table 47: Graph Visualiser function specification.....	107
Table 48: CCC Models specification	109
Table 49: Application / service model specification.....	109
Table 50: Resource / device model specification	110
Table 51: Telemetry data model specification	110
Table 52: Data Access and Sharing Interfaces Component specification.....	113
Table 53: API's module specification.....	113
Table 54: Read Data function specification	114
Table 55: Write Data function specification	114
Table 56: Data Connector module specification.....	114
Table 57: Read Data function specification	114
Table 58: Write Data function specification	115
Table 59: Data Manager Component specification	118
Table 60: Data Store module specification.....	118
Table 61: Data Storage functional specification	118
Table 62: Data Retrieval function specification.....	118
Table 63: Metadata Manager module specification	119
Table 64: Data Indexing functional specification.....	120
Table 65: Data Filtering function specification.....	120
Table 66: Data De-indexing functional specification	121
Table 67: Security & Access Control module specification	121
Table 68: Identity Verification functional specification	122
Table 69: Access Control function specification	123
Table 70: Monitoring Services module specification.....	123
Table 71: AI Forecaster Component specification	125
Table 72: Data Analysis module specification.....	125
Table 73: ProcessData function specification	125
Table 74: AI Forecaster module specification	125
Table 75: RunForecast function specification	126
Table 76: ProcessingInput function specification	126
Table 77: Data Exchange module specification	126
Table 78: GetData function specification	126
Table 79: SendData function specification.....	126
Table 80: Deep Reinforced Learning Component specification.....	128
Table 81: Data Analysis module specification.....	128
Table 82: ProcessData function specification	128
Table 83: AI Scheduler module specification	128
Table 84: RunOptim function specification	129
Table 85: ProcessInput function specification	129
Table 86: Data Exchange module specification	129
Table 87: GetData function specification	129
Table 88: SendData function specification.....	129
Table 89: Orchestrator component specification	132
Table 90: Application Manager Handler function specification.....	133

Table 91: Deployment Plan Handler function specification	133
Table 92: Deployment Monitoring function specification.....	134
Table 93: Scheduler function specification	135
Table 94: AI Act Compliance Check Component specification	137
Table 95: ComplianceLogic module specification.....	137
Table 96: AI ComplianceLogicScore function specification.....	137
Table 97: AIActKnowledgeBase module specification.....	138
Table 98: AIActKnowledgeBaseUpdate function specification	138
Table 99: APM component specification	140
Table 100: APM Data Service module specification.....	140
Table 101: High-level function specification.....	140
Table 102: List of Available Data Sources function specification	141
Table 103: APM Dynamic Querying Layer module specification.....	141
Table 104: CRUD Specification function specification.....	141
Table 105: Abstraction Layer module specification.....	141
Table 106: Connector function specification.....	142
Table 107: Markup UI function specification	142
Table 108: Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine component specification.....	143
Table 109: Quality Monitoring module specification	144
Table 110: Register Quality Indicator function specification	144
Table 111: Calculate Quality Indicator function specification.....	144
Table 112: Retrieve Quality Indicator function specification	144
Table 113: Remove Policy function specification.....	144
Table 114: Policy Monitoring module specification.....	145
Table 115: Register Policy function specification.....	145
Table 116: Retrieve Policy function specification.....	145
Table 117: Remove Policy function specification.....	145
Table 118: Log Exporter module specification.....	145
Table 119: Forward Logs function specification	146
Table 120: Query Engine module specification	146
Table 121: Alert module specification	146
Table 122: Push alert function specification	146
Table 123: Zero-Touch Provisioning (ZTP) Service specification	148
Table 124: ZTP Manager for Devices module specification	148
Table 125: Discovery of Devices function specification	148
Table 126: Secured Bootstrapping of Devices function specification.....	149
Table 127: Configuration Management of Devices function specification	149
Table 128: ZTP Manager for K8 Clusters module specification	149
Table 129: ClusterDiscovery function specification.....	149
Table 130: Configuration Management of Devices and K8 function specification	149
Table 131: Security Risk Modeller (SRM) Component specification	152
Table 132: Interface module specification	153
Table 133: Web UI function specification	153
Table 134: Keycloak function specification	154
Table 135: MongoDB function specification	154
Table 136: System Model module specification	155

Table 137: Data Transformation function specification.....	155
Table 138: System Model Development function specification	156
Table 139: Risk Treatment Plan (RTP) module specification.....	156
Table 140: Risk Mitigation Strategies function specification	157
Table 141: Software Development Kit (SDK) Component specification.....	159
Table 142: SDK Libraries specification.....	159
Table 143: Libraries that interact with platforms function specification.....	159
Table 144: Libraries that interact with ENACT function specification	159
Table 145: Development Tools specification	159
Table 146: SDK Libraries function specification.....	160
Table 147: Libraries that interact with platforms function	160
Table 148: Documentation module specification.....	160
Table 149: Application Policy Model Component specification.....	162
Table 150: Network Policies module specification	162
Table 151: Validate Network Policy function specification	162
Table 152: Store Network Policy Function specification	163
Table 153: Retrieve Network Policy function specification	163
Table 154: Delete Network Policy function specification	163
Table 155: Storage Policies module specification.....	163
Table 156: Validate Storage Policy function specification.....	163
Table 157: Store Storage Policy function specification	164
Table 158: Retrieve Storage Policy function specification.....	164
Table 159: Delete Storage Policy function specification	164
Table 160: Computational Policies module specification	164
Table 161: Validate Compute Policy function specification	165
Table 162: Store Compute Policy function specification.....	165
Table 163: Retrieve Compute Policy function specification.....	165
Table 164: Delete Compute Policy function specification.....	165
Table 165: Locality Policies module specification.....	166
Table 166: Validate Locality Policy function specification.....	166
Table 167: Store Storage Locality Policy function specification.....	166
Table 168: Retrieve Locality Policy function specification.....	166
Table 169: Delete Locality Policy function specification.....	166
Table 170: Policies Datastore module specification	167
Table 171: Store Policy function specification.....	167
Table 172: Retrieve Policy function specification.....	167
Table 173: Delete Policy function specification.....	167
Table 174: Policy Manager module specification	168
Table 175: Insert Policy function specification.....	168
Table 176: Retrieve Policy function specification.....	168
Table 177: Delete Policy function specification.....	168
Table 178: Technologies and technological modules in the data processing pipeline	175
Table 179: Resources needed for the use-case components.....	180
Table 180: List of metrics per category.....	196
Table 181: Dracena data structures.....	197
Table 182: Resources needed for the use-case components.....	202

List of Figures

Figure 1: Node and edge in a graph.....	25
Figure 2: Data Space Architecture based on IDSA RAM	32
Figure 3. Internal workflow of the Security Risk Modeller	42
Figure 4: Graph Neural Networks: A Review of Methods and Applications	52
Figure 5: Application Control in ENACT	63
Figure 6: Major sports streaming rights acquisitions.....	170
Figure 7: Example of metadata annotations.....	173
Figure 8 - High-level architecture of the use-case data pipelines	174
Figure 9: Fujitsu Mobility Digital Twin setup	186
Figure 10: A standalone customer deployment.....	187
Figure 11: Following diagram between components	189
Figure 12: Fujitsu Mobility Digital Twin high level design.....	190
Figure 13: Data Ingestion.....	190
Figure 14: High Level Overview of Dracena	193
Figure 15: Example of Internals workflow of Digital Twin.....	195
Figure 16: ENACT Project phases	203

List of Abbreviations

AES	Advanced Encryption Standard
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AlaaS	AI as a Service
AIoT	Artificial Intelligence of Things
AMQP	Advanced Message Queuing Protocol
ANN	Artificial Neural Network
API	Application Programming Interface
APK	Android Application Package
APM	Application Programming Model
ARCTUR	ARCTUR RACUNALNISKI INZENIRING DOO
ARDIA	A resource Reference model for Data-Intensive Applications
AutoML	Automated Machine Learning
AWS	Amazon Web Services
Bi-LSTM	Bidirectional LSTM
BioPAX	Biological Pathway Exchange
BSD	Berkeley Software Distribution
CCC	Cognitive Computing Continuum
CEP	Complex Event Processing
CERTH	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS

CI/CD	Continuous Integration / Continuous Delivery
CIA	Confidentiality, Integrity and Availability
CNI	Container Network Interface
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CRUD	CREATE, READ, UPDATE and DELETE
CSF	Cyber Security Framework
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
cuDNN	CUDA Deep Neural Network
D	Deliverable
DB	Database
DCAT	Data Catalog Vocabulary
DDoS	Distributed Denial of Service
DFD	Data Flow Diagram
DFGM	Dynamic Federated Graph-based Modeller of Resources, Devices and Services
DGL	Deep Graph Library
DGM	Dynamic Graph Modeller
DHCP	Dynamic Host Configuration Protocol
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technologies
DNET	DUNAVNET LIMITED
DoA	Description of Action
DPH	Deployment Plan Handler
Dracena	Dynamically Reconfigurable Asynchronous Consistent Event Processing Architecture
DREAD	Damage potential, Reproducibility, Exploitability, Affected users, and Discoverability
DRL	Deep Reinforced Learning
DS4	DIGITAL SYSTEMS 4.0
eBPF	extended Berkley Packet Filters
ECL	ECLIPSE FOUNDATION EUROPE GMBH
ECR	Amazon Elastic Container Registry
EDC	Eclipse Dataspace Components
EDPB	European Data Protection Board
ELK	Elasticsearch, Logstash, and Kibana
eSIM	embedded Subscriber Identity Module
EU	European Union
FDI	FOUR DOT INFINITY INFORMATION AND TELECOMMUNICATIONS SOLUTIONS PRIVATE COMPANY
FL	Federated Learning
FPGA	Field Programmable Gate Arrays
fps	frames per second
FUJ	FUJITSU TECHNOLOGY SOLUTIONS SPZOO
GA4GH	Global Alliance for Genomics and Health
GAT	Graph Attention Network
GCN	Graph Convolutional Network
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GEXF	Graph Exchange XML Format
GIN	Graph Isomorphism Network
GNN	Graph Neural Network

GPL	General Public License
GPS	Global Positioning System
GPU	Graphics processing unit
GraphSAGE	Graph Sample and Aggregation
GSM	Global System for Mobile Communications
GSMA	GSM Association
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HDD	Hard Disk Drive
HDFS	Hadoop Distributed File System
HIPAA	Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act
HPA	Horizontal Pod Autoscaler
HPC	High-Performance Computing
HTML	Hypertext Mark-up Language
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
IaC	Infrastructure as Code
ICCS	EREVNITIKO PANEPISTIMIAKO INSTITOUTO SYSTIMATON EPIKOINONION KAI YPOLOGISTON
ICE	INFORMATION CATALYST SL
ID	Identifier
IDE	integrated development environment
IDSA	International Data Spaces
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
INNO	ASOCIACION DE EMPRESAS TECNOLOGICAS INNOVALIA
IoT	Internet of Things
IoT-SAFE	IoT SIM Applet For Secure End-2-End Communication
IP	Internet Protocol
ISMS	Information Security Management System
ISO	International Standard Organisation
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
K8S	Kubernetes
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LD	Linked Data
LGPL	GNU Lesser General Public License
LLM	Large Language Model
LSTM	long Short-Term Memory
MAAS	Metal as a Service
MEC	Multiple Access Edge Computing
ML	Machine Learning
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
MLP	Multi-Layer Perceptron
MOG	MOG TECHNOLOGIES SA
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
NFV	Network Function Virtualisation
NIC	Network Interface Card

nq	N-Quads
OCI	Oracle Cloud Infrastructure
ODRL	Open Digital Rights Language
OpenWDL	Workflow Description Language
OS	Operating System
OSM	Open Service Mesh
OTA	Over-The-Air
OTel	Open Telemetry Data Format
OWASP	Open Web Application Security Project
OWASP	The Open Web Application Security Project
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PDF	Portable Document Format
PUE	Power Usage Effectiveness
QoE	Quality of Experience
QoS	Quality of Service
RAG	Retrieval-Augmented Generation
RAM	Random Access Memory
RAM	Reference Architecture Model
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RDFS	Resource Description Framework Schema
REST	Representational State Transfer
RL	Reinforcement Learning
RPC	Remote Procedure Call
RT	Real Time
RTM	Risk Treatment Plan
RTP	Risk Treatment Plan
SaaS	Software as a Service
SBML	Systems Biology Markup Language
SDF	Service Description Framework
SDK	Software Development Kit
SDN	Software Defined Networking
SIE	SIEMENS SRL
SLA	Service-Level Agreement
SM	System Model
SOA	Service-Oriented Architectures
Soft-AP	Software-enabled Access Points
SotA	State of the Art
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
SQL	Structured Query Language
SRM	Security Risk Modeller
SSD	Solid State Drive
SSL	Secure Sockets Layer
SSM	Systems Security Modeller
STORE	Security Threat Oriented Requirements Engineering
STRIDE	Spoofing, Tampering, Repudiation, Information Disclosure, Denial of Service, and Elevation of privilege

SVR	Support Vector Regression
T	Task
TBD	To be discussed
TDCME	Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine
TFTP	Trivial File Transfer Protocol
TMT	Microsoft Threat Modelling Tool
TOSCA	Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TTP	Time-To-Provision
UC	Use Case
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
UI	User Interface
UML	Unified Modelling Language
UNP	UNPARALLEL INNOVATION LDA
UOWM	PANEPITIMIO DYTIKIS MAKEDONIAS
UPV	UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA DE VALENCIA
VM	Virtual Machine
VTE	Virtual Training Environment
WP	Work Package
XGMML	eXtensible Graph Markup and Modeling Language
XLS	Microsoft Excel Spreadsheet
XLSX	Microsoft Excel Spreadsheet
XML	Extensible Markup Language
YAML	YAML Ain't Markup Language
ZTP	Zero-Touch Provisioning

1. Executive Summary

This ENACT deliverable **D2.1 (State of the Art Analysis, Vision, & ENACT Specifications)** combines and presents the first iteration of work undertaken in T2.1 (State of Art Analysis and Requirements for Efficient Data Processing in Compute Continuum), T2.2 (Specifications of Innovative Solutions for Efficient Data Processing in the Compute Continuum) and T2.4 (ENACT Use-Case Definitions and Specifications of Use-Case Solutions) of the ENACT project, and includes a thorough analysis of the SotA in research fields relevant to ENACT scopes and objectives; the specification of the ENACT platform and its components; the definitions and specifications of the ENACT Use Cases (UCs); and the Impact and Vision for the ENACT platform as well as the ENACT Pilots.

The deliverable takes into consideration the activities and purposes detailed in the Description of Action (DoA) and presents the outcome of iterative and highly collaborative work performed among technical and UC partners in the frame of ENACT WP2 activities, including the aforementioned Tasks as well as T2.3 (Architecture of the ENACT Cognitive Continuum). Activities were organised by the respective Task leaders and overseen by the WP2 lead and project coordination, ensuring close collaboration among Tasks and partners, and compliance with the ENACT project scopes and objectives as well as with the ENACT platform architecture being prepared in parallel.

In this deliverable, following concrete methodologies, all partners contributed to the SotA analysis, pilot partners provided the definitions and specifications of the UCs and technical partners defined the first version of ENACT platform and components specifications. The results of this work serve mainly as input to the first iteration of requirements analysis and consequently the ENACT platform architecture specification, to enable the commencement of software engineering activities and processes within the project. The supplementary outcomes WP2 work will be presented in deliverables **D2.2 (ENACT User and System Requirements)** and **D2.3 (ENACT Cognitive Compute Continuum Reference Architecture)**.

2. Introduction

2.1 Purpose and scope of the deliverable

The deliverable focuses on three main topics that comprise crucial foundation for the design and implementation of the ENACT platform: the SotA analysis; the specification of the ENACT platform and its components; and the definitions and specifications of the UCs.

State of the Art analysis is a crucial initial step in any research project. It involves a thorough review and evaluation of the latest research, technologies, methodologies, practices, standards, and solutions within relevant scientific fields. This analysis establishes a benchmark for identifying existing knowledge, innovations, and gaps that the project aims to address. By understanding the current landscape, researchers can consolidate foundational concepts, theories, and methodologies essential to the project, and define a precise research focus. SotA analysis prevents redundancy by ensuring researchers are aware of existing work, thus avoiding duplication and promoting innovation by building upon previous research. It also guides the selection of appropriate methodologies and tools, enhancing the rigor of the research. Additionally, SotA

analysis identifies potential collaborators and establishes benchmarks for evaluating progress and outcomes, ensuring the research remains relevant and current. Overall, it grounds the research in current knowledge, addresses genuine gaps, and contributes meaningful advancements to the field.

The specifications of a software system and its components encompass detailed descriptions of the functional and non-functional requirements, architecture, interfaces, and behaviours that the software must exhibit. These specifications provide a comprehensive blueprint for guiding the development, deployment, and maintenance of the software. They outline how different components interact with each other and with external systems, ensuring interoperability and scalability. Clear and detailed specifications are crucial for aligning stakeholders, including developers, project managers and end-users, by providing a common understanding of the system's goals and requirements. This alignment sets realistic expectations and ensures all parties are on the same page regarding the project's scope and deliverables. Specifications act as a roadmap for developers, offering precise guidelines for implementation, reducing ambiguity, and minimising the risk of misinterpretation. They facilitate the identification of potential issues early in the development cycle, allowing for proactive problem-solving and reducing costly rework. Detailed specifications are vital for quality assurance and testing, providing criteria against which the software is validated and verified, ensuring it meets defined requirements and performs as expected. They also support maintenance and scalability, offering a clear reference for future enhancements and modifications. In summary, software specifications ensure stakeholder alignment, guide development, facilitate quality assurance, and support maintenance and scalability, forming the cornerstone of successful software engineering.

Out of these aspects, this deliverable focuses on the ENACT components specifications, while the functional and non-functional requirements and platform architecture are addressed in ENACT deliverables D2.2 (ENACT User and System Requirements) and D2.3 (ENACT Cognitive Compute Continuum Reference Architecture) respectively.

The definitions and specifications of Use Cases in a pilot project refer to detailed descriptions of scenarios in which the software system will be utilised. These UCs outline the interactions between users (or other systems) and the software to achieve specific goals, including the identification of actors, the sequence of actions, expected outcomes, and any variations or exceptions. They also usually detail preconditions that must be met before the UC begins and postconditions that define the system's state after the UC is completed. Defining and specifying UCs is essential for capturing the functional requirements of the system from the user's perspective, ensuring it meets actual needs and expectations. This enhances user satisfaction and system usability. UC specifications facilitate communication among stakeholders, serving as a common language that bridges the gap between technical and non-technical parties. This alignment helps set accurate expectations and avoids misunderstandings that could lead to delays. UCs provide a foundation for testing and validation by offering specific scenarios for developing test cases, ensuring the system is thoroughly tested against real-world conditions. They guide the development process by helping developers understand the context and flow of user interactions, enabling them to design and implement the system more effectively. In summary, UC definitions and specifications are critical for capturing user requirements, facilitating stakeholder communication, guiding development, and ensuring thorough testing and validation. They are essential for successful project execution, ensuring the system meets user needs and operates effectively in real-world scenarios.

The deliverable further presents **the Vision for the ENACT platform as well as the ENACT Pilots.**

Due to the withdrawal of partners associated with Pilot 3 of the ENACT proposal in the early stages of the project, it should be noted that the UC specifications and Vision presented in this deliverable have been provided by the remaining pilot leads MOG, and FUJ. The introduction of a new UC partner to the ENACT project as a replacement for Pilot 3 is currently in process and being finalised, and as the definition and specification of the new Pilot, will be reported in the next iteration of this deliverable.

2.2 Relation to other WPs and tasks

This deliverable is produced within WP2 (Requirements and Specifications for Cognitive Compute Continuum), and the work presented was completed within T2.1 (State of Art Analysis and Requirements for Efficient Data Processing in Compute Continuums); T2.2 (Specifications of Innovative Solutions for Efficient Data Processing in the Compute Continuum); and T2.4 (Use-case definitions and Specifications of Use-Case Definitions). During the completion of this work, there was also close collaboration with T2.3 (Architecture of the ENACT Cognitive Continuum).

2.3 Structure of the deliverable

This deliverable is broken down into the following sections:

- **Section 1 (Executive Summary):** Provides a summary of the most relevant parts of the project in relation to this deliverable.
- **Section 2 (Introduction):** Provides an introduction to this deliverable, which includes the purpose and scope, Relation to other WP's and Tasks, and the Structure of the deliverable.
- **Section 3 (Methodology):** Describes the processes and methods used to distribute and organise work, to collect and analyse the SotA, the UC definitions and specifications, and the ENACT platform specifications.
- **Section 4 (State of the Art and Beyond):** Provides an analysis of the SotA in different key fields of interest to ENACT, including research directions and related work, market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards, and information regarding the ENACT advancements beyond the SotA.
- **Section 5 (ENACT Use Cases Analysis and Specifications):** Provides a general description of each ENACT Pilot, including the opportunities and barriers, motivation, target objectives and key research areas, followed by the UC scenario, including its description, the high-level architecture, involved components, information flows, datasets and models, ENACT impact and benefits, the current status, and testing and validation details.
- **Section 6 (ENACT Platform Specifications):** Provides the specifications of the ENACT platform, including an overview of each component followed by detailed information regarding (as applicable) the component modules, workflow, interactions with other components, prototypical mock-ups of GUIs, pre- and post-ENACT Technology Readiness Level (TRL), applicability in the ENACT Pilots, relevance with layers of the provisional ENACT architecture, and implementation details, such as technologies, frameworks, libraries and tools envisioned to be used, high-level description of the interfaces, deployment type, authorisation details and licensing information. Furthermore, the functional specifications of

the component modules and functions are defined, including description, implementation priority, interactions and success criteria.

- **Section 7 (ENACT Vision):** Provides the goals and aspirations for the ENACT platform as well as the vision for each of the aforementioned Pilots and associated UCs.
- **Section 8 (Conclusions):** Provides concluding remarks and closes the deliverable.

3. Methodology

3.1 Key topics definition and work distribution

The ENACT project brings together UC providers and technical partners to deliver innovative solutions that can radicalise the utilisation and management of a cognitive edge-cloud continuum . At the beginning of WP2 activities, and specifically as part of T2.1, the ENACT consortium, as a whole, undertook a process to identify the key technology areas pertinent to the Project’s scope and objectives. The identification of these areas was informed by the project’s goals and vision, as well as the individual partners’ expertise. This activity resulted in the establishment of ten Key Topics that represent the key innovations in the project, as outlined in Table 1. These Topics form the foundation for a) SotA analysis (in the current deliverable, D2.1) and b) requirements collection and analysis (in deliverable D2.2).

ID	Key Topic	Lead partner	Main Participants	Relevant Tech WP
T01	Computing continuum modelling and visualisation	UPV	ICCS	WP4
T02	Distributed storage and data spaces	CERTH	ARCTUR, INNO	WP4
T03	Risk and compliance	DS4	UOWM	WP4
T04	Zero-touch provisioning services	SIE	-	WP4
T05	Edge-cloud orchestration	UNP	CERTH, ICCS, FDI	WP5
T06	AI Algorithms and training environments	CERTH	UPV, ICCS, FDI	WP5
T07	Application programming models	SIE	ICE	WP6
T08	Application control	ICE	SIE	WP6
T09	Software development kits	SIE	-	WP6
T10	Quality and security for distributed applications	UOMM	DS4	WP6

Table 1: Key Topics

To ensure high quality contributions across all ten innovation Topics within the designated timeframe and work plan, a dedicated working group was established for each Key Topic, comprising both technical and UC partners. These groups were tasked with focusing on the SotA and requirements collection and analysis pertinent to their specific Topic. Based on the partner expertise and effort distribution in T2.1 and the relevant Project Tasks (in WP2 and other technical WPs), each Key Topic was assigned a Lead technical partner and a number of Main (technical) participants, while all technical and UC partners were invited to contribute to the activities related to each Topic. Lead partners were responsible for overseeing work within their Topic, communicating with participants and consolidating the relevant deliverable sections of the deliverables, while the T2.1 leader guided and organised the overall work.

It is noteworthy that the activities in ENACT T2.1 (State of the Art and requirements collection and analysis), T2.2 (ENACT solutions and components specification), T2.3 (Architecture specification) and

T2.4 (ENACT Use Cases definition and specification) were conducted concurrently within WP2. These activities evolved progressively through close collaboration and information sharing among the participants of these Tasks. Additional collaboration between technical and UC partners ensured that the outcomes were highly relevant to the ENACT UC scopes and requirements.

The work was undertaken in several iterations and biweekly calls were held at T2.1, T2.2, T2.3 and T2.4 levels, involving all participating partners. Monthly WP2 and project-level meetings further supported a comprehensive, multi-level work approach. Various tools and techniques were utilised to enhance efficiency and coordination. Online collaboration platforms were employed to facilitate information exchange and track progress. These platforms supported document sharing, version control, and collaborative editing.

3.2 State of the Art collection and analysis methodology

One of the primary activities in T2.1, as presented in this deliverable, was the collection and analysis of the SotA for each Key Topic. In some cases, Subtopics were identified, and the work was distributed among the most relevant partners according to their expertise. For each Topic/Subtopic, participants agreed to focus on the following three areas, which correspond to specific sections of this deliverable:

- **Research directions and related work:** This area focuses on the most recent and relevant research in each Topic. It includes a review of international scientific literature, including the latest contributions from ENACT partners. It also introduces and analyses the experiences of past and ongoing related projects where information is available.
- **Market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards:** This area aims to highlight the most significant and widely used mature solutions and standards of relevance, which are commonly utilised by the industry and in commercial settings. It involves analysing official reports, documents and specifications, presenting the main characteristics and capabilities of these solutions, and assessing their relevance to the ENACT project's scope and objectives.
- **Beyond State of the Art:** This focus area provides detailed information on the technological advancements in each Key Topic within the ENACT project and the specific ENACT components involved. Partner contributions in this area were completed in the final phase, incorporating the latest work on ENACT specifications (T2.2) and Architecture (T2.3) to ensure that the information reflects the actual ENACT platform components to be developed.

The work was conducted and completed in three main rounds of contributions, with improvements made progressively based on discussions at the T2.1 level and the evolution of work in other related Tasks of the Project.

3.3 ENACT platform specifications methodology

The main activity for Task 2.2 was to define the functional and technical specifications for the ENACT CCC platform covering all its components. This was done in close collaboration with other WP2 Tasks such as:

- **T2.1** in order to take into account the findings of state-of-the-art analysis of similar technologies and concepts as well as system requirements as identified and described in this Deliverable.
- **T2.3** in order for each component’s specifications to be in-line with the ENACT architecture and achieve the desired overall ENACT functionality and goals.
- **T2.4** in order to satisfy end-user requirements and the specific needs of the pilot projects.

Once the system and end-user requirements were elicited a high-level architecture was designed with the main components identified. This process was highly iterative since outputs from T2.2 and T2.3 were interlinked, i.e. the functionality and specifications of each component was to a large extent dependent on its neighbouring ones.

Once the required components of the ENACT platform were finalised their specifications were assigned to partners based on two parameters: (i) who was leading a relevant project Task, and (ii) relevant expertise and prior experience.

The next step was to collect the functional specifications of each of the ENACT components using a template and approach based on previous experience from other EU projects where it proved effective for collecting them in a standardised manner. There are three levels of templates used in the same document:

- **ENACT Component** – The overall ENACT Solution as described in the DoA (Table 2).
- **Module** – A specific area in the ENACT Solution that may contain many functions (if applicable) (Table 3).
- **Function** – A specific function or component in the app, dedicated to one, or one type of task (Table 4).

After one iteration, where component (i) Interfaces and (ii) Technologies fields were added, the templates used were finalised as follows.

Component Name	<The name of the ENACT component>
Intro / Overview	<Provide a short summary of the main modules and functionalities to be implemented in the ENACT Component.>
Extracted Modules	<Provide a bulleted list of all Modules available in the ENACT Component. For each Module listed, the Module Specification Template should be duplicated and completed.>
Component Workflow	<Identify and describe the overall flow of control via activity diagrams to be implemented by the ENACT Component. In the activity diagram of a component, graphical representations of a limited number of shapes, connected with arrows are provided to show component activities (also data exchanged).>
External Component Interaction	<Describes component interactions with other connected components of the ENACT platform. It is described which input data is demanded and which output data is provided.>
Prototypical Mock-ups	<Mock-ups to visualise a first draft of possible implementations of User Interfaces. These Mock-ups are in a prototypical state and do not represent the final User Interface at the end of the project. They only serve as guidelines for further implementations.>
TRL	<Provide the Technology Readiness Level of the proposed component>
Potential Use-cases	<Describe the Use Case where this component could be applied>
Layer	<The Layer in the proposed architecture where this component belongs to>
Technologies	<Technologies, frameworks, libraries, tools that you envision of using>
Interfaces	<High-level description of interfaces including:

	Overview: a description of the interface Type: e.g. REST State: Synchronous or asynchronous Data Format: e.g. JSON >
Deployment Type	<e.g. Hardware vs Software>
Authorisation Definition	<Licensing and Permissions that are needed to use Modules, Functions, and UI elements of the ENACT component for the respective user.>
Licence	<State the licence of the overall ENACT component. E.g. GPL, LGPL, Apache License 2.0, BSD, MIT>

Table 2: ENACT Component Functional Specification Template

Module Name	<The name of the module should be defined wisely, to indicate the meaning based on the name>	Priority	<Must / Should / Nice to have>
Description	<Describes the meaning of the Module – i.e., what the module does and which result(s) can be achieved.>		
Interacts with	<Provide a bulleted list of all modules that interact directly with this module>		
Extracted Functions	<Provide a bulleted list of all Functions available in the ENACT Module. For each function listed, the Function Specification Template should be duplicated and completed.>		
Success Criteria	<Describes the minimal criteria, which the implementation should fulfil, related to the requirements of D2.1.>		

Table 3: Module Functional Specification Template (if applicable)

Function Name	<The name of the function should be defined wisely, to indicate the meaning based on the name>	Priority	<Must / Should / Nice to have>
Description	<Describes the meaning of the Function – i.e., what the function does and which result(s) can be achieved.>		
Interacts with	< Provide a bulleted list of all functions that interact directly with this function>		
Success Criteria	<Describes the minimal criteria, which the implementation should fulfil, related to the requirements of D2.1.>		

Table 4: Function Specification Template

Since the result of T2.1 (Specifications) was to a large extent the output of T2.3 (Architecture) and vice-versa, several revisions of the component specifications were required with improvements made progressively based on scheduled WP2-wide bi-weekly calls, dedicated Slack¹ channel and one-to-one discussions. T2.2 and T2.3 leaders were tasked with coordinating these activities and making sure there were no discrepancies with the overall architecture as well as between neighbouring components.

3.4 Use Cases definition and specifications methodology

The methodology for use-case definition and specification involved several key phases. Initially, the focus was on **Requirements Gathering**. This involved engaging other consortium partners, end-users, and other relevant parties. A detailed analysis was also performed during this phase to

¹ <https://slack.com/>

identify specific needs and scenarios, which helped in pinpointing what needed to be specified for each UC.

Once requirements were gathered, the **Specification Development** phase commenced. A standardised template was prepared and shared to facilitate information collection. This template ensured consistency in capturing details across different UCs.

The work organisation for the project was structured around **rounds and iterations of contributions**. The information collection and specification processes were iterative, with multiple rounds allowing for incremental improvements and refinements. Feedback loops were integral to this process, as initial drafts were reviewed, and feedback was provided to contributors for necessary **revisions**.

There was also significant **collaboration with other tasks** within the project to ensure that the specifications were aligned with the overall project goals and integrated seamlessly with other work packages. **Task meetings** facilitated the exchange of information and alignment of efforts.

By applying this structured methodology, the ENACT project was able to develop detailed, accurate, and comprehensive specifications for platform components and UCs. The iterative approach, combined with effective stakeholder engagement and collaboration across tasks, ensured the success of the requirements and specification process.

4. State of the Art analysis and beyond

This section presents the SotA analysis performed by the ENACT consortium, grouped per Key Topic and focusing in three areas (as already explained in section 3.2): Research directions and related work; Market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards; Beyond State of the Art.

4.1 Computing continuum modelling and visualisation

4.1.1 Research directions and related work

4.1.1.1 *Computing continuum modelling*

Modelling the various entities and data types of a computing continuum ecosystem in a detailed and usable manner constitutes a crucial foundation for enabling the realisation of a computing continuum that supports real-time visibility, automatic discovery, dynamic deployment, predictive management and real-time self-adaptation of federated resources. Data modelling and representation aspects involve how information is structured, encoded, and manipulated to successfully facilitate the exchange of needed data as well as its usage for demanding cognitive tasks, such as learning, reasoning and decision-making. The advance specification of data elements' format, structure, and meaning not only streamlines the development of pertinent systems by ensuring inclusion of all crucial parameters but also shields against potential errors, such as data misinterpretation.

The computing continuum infrastructure encompasses various types of resources, usually including edge and cloud computing infrastructures and fog computing nodes. Edge infrastructure

includes the hardware and software resources deployed at the edge of the network to facilitate local processing, storage, and analysis of data. It typically features edge servers, gateways, and devices like sensors, smartphones, and IoT devices. Additionally, various resources such as NICs and accelerators (e.g., GPU, FPGA) with diverse capabilities may be connected to these entities. Cloud computing infrastructure, made available by cloud service providers, offers on-demand access to computing resources over the internet, including virtual machines, storage, and networking. Fog computing extends the cloud computing paradigm to the network edge, delivering computing, storage, and networking services closer to end-users or data sources through fog nodes, which communicate with both edge devices and cloud infrastructure.

Optimal deployment of applications or services in the available computing continuum resources requires comprehensive consideration of several key parameters. Latency requirements guide decisions on processing location at the edge or the cloud, balancing real-time responsiveness with available computational resources. Bandwidth needs for data transmission between edge devices, fog nodes, and cloud infrastructure must be evaluated to ensure efficient data transfer and minimise network congestion. Scalability demands dynamic resource allocation across the continuum to accommodate fluctuating workloads. Security measures, including data encryption and access control, are essential for protecting sensitive information and privacy. Cost and energy considerations, covering infrastructure provisioning, maintenance, and operational expenses, guide the development of cost-effective and energy-efficient deployment strategies optimising resource utilisation and/or minimise energy consumption while meeting application requirements.

Enabling real-time visibility and automatic resource discovery in the cloud continuum depends on effective monitoring, metadata management, and standardised communication protocols. Robust monitoring mechanisms continuously collect telemetry data, providing insights into resource status and performance metrics such as CPU utilisation, network latency, and storage availability. Effective metadata management indexes and categorises resources based on their attributes and relationships, facilitating rapid and accurate discovery. These parameters are crucial for establishing a dynamic and responsive cloud continuum ecosystem supporting diverse applications and workloads with agility and scalability.

Telemetry data play a vital role in facilitating optimal orchestration in the computing continuum, providing real-time insights into resources performance and state. Continuous monitoring of metrics like CPU utilisation, memory usage, network latency and storage capacity across edge devices, fog nodes, and cloud infrastructure allows orchestration systems to dynamically adjust resource allocation and workload distribution to optimise performance and resource utilisation. Historical telemetry data offer valuable insights for predictive orchestration, enabling anticipation of future resource demands and proactive adjustments to accommodate expected workloads. By combining historical telemetry data with real-time monitoring, organisations can enhance system efficiency, reliability and agility, and mitigate performance degradation risks. Intelligent application orchestration is further enhanced by combining historical telemetry data on particular applications' deployment outcomes with the characteristics of the involved resources. This approach harnesses data from various sources in a combinatory manner, enabling optimal predictive dynamic orchestration.

To accomplish the objectives of the ENACT continuum, data from all the previously mentioned sources and categories, including applications and services, resources and devices, as well as telemetry, must undergo appropriate modelling and be made accessible for utilisation by the

platform and its diverse components. The models developed should exhibit a level of representability and expressibility adequate to encompass the mentioned scopes comprehensively.

A recent work on A resource Reference model for Data-Intensive Applications (ARDIA) Framework [1] introduces a collection of models that provide a rich semantic representation of the concepts for the overall description of application / service, resource / device and telemetry data in the context of data-intensive security-critical applications, and enables the specification of relations among these entities. The ARDIA Framework, developed in the EU-funded SERRANO project², has been used as the foundation of a robust architecture aimed at enhancing cloud continuum application deployment and execution through intent-based AI-enhanced orchestration. It contains three fundamental models. The Application Model, describes applications and services in terms of their high-level requirements, which include design, intent, implementation details, and deployment constraints. It serves as a framework for specifying what the application needs to function optimally in a computing continuum environment, also capturing the overall goal and requirements of the application provider in an abstract, infrastructure-independent manner. It can further capture the internal application components and workflow on the basis of OpenWDL (for more information please refer to section 4.1.2.1). The Resource Model, compatible with TOSCA (for more information please refer to section 4.1.2.1), details the physical and software resources available in the infrastructure. It outlines the performance aspects, security capabilities, utilisation, and deployment specifics of each resource as well as connected entities and accelerators, providing a comprehensive view of the infrastructure capabilities. The Telemetry Data Model is used for capturing and managing the telemetry data from the applications deployed in the continuum resources, further enabling evaluation of application execution and quality of experience. It focuses on runtime measurements, storing data in a time-series database, which aids in monitoring and decision-making processes related to predictive orchestration. These models interact through a series of AI-driven processes and mapping rules, facilitating dynamic and efficient application deployment. The architecture leverages Machine Learning (ML) to enhance the decision-making process, ensuring that the deployments are optimally aligned with the application and user requirements, and the available resources. This system showcases the potential of integrating AI with cloud resource management to adapt swiftly to changing application needs and environments.

4.1.1.2 Visualisation tools

Graph visualisation, also known as network visualisation or link analysis, is a method for visually depicting the relationships between different data entities. A node-link model is the most effective method for graph visualisation, with nodes representing entities and links depicting their connections.

These nodes and links (Figure 1) can represent any kind of information, such as transactions between accounts, devices connected in a network, or communications between friends. Their size or content of data does not matter, as long as there are connections between the data that can be visualised/draw in a graph way. This visualisation is not static. It can be characterised by filtering data. Graphs are mainly used in very complex data structures with huge amounts of data that could

² SERRANO - Transparent Application Deployment in a Secure, Accelerated and Cognitive Cloud Continuum. Grant agreement ID: 101017168. <https://ict-serrano.eu/>

be difficult to process and relate directly with the raw data, but it could be easy to digest and understand if the data is shown as a graph.

Figure 1: Node and edge in a graph

Graph visualisation tools are software programs designed to transform complex network data into clear and understandable visual representations. These tools help researchers, analysts, and anyone working with interconnected information to explore relationships, identify patterns, and gain insights from their data.

These kinds of tools were developed mainly as desktop applications that must be installed in a computer and used to analyse local data. Actually, with the advances of microservices technology these tools have evolved from desktop app's to code libraries to be used directly by almost any programming language. These libraries, open the possibility to adapt almost any frontend technology to be able to represent graphs. It is true that libraries are not as powerful as original desktop applications, especially in the use of resources being less capable compared to desktop applications, but for some applications that will process little size data sets is more than enough.

4.1.2 Market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards

4.1.2.1 Computing continuum modelling

Starting from more generic approaches, the Service Description Framework (SDF) [2] provides a standardised way to describe applications and services, including their capabilities, interfaces, and requirements. It facilitates service discovery, composition, and interoperability in distributed systems. SDF is commonly used in Service-Oriented Architectures (SOA) and web services. For modelling resources and devices, the Resource Description Framework (RDF) [3] can be used. It is a flexible data model for representing resources and their relationships in a graph format. It provides a standard syntax for expressing metadata about resources on the Web. RDF is widely used in the context of the Semantic Web for describing resources and enabling interoperability. On the other hand, the Unified Modelling Language (UML)³ can be used to create models for representing Telemetry Data structures, including data types, measurements, and events. UML provides a standardised notation for designing and visualising data models, making it suitable for capturing complex telemetry data schemas. Time Series Data Models [4], which are specialised for representing temporal data usually collected from sensors or devices over time, can be used for storing telemetry data. These models often include W3C Recommendation features for

³ Object Management Group. Unified Modelling Language (UML). OMG Specification. <https://www.omg.org/spec/UML/>

timestamping, interpolation, and aggregation of time-series data. Finally, the Open Telemetry Data Format (OTel)⁴ is an open-source standard for representing telemetry data collected from distributed systems and applications. It provides a vendor-neutral format for exporting metrics, traces, and logs, enabling interoperability and observability across different platforms.

Applications usually consist of services or microservices executed in a specific order. The Workflow Description Language (OpenWDL)⁵ standard provides a robust framework for describing and executing computational workflows in a scalable and reproducible manner. Developed by the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH), OpenWDL offers a structured syntax for defining workflows comprising multiple tasks and dependencies, facilitating interoperability across different workflow execution engines and environments. Its declarative nature allows users to specify computational tasks, inputs, outputs, and dependencies concisely, enabling automated execution and portability across various computational platforms. OpenWDL's flexibility and extensibility make it suitable for a wide range of scientific applications, empowering researchers to design, share, and execute complex computational workflows efficiently. This standardisation greatly enhances collaboration, reproducibility, and scalability.

Particularly in the realm of cloud applications, the OASIS Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications (TOSCA)⁶ aids system administrators or software agents, such as orchestration components, in configuring applications and their underlying infrastructure, as well as managing them. TOSCA-based orchestration relies on YAML Ain't Markup Language (YAML)⁷, a human-readable data serialisation language commonly used for configuration files. YAML is also extensively used by Kubernetes (K8s)⁸ for defining and configuring resources such as pods, deployments, services, and more. In Kubernetes, YAML files serve as the primary means of declaring the desired state of the system, specifying attributes, configurations, and relationships between various components. YAML's human-readable syntax and structure make it easy for developers and administrators to write and understand configuration files, allowing them to define complex deployments and manage Kubernetes resources effectively. By leveraging YAML, Kubernetes provides a standardised and intuitive way to define, manage, and orchestrate containerised applications and microservices within a cluster environment, facilitating efficient deployment, scaling, and management of distributed systems.

Semantic Web [5] technologies, including RDF⁹, RDFS¹⁰, and OWL¹¹, facilitate the representation of knowledge in a machine-processable format, typically in the form of ontologies [6]. These

⁴ OpenTelemetry Community. OpenTelemetry Specification. GitHub Repository, <https://github.com/open-telemetry/opentelemetry-specification>

⁵ Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH). Workflow Description Language (OpenWDL). <https://github.com/ga4gh/workflow-execution-service-schemas>

⁶ Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications (TOSCA) Version 1.0 OASIS Standard. <http://docs.oasis-open.org/tosca/TOSCA/v1.0/TOSCA-v1.0.html>

⁷ YAML Ain't Markup Language™. <https://yaml.org/>

⁸ Kubernetes open-source system for automating deployment, scaling, and management of containerised applications. <https://kubernetes.io/>

⁹ Resource Description Framework (RDF). World Wide Web Consortium (W3C). (2004). RDF 1.1 Concepts and Abstract Syntax. <https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf11-concepts/>

¹⁰ Resource Description Framework Schema (RDFS). World Wide Web Consortium (W3C). (2014). RDF Schema 1.1. <https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-schema/>

ontologies can be precisely interpreted by software agents, enabling them to address complex relationships and data retrieval needs effectively. Semantic and Knowledge Graphs [7] serve as potent data representations, capturing intricate relationships and semantics between entities. Widely utilised in cognitive computing systems, these graphs facilitate the representation of structured knowledge, enabling advanced reasoning and inference capabilities. Techniques such as RDF (Resource Description Framework) and SPARQL (SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language)¹² are commonly employed for querying and manipulating semantic data. Ontologies, on the other hand, offer a formal and explicit specification of a shared conceptualisation within a specific domain. They delineate concepts, relationships, and constraints, thereby fostering interoperability and knowledge sharing among diverse cognitive systems. Vital in representing domain-specific knowledge, ontologies are instrumental in enabling semantic reasoning.

4.1.2.2 Visualisation tools

Here's a comparison among the most popular open-source tools for graph visualisation:

- **Gephi**¹³ [8] [9]: Gephi is a free and open-source software program that's specifically designed for network analysis and visualisation. Developed by a diverse community of researchers and developers, Gephi provides a user-friendly platform for exploring and understanding the relationships within networks of various kinds, including social networks, biological networks, transportation networks among others.
 - Usability: Intuitive graphical interface that is easy to use, suitable for users without programming experience.
 - Features: Real-time visualisation, support for large networks, dynamic layout algorithms, and interactive manipulation capabilities.
 - Customisation: Allows customisation of the visualisation with various layout algorithms and has extensible plugins like MultiViz for multilayer visualisation.
 - Data Handling Capabilities: Excellent for dynamically changing data and visualising complex structures.
 - Graph input format:
 - Desktop application: GEXF, GDF, GML, GraphML, Pajek NET, GraphViz DOT, CSV, UCINET DL, Tulip TPL, Netdraw VNA, Spreadsheet
 - Web Based: GEXF, GraphML
 - Type: Desktop application and Web Based (lite) version.
- **Graphviz**¹⁴: Graphviz is a software toolkit primarily designed for the creation and visualisation of diagrams specified in the DOT language. Originally developed by AT&T Labs, Graphviz was later released as open-source software under the Eclipse Public License.

¹¹ Web Ontology Language (OWL). World Wide Web Consortium (W3C). (2012). OWL 2 Web Ontology Language Document Overview (Second Edition). <https://www.w3.org/TR/owl2-overview/>

¹² SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language. World Wide Web Consortium (W3C). (2008). SPARQL Query Language for RDF. <https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-sparql-query/>

¹³ Jacomy M. Gephi Lite. Gephi blog. 2022. <https://gephi.wordpress.com/2022/11/15/gephi-lite/>

¹⁴ Graphviz. <https://graphviz.org/>

- Usability: More oriented towards users with programming skills; used via scripts.
 - Features: Strong in creating structured diagrams; uses DOT language to describe graphs.
 - Customisation: Less interactive in real-time but very flexible in generating complex static graphics.
 - Data Handling Capabilities: Ideal for static visualisations and complex flowcharts.
 - Graph input format: DOT.
 - Type: Desktop application and library.
- **Cytoscape**¹⁵: Cytoscape is an open-source bioinformatics software platform designed to visualise intricate molecular interaction networks and seamlessly integrate with gene expression profiles and other pertinent data. Beyond its core functionalities, Cytoscape boasts a wealth of additional features accessible through plugins. These plugins expand the platform's capabilities to encompass network and molecular profiling analyses, introduce novel layouts, broaden support for various file formats, and establish connections with databases, facilitating efficient searches within expansive networks.
 - Usability: Graphical interface focused on computational biology and molecular networks.
 - Features: Excellent for the analysis of biological networks, integration of biomedical data, and interactive visualisation.
 - Customisation: Wide range of plugins for specific analysis in the biological domain.
 - Data Handling Capabilities: Specially designed to handle specific attributes of biological data.
 - Graph input format: SIF, GML, XGMML, SBML, BioPAX, GraphML, Delimited text, XLS, XLSX, Cytoscape.js JSON, Cytoscape CX.
 - Type: Desktop application.
- **NetworkX**¹⁶: NetworkX is a Python library designed for exploring graphs and conducting network analysis. It's freely available under the BSD-new license. NetworkX excels at handling extensive real-world graphs, including those with more than 10 million nodes and 100 million edges. Leveraging a pure Python data structure known as a "dictionary of dictionary," NetworkX proves to be a reasonably efficient and highly adaptable framework, making it an excellent choice for analysing both social and general networks
 - Usability: Python library, requires programming skills for effective use.
 - Features: Strong in modelling, transforming, and analysing complex graphs; not focused on visualisation.
 - Customisation: Highly customizable through code; integrates well with other Python libraries for visualisation like Matplotlib.

¹⁵ What is Cytoscape? https://cytoscape.org/what_is_cytoscape.html

¹⁶ NetworkX. <https://networkx.org/>

- Data Handling Capabilities: Excellent for algorithmic network analysis but does not provide advanced visualisation tools directly.
- Graph input format: DOT, GEXF, GraphML, JSON, LEDA, SpareGraph6, Pajek, Matrix Market, Network text.
- Type: Library

The choice of tool depends on the type of data, the analysis goals, the need for visualisation interactivity, user's skills and type of application. Gephi excels in interactive and dynamic visualisations with an easy-to-use interface, making it popular in fields outside of computational biology, unlike Cytoscape, which is preferred in that field for its specific capabilities. Graphviz and NetworkX offer strong programming capabilities for technical users, preferred in scenarios where extensive automation and customisation in graph generation are required.

Another thing to take into consideration is the type of software in which each tool is packed. Nowadays with the containerisation and microservices as the standard for the architecture of any project/IT solution it is difficult to include/adapt a desktop application to be used in this kind of environment. Apart that it is possible that the performance of the desktop version won't be the same than the original one, so a library or web-based solutions are more suitable for this kind of actual standards. For this reason, Gephi in their Web Based version is the only tool that could be easily adapted to be used as a microservice and hence with actual standards.

4.1.3 Beyond State of the Art

4.1.3.1 *Computing continuum modelling*

Conceptual modelling often stems from the specific purposes it aims to fulfil. Consequently, the parameters defined for a particular domain heavily rely on decisions made during system design, such as the chosen design paradigm and classification axes. Adopting models developed for alternative purposes presents significant challenges, necessitating a complex transformation process with potentially ambiguous outcomes. This process assumes precise mapping of elements from existing specifications to those explicitly or implicitly dictated by the specific needs of ENACT. Independent design of applications and corresponding models exacerbates this mapping process, particularly when dealing with partially overlapping knowledge domains, leading to potential oversights or mismatches in element mapping. Anticipating the goals and necessary parameters for system functionality is critical during model design, enabling the identification of potential issues. Accordingly, investigating the formal expression of various concepts, their potential relationships, and their impact on service execution is essential. Enabling interoperable representation of critical model elements and their relationships facilitates the application of these models to address ENACT's needs and objectives, particularly concerning optimal orchestration and interaction among platform components.

In light of this, certain works outlined in the preceding section demonstrate notable relevance to the objectives and requirements of ENACT. As a result, we intend to conduct a thorough examination of these works, with the possibility of leveraging them as foundational resources. If deemed pertinent, we aim to build upon, integrate, and extend these works, utilising them as a basis for designing and implementing the ENACT CCC Models, a data modelling framework tailored to the needs of ENACT. These models will facilitate the representation of essential concepts and data required for ENACT's objectives. Specifically, they will support the seamless integration of

relevant ENACT platform components, such as the Dynamic Graph Modeller, the Orchestrator, the AI Forecaster, the Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine, the Data Manager, the APM, the Application Controller and the Application Policy Model, and enable the realisation of a fully integrated computing continuum. This continuum will prioritise trustworthy and secure communication and service execution across various levels, while embracing features such as discoverability, dynamic deployments, data management, and intelligent predictive and real-time orchestration.

The development of the data modelling framework will entail close collaboration with all ENACT Tasks impacted by relevant decisions, ensuring comprehensive consideration of all requirements. The models will undergo iterative improvement and evolution in alignment with the specifications as well as emerging needs and requirements of the ENACT platform and its components as design and implementation proceed.

Moreover, we will assess and strive for compatibility with established and widely recognised standards in the pertinent domains, aiming to implement models and components that seamlessly integrate with other systems. If relevant, ENACT will actively collaborate with existing or emerging standardisation initiatives in the field, with the intention of contributing where feasible.

4.1.3.2 Visualisation tools

The proposed ENACT modelling environment is the main outcome of T4.2. It will advance the state-of-the-art in cloud-edge continuum visualisation and optimisation by leveraging the power of graph theory and Graph Neural Networks (GNNs). The visualisation tool will represent the continuum information collected through the Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine and the Zero-Touch Provisioning services.

At the core of the modelling environment will be a graph-based representation of the cloud-edge continuum. Each node in the graph will represent a computing resource, whether it be a cloud data centre, an edge server, or an IoT device. The edges between nodes will represent the network connections, with attributes such as bandwidth, latency, and reliability associated with each edge.

This graph-based representation will allow for a rich and intuitive visualisation of the complex cloud-edge ecosystem. Users will be able to easily navigate the topology, inspect the properties of individual nodes and edges, and understand the interconnections between different components. This level of visibility is crucial for effectively managing and optimising the cloud-edge continuum.

DGM will provide graph information to DRL, AI forecaster and GNN components to predict optimal configurations for the cloud-edge continuum. This will allow the modelling environment to show changes in the network topology, resource allocation, or application deployment.

The key innovations of the proposed modelling environment are:

- **Comprehensive visualisation:** The graph-based representation of the cloud-edge continuum will provide a level of visibility and understanding that is not possible with traditional visualisation tools.
- **Predictive capabilities:** The integration of AI components will enable the modelling environment to go beyond simple visualisation and provide actionable insights for optimising the cloud-edge continuum.

- **Scalability and flexibility:** The graph-based approach and the use of GNNs will allow the modelling environment to scale to large, complex cloud-edge systems and adapt to a wide range of UCs and requirements.

4.2 Distributed storage and data spaces

4.2.1 Research directions and related work

The Commission is determined to make this Europe's "Digital Decade"¹⁷. Europe must now strengthen its digital sovereignty and set standards, rather than following those of others – with a clear focus on data, technology, and infrastructure.

Federated cloud environments such as GAIA-X¹⁸ and initiatives like IDSA¹⁹ and FIWARE²⁰ deliver infrastructure, reference architectures and formal standards to enable secure and trustworthy data-sharing [10] [11]. These initiatives provide complete frameworks for data sharing including:

- Business level that describes the roles of participants in a data space such as data owner, data provider/consumer, service provider, etc.
- Functional level that describes all the necessary components should be included in a data sharing ecosystem such data connectors, metadata registry service, etc.
- Process level that includes all the interactions and connections between the various components in a data sharing ecosystem.
- Information level that is just the modelling of both components and stakeholders.
- System level that instantiates the previous levels, so components, their connectors and the actual actors to setup an operational system to enable the shafting of data.

Based on popular standards^{21 22}, secure and trustworthy data sharing can be supported by data connectors and APIs (Open API standards), with security delegated in third-party components. Current approaches^{23 24 25} are based on containers and virtualisation concepts, and they are mainly focused on data sharing. This containers based approach enables data connectors and other related components to be packed over an OS, to include an application container manager that enables the execution of a specific application alongside with containers for the configuration of a data connector during runtime.

¹⁷ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age_en

¹⁸ <https://www.data-infrastructure.eu/GAIA-X/Navigation/EN/Home/home.html>

¹⁹ <https://internationaldataspaces.org/>

²⁰ <https://www.fiware.org/>

²¹ <https://internationaldataspaces.org/ids-officially-a-standard-din-spec-27070-is-published/>

²² <https://internationaldataspaces.org/dataspace-protocol-ensuring-data-space-interoperability/>

²³ <https://fiware-tutorials.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

²⁴ <https://international-data-spaces-association.github.io/DataspaceConnector/>

²⁵ <https://projects.eclipse.org/projects/technology.edc>

In particular, the various approaches related to data spaces are built over the IDSA Reference Architecture Model (IDSA RAM²⁶). It defines all the roles in a data sharing ecosystem, the sharing policies and the major software components:

- Connector: It is a dedicated software component that allows participants to attach usage policies to their data in a data space and enforce the usage policies. This component acts as a gateway for data and services.
- Metadata Broker/Registry: It offers information about data sources in terms of content, structure quality, etc.
- Clearing House: It is the service for logging and keeping track of all data exchange and financial transactions within a data space.
- Vocabularies: They are mainly data models and ontologies that are related to specific domains/UCs and aim to describe the structure of the data that are transferred.
- Identity Provider: This software component creates, maintains, manages and validates identity information of and for participants in a data space.
- App Store: It provides applications that can be deployed in Connectors to execute various tasks like data analytics, etc.

Figure 2: Data Space Architecture based on IDSA RAM

As the core component is the Data Connector, the different relevant initiatives and foundations has developed relevant components. FIWARE has introduced its connector²⁷, that is based in FIWARE's core component, the ORION Context Broker. It uses Keycloak to issue certificates, Keyrock for

²⁶ <https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/knowledge-base/ids-ram-4.0>

²⁷ <https://github.com/FIWARE/data-space-connector>

authorisation and both SQL and no-SQL databases for storing data. Eclipse Foundation has also introduced a series of Data Space components based on IDSA principles. However, the only operational component there is the EDC connector. It is based on Dataspace Connector Java implementation and it is expected to provide extra functionalities such as federated cache for metadata, etc. EDC connectors were combined with GAIA-X infrastructure (that it focuses on sovereign cloud services and cloud infrastructure) to enable the setup of Catena-X²⁸ and Eona-X²⁹ data spaces.

However, in the distributed applications the need for sharing of data (as chunks and streams) is often complemented by the need for sharing data objects [12]. Regarding the objects sharing and distributed management, there are some distributed storages coming from academia, such as BSC dataClay [13], i.e., a distributed data store that enables applications to store and access objects in the same format they have in memory. However, they are not designed to support the notion of trusted shared dataspace and are bounded by proprietary software and platforms.

4.2.2 Market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards

Various market-ready solutions have been developed so far related to data sharing and data space technologies.

- **Telekom DIH Connector**³⁰: T-Systems has developed IDS certified, Gaia-X compliant, cloud agnostic, plug-and-play connectors. It supports HTTPs communication protocol and Identity Management both Centralised (X.509) and Decentralised (did:web). Available for both cloud and edge deployment.
- **Tritom Enterprise Connector**³¹: It enables data source and target systems technical connectivity to the Tritom service to produce services based on data sovereignty principles. Tritom also brings together ecosystem parties and provides the capabilities to create data and service catalogues. It supports REST communication protocol. Available for both cloud and edge deployment.
- **Trusted Supplier Connector**³²: German Edge Cloud GmbH & Co offers its connector that supports IDS Multipart, HTTP, Cloud Events and IDS Header for communication. Available for both cloud and edge deployment
- **TRUE Connector**³³ : Engineering Ingegneria Informatica has developed this connector that enables the trusted data exchange in order to be an active part of an IDS Ecosystem, a virtual data space leveraging existing standards and technologies, as well as governance models well accepted in the data economy, to facilitate secure and standardised data exchange and data linkage in a trusted business ecosystem. The TRUE connector is also part of the Fiware Catalogue. It supports IDS Multipart and IDS protocol (IDSCP) for communication. Available for both cloud and edge deployment.

²⁸ <https://catena-x.net/en/>

²⁹ <https://eona-x.eu/>

³⁰ <https://dih.telekom.com/>

³¹ <https://www.dataspace.fi/en/data-intermediation-service>

³² <https://gec.io/solutions/gaia-x-dienste/>

³³ <https://github.com/Engineering-Research-and-Development/true-connector>

Besides Data Spaces, market ready solution are available related to distributed data storage with a key representative to be Amazon S3³⁴. It is an object storage service offering industry-leading scalability, data availability, security, and performance. It is created to enable the storage and retrieval of any size of data and provides services for data protection and security, access control and management

4.2.3 Beyond State of the Art

ENACT will create its own data space to be used for data exchange across the Cognitive Computing Continuum and its pilot cases by aiming to combine these two core concepts of European research, the compute continuums and data spaces. More specifically, ENACT aims to provide a Secure and Sovereign Distributed Data Storage comprising of (i) Data Stores distributed across the cloud and edge nodes of the ENACT continuum, (ii) a Data Manager that is responsible for identity and access management, handles metadata and monitors the Distributed Data Storage's health, and (iii) Sharing Interfaces for data exchange with external ENACT components. The latter will employ Data Space Connectors to ensure that data is shared among different parties in a secure and sovereign manner.

Moreover, ENACT will try move a step further from data sharing to an innovative sharing of (data) objects between the applications that will be associated with the concept of data space. The faster implementation of distributed and dynamic ENACT applications will be enabled as the dataspace will act as a kind of a distributed data store that can manage the localisation and dynamism requirements of the application. The shared object space can be used by different components or services ranging from those running at edge devices to HPC clusters

4.3 Risk and compliance

Risk and compliance are achieved in ENACT's CCC by addressing both technical and regulatory aspects of the system as a whole to make it secure and in accordance with legal requirements such as GDPR and AI act. Large amount of sensitive data processed in the edge-to-cloud continuum makes it vulnerable to security breaches and unauthorised access. ENACT performs security risk modelling based on ISO 27005 for risk management which provides framework for information security management systems. Also, the data used by the ENACT's solutions will be assessed to check their adherence to the principles of AI act addressing transparency, trustworthiness and accountability of high-risk applications. The process of checking compliance of data with AI act will be automated in the ENACT.

4.3.1 Research directions and related work

4.3.1.1 Security Risk Modelling

With a rapid increase in demand for data intensive applications, the need for distributed data processing through extended edge services and reduced latency is ever increasing. Introduction of cognitive capabilities into computing environment such as edge, fog and cloud computing ensure that processing capabilities are distributed and operational across different layers of the network.

³⁴ <https://aws.amazon.com/s3/>

The combination of cognitive computing with cloud computing results in real-time decision making, enhanced big data analytics, cost and resource efficiency.

To take full advantage of the Cognitive Computing Continuum (CCC) in a secure and trustworthy approach, multiple (layers of) cloud, edge and IoT platforms need to be continually analysed for cybersecurity threats. Cybersecurity means protecting digital information in the cyber environment which is a collection of networking devices, infrastructure, applications, communications protocols, and services. Proactive and automated mechanisms should be applied for risk analysis and mitigation to ensure the security and privacy of data and applications in such an interconnected distributed environment. To handle cybersecurity utilising International Standard Organisation (ISO) standards, security elements such as integrity, identification, privacy, durability, physical security must be considered for distributed applications in the CCC. Following is a list of security threats faced by applications in the CCC:

1. Data security and privacy: Any unauthorised access to sensitive data stored on the cloud can cause data breaches. Inadequate protection of data can lead to data leakage.
2. Compliance and legal risks: Applications stored/process using cloud infrastructure must comply with regulations such as General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA). Data stored within the cloud environment must follow the laws of the country where the data centres are located.
3. Adversarial attacks: Cognitive systems based on ML can face adversarial attacks due to model manipulation through feeding manipulated data into system to affect its outcome. It is also vulnerable to data poisoning where the malicious data is injected into the training data.
4. Operational risk: Service downtime and integrity of data must be considered to avoid impacting applications outcome and reliability.
5. Security threats: Applications in the CCC are vulnerable to various cyber threats such as Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) [14] attacks, malware, and ransomware.
 - DDoS attack tries to disturb the normal traffic of a server by flooding it with traffic from multiple sources. These types of attacks exhaust the resources i.e. bandwidth, CPU and memory decreasing the availability to the legitimate users in the cloud computing environment.
 - Malware [15] imposes threats due to misconfiguration, unpatched software, phishing and infected data.
 - Ransomware [16] is a type of software that tries to block access to system/data by encrypting the data making it inaccessible for the user.

The aforementioned security threats should be considered in the deployment and management of distributed applications. These types of security threats can be reduced by considering certain mitigation strategies such as:

- Using data encryption algorithms to protect sensitive data from unauthorised access. Advanced Encryption Standard (AES)³⁵ and End-to-End encryption [17] is widely used to encrypt data from sender to receiver.
- Implementation of access control and identity management to ensure only authorised users can access sensitive information. Standardised approaches to support the user identification and authorisation include OpenID Connect [18], OAuth 2.0 [19] that are realised to verify clients access to the resources.

Data protection [20] is one of the key objectives for the security of cloud technology, it focuses on confidentiality, integrity, and availability (CIA) triad. For addressing the security and privacy related concerns, Cyber Security Framework (CSF) is a collection of security principles, standards, regulations, directives, and risk management process that can be used to protect the users and their assets³⁶. Moreover, innovative threat modelling techniques are needed to identify and mitigate security vulnerabilities. There are solutions available that are able to perform threat modelling and analysis. Many of the advanced ones are also able to estimate and analyse the likelihood and impact of each threat to help determine the possible solution or mitigation action based on the specific risk level. There are various risk treatment techniques to identify potential security threats to the distributed applications in the CCC environment. Following is a list of well-known solutions in the literature:

1. Threat modelling: Threat modelling tools identify vulnerabilities in the system. Below is a list of common methodologies:
 - a. Security Threat Oriented Requirements Engineering (STORE) [21] methodology which embeds security requirements in the software development process based on a threat catalogue which contains previously identified threats.
 - b. Spoofing, Tampering, Repudiation, Information Disclosure, Denial of Service, and Elevation of privilege (STRIDE) [22] for identification of threats.
 - c. Damage potential, Reproducibility, Exploitability, Affected users, and Discoverability (DREAD) [23] Threat Model which evaluates the security threats.
2. Risk Assessment Frameworks: There are various organisations that define Cyber Security Framework (CSF).
 - a. The non-governmental International Organisation of Standardisation (ISO)³⁷ created in 1947 promoted by International Telecommunication Union (ITU) and the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC). The most important ISO standard for Information Security Management System (ISMS) is ISO/IEC 27005 [24]. Based on ISO/IEC 27000, different security requirements are identified at the planning stage of a software, cybersecurity threats are assessed and then control strategies are developed to lower the risks. In order to ensure trustworthiness, ISMS performance

³⁵ Dworkin, Morris J., et al. "Advanced encryption standard (AES)." (2001).

<https://nvlpubs.nist.gov/nistpubs/FIPS/NIST.FIPS.197-upd1.pdf>

³⁶ ITU-T, "Series X: Data Networks, Open System Communications and Security, X.1205," ITU-T, 2008.

<https://www.itu.int/rec/T-REC-X>

³⁷ <https://www.iso.org/about>

should be analysed frequently on an ongoing basis to address foreseen risks and make improvements for any future risks.

- b. NIST SP 800-37³⁸: National Institute of Standards and Technology provides guidelines for managing and assessing security and privacy risks in cloud computing.

4.3.1.2 Regulatory compliance

The AI Act³⁹ is a proposed regulatory framework by the European Union aimed at managing the use and development of AI within its member states. The primary goal of the AI Act is to ensure that AI technologies are safe, trustworthy, and aligned with EU values and fundamental rights.

The key aspects of the AI Act are:

1. **Risk-Based Approach:** The AI Act categorises AI systems based on the level of risk they pose to users. These categories include:
 - a. **Unacceptable Risk:** AI systems that are considered a clear threat to safety, livelihoods, and rights are banned. Examples include social scoring by governments.
 - b. **High Risk:** These systems require strict regulations and oversight. They are subject to rigorous testing, documentation, and monitoring. Examples include AI in critical infrastructure, education, employment, and law enforcement.
 - c. **Limited Risk:** These systems have specific transparency obligations. Users must be informed that they are interacting with an AI system.
 - d. **Minimal Risk:** These AI systems are considered low-risk and can operate without additional requirements. This category includes applications like AI-enabled video games or spam filters.
2. **Compliance and Enforcement:** The AI Act establishes requirements for AI providers and users, including risk management systems, data governance, documentation and logging, transparency, human oversight, and robustness. It also proposes the creation of national supervisory authorities and a European AI Board to ensure compliance and enforcement.
3. **Innovation and Flexibility:** The Act aims to balance regulation with fostering innovation. It includes provisions to support regulatory sandboxes, where AI systems can be tested under controlled conditions before being deployed.
4. **Alignment with EU Values:** The AI Act emphasises the importance of protecting fundamental rights, including privacy, non-discrimination, and data protection. It seeks to ensure that AI systems respect human dignity and democratic values.

With the introduction of the AI Act, it is important for solution developers to ensure compliance with these acts to avoid potential legal problems and financial repercussions. The ambition of proposed component to automatically check the data planned to be used by the solutions to assess their adherence to the principles of the AI Act. The research focus is on developing an approach for automated regulatory compliance verification, designed for seamless integration into diverse technology stacks.

³⁸ <https://csrc.nist.gov/pubs/sp/800/37/r2/final>

³⁹ <https://artificialintelligenceact.eu/>

4.3.2 Market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards

4.3.2.1 Security Risk Modelling

Various market ready solutions have been developed to address cybersecurity threats. Following is a list of commercial solution for security threat modelling and analysis:

- **Microsoft Threat Modelling Tool (TMT)** [25] is a software developed by Microsoft for identifying security vulnerabilities in software applications. It is based on Spoofing, Tampering, Repudiation, Information Disclosure, Denial of Service, and Elevation of privilege (STRIDE) [26] method to systematically identify threats. Data flow diagrams (DFDs) are used to model the system and its behaviour based on STRIDE categories. Users can create a threat model, visualise attack patterns and control strategies are generated as reports for the implementation of security measures.
- **Threat Modeller** [27] Software, Inc. has developed a threat modelling platform which help organisations assess and mitigate cyber intrusion using a process flow diagram. It offers automated threat intelligence and attack path analysis and integration with security workflows.
- **Open Web Application Security Project (OWASP) threat dragon** [28] is an open-source software for threat modelling that is used to create threat models for the software applications.
- **IriusRisk** [29] is a commercial threat modelling tool developed by IriusRisk Ltd. which requires a paid subscription to use. It uses a variation of data flow diagrams.
- **Eclipse Papyrus for Real Time (Papyrus-RT)** [30] is an open-source software for creating architectural models for real time and embedded systems. It is not designed specifically for threat modelling but can be used to identify potential security vulnerabilities.
- **Lucidchart** [31] is a commercial cloud-based diagram tool used to create various diagrams to visualise system architecture and security vulnerabilities.
- **Systems Security Modeller (SSM)** [32] processes system models to perform risk analysis. A system model represents the structural and functional aspects of the applications and hardware involved for risk analysis. It includes various processing components and their interconnections. Physical objects (such as data, database, process, servers, etc.) are represented as nodes in the system model which are termed as assets. The interaction between these assets is known as connections.

SSM developed by University of Southampton is based on asset-approach to system security enabling automatic identification of potential security risks to all assets and also consider inter-connectivity between assets. Assets include both humans and technology. It also checks for GDPR⁴⁰ compliance and follows ISO 27005⁴¹ risk assessment procedure hence also supports ISO 27001. It also checks for threat patterns from OWASP Top 10 vulnerabilities [33].

⁴⁰ <https://gdpr-info.eu/>

⁴¹ ISO/IEC 27005 (2018). Information technology - Security techniques - Information security risk management

Risk assessment methods in literature primarily focus on the specific assets of the system (such as database or data storage) and do not consider the interconnectivity between these assets in a system known as context establishment. However, risk modelling solutions should also be able to analyse the risks arising from interconnectivity of the assets so that risk analysis of the overall system can be performed. SSM described above is one such solution in the literature which performs risk analysis for assets and their interactions.

4.3.2.2 Regulatory compliance

As of now, specific tools designed exclusively for AI Act compliance are not widely available, given that the AI Act is still in the proposal stage and has not been fully ENACTed. However, several existing AI compliance and governance tools can help organisations align with the anticipated requirements of the AI Act. These tools generally focus on transparency, fairness, bias detection, and robust documentation, which are key elements of the AI Act. Here are some tools that can be leveraged for this purpose.

EU AI Act Compliance Checker⁴² is developed by the team at the Future of Life Institute. The EU AI Act Compliance Checker is a tool or service designed to help organisations ensure that their AI systems comply with the European Union's AI Act. The tool consists of the set of questions related to AI Act, related to the organisation, like: *Which kind of entity is your organisation?; Is your system a General Purpose AI model?; Does your AI system (or the product for which your AI system is a 'safety component') fall within any of the following high-risk categories?; etc.*

Based on the answers the tool provides guidance through different aspects of compliance with AI Act (Risk Classification, Compliance Assessment, Documentation and Reporting, Monitoring and Auditing, Best practices, Mitigation strategies).

However the tool doesn't provide possibility to the search by the specific questions and topics and on the other hand, tool is built in a way that makes it difficult to support implementation on other sites, since there are no an API available.

The **AI Compliance tool**⁴³ will guide technical, business and risk, and compliance teams through the requirements of the AI Act and provide them with a single platform to cooperate and document the compliance of separate AI projects within an organisation.

Key features of the tool are:

- Organisation of many AI projects in one place and quick assessment of their risks;
- Following of straightforward step-by-step tasks to tackle complex legal requirements;
- Documentation of an organisation's compliance journey;
- Collection of supporting evidence in one place;
- Access to guidance for AI governance best practices to understand the ways to achieve the highest level of compliance;
- Utilisation of a tool which will be updated regularly.

⁴² <https://artificialintelligenceact.eu/assessment/eu-ai-act-compliance-checker/>

⁴³ <https://www.pwc.com/cz/en/sluzby/technologie-a-data/ai-act/ai-compliance-tool.html>

AI Act self-assessment tool⁴⁴ for business owners who use AI technology in their product and plan to distribute their product or already distribute their product in the EU. The scope of the tool is to answer is the technology used falls under the definition of the AI system. There is a definition inside the self-assessment tool that will help better understand if the AI Act applies in each case.

The self-assessment tool is split into four parts:

1. The first few questions focus on understanding whether the AI Act will *apply* to the organisation's AI system.
2. The second set of questions evaluates if the organisation's system can be considered *prohibited* under the AI Act.
3. If it's not likely to be prohibited, one can proceed to the questions evaluating if the system can be considered *high-risk*, and if not what other obligations might apply under the AI Act.
4. Finally, if the AI system is not deemed high risk or prohibited, the tool will assist in evaluating whether it poses *limited risk* under the AI Act and the corresponding obligations associated with it.

European AI Scanner⁴⁵ (RegTech tool for EU AI Act compliance) is EU AI Act compliance platform that identifies and assesses AI systems to assign a risk categorisation. It leverages tools, software, and data analytics to automate assessment processes, monitor regulatory changes, and manage risk. The tool focuses on streamlining and automating the assessment process to assign risk categories under the EU AI Act. It assists businesses in managing compliance requirements for both high-risk and non-high-risk AI systems. Key features of the European AI Scanner include a configurable Rules Engine and an Impact Assessment module, providing various options to ensure compliance with the EU AI Act. The tool supports alignment with internal policies and generates necessary documentation and reports for functions such as CSR, ethical charters, and boards.

In-depth EU AI Toolkit: AI Act Toolkit ⁴⁶ project is developing a step-by-step pro-justice compliance tool for developers of high-risk AI.

Complying with the AI Act can be challenging for providers of high-risk AI, as it demands extensive documentation, including a risk management system, data governance, and a declaration of conformity.

The Tool simplifies this critical task, streamlining the process of conducting mandatory internal controls and documentation while offering essential guidance on ethical and social considerations related to AI products. It reorganises the AI Act requirements into step-by-step instructions, guiding users through the workflow to ensure all necessary documentation is complete and compliant with regulatory guidelines. Users can download the completed documents for compliance or public disclosure and upload them to a dedicated section for citizens and prospective clients to view. This demonstrates their commitment to exceeding the legal minimum required by the Act.

This tool goes beyond legal compliance. It encourages product managers to critically consider how AI relates to structural inequality and engage with the ethos of the Act. It prompts AI practitioners

⁴⁴ <https://legalnodes.com/article/eu-ai-act-self-assessment>

⁴⁵ <https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-alliance/best-practices/european-ai-scanner-regtech-tool-eu-ai-act-compliance>

⁴⁶ <http://lcfi.ac.uk/projects/ai-innovation-praxis/eu-ai-act-toolkit/>

to consider both technical and sociotechnical responses to risk, recognising that systems can be harmful even without errors or biases. The tool advises consulting ethics experts from the product ideation stage and includes educational resources like short videos illustrating potential risks.

Privacy Pact⁴⁷ is a tool designed for companies to demonstrate their commitment to adhering to the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) rules and principles, regardless of their location. It includes the contractual obligations outlined in Article 28, which are required for all Data Processors. This tool is contractually binding and authenticated using Blockchain technology, making it a secure way to communicate the organisation's commitment on its website. While it is not a certification, it can be used to prepare for certification processes like Europrivacy⁴⁸.

Europrivacy, approved by the European Data Protection Board (EDPB) as the European Data Protection Seal, assesses and certifies compliance with GDPR and complementary national data protection regulations. It helps applicants identify and mitigate risks, demonstrate and validate their compliance, and enhance their reputation and market access. Europrivacy is the only GDPR certification officially recognised in all EU Member States.

4.3.3 Beyond State of the Art

4.3.3.1 Security Risk Modelling

Despite the recent advancements in risk analysis methods, these approaches do not consider the challenges faced by edge-cloud continuum in terms of auto-generation of system models to perform a thorough risk analysis. ENACT aims to provide beyond state-of-art by performing auto-discovery of assets that are spread over edge-to-cloud continuum and embedding this information in the Dynamic Federated Graph-based Modeller of Resources, Devices and Services (DFGM). Security Risk Modelling will be performed which is based on the open-source solution called Security Risk Modeller (SSM). SSM functionalities will be extended in the SRM to automatically generate system models based on the outcome of DFGM and perform risk analysis. This choice of the baseline solution is depended on the functionality expected from the threat modelling solution in the ENACT conceptual architecture, where assessment of cybersecurity risks associated with distributed systems is an important aspect.

SRM allows to develop a system model by connecting different assets and perform design-time risk analysis. SRM allows implementation of ISO 27005, Open Worldwide Application Security Project⁴⁹ (OWASP), and General Data Protection Regulation⁵⁰ (GDPR) principles at the backend to analyse risks. As ENACT UCs are processing personal data, there is also a need to consider GDPR compliance throughout the data processing pipeline in the edge-cloud continuum. Figure 3 depicts the internal workflow for SRM.

⁴⁷ <https://www.europrivacy.org/en/resource/privacy-pact>

⁴⁸ <https://www.europrivacy.com/>

⁴⁹ <https://owasp.org/>

⁵⁰ <https://gdpr-info.eu/>

Figure 3. Internal workflow of the Security Risk Modeller

The risk mitigation strategies generated by the SRM will enhance the overall security of ENACT platform and the distributed systems/application running in the cloud-edge continuum.

4.3.3.2 Regulatory compliance

In order to develop an **AI Act compliance checker** component that will automatically check the data planned to be used by the solutions to assess their adherence to the principles of the AI Act, we plan to use LLM (Large Language Models) like: GPT-4, Gemini Pro, Llama 31. We will follow developments in the field of LLM and regularly update the LLM used to avail of the latest capabilities. Integrating of any LLM with the AI Act's regulatory framework involves ensuring that the use of chosen LLM complies with the requirements and guidelines outlined in the AI Act, particularly around high-risk applications, transparency, trustworthy, fairness, and accountability. We will analyse LLMs performances (architecture, parameters, training data, key features, UCs) and choose the most suitable model for the component functionalities.

We want to automate checking compliance with the AI Act as much as possible, from assessing the type of the solution and to which risk group it belongs, to evaluating the documentation and whether it's sufficient as well as assessing the datasets used for training.

To comply with the AI Act, solution providers must prepare comprehensive documentation covering technical details, data usage, testing, transparency, regulatory compliance, and ethical considerations. Required technical documentation could be found in Annex IV ⁵¹ :

- A general description of the AI system,

⁵¹ <https://artificialintelligenceact.eu/annex/4/>

- A detailed description of the elements of the AI system and of the process for its development, Detailed information about the monitoring, functioning and control of the AI system,
- A description of the appropriateness of the performance metrics for the specific AI system;
- A detailed description of the risk management system,
- A description of relevant changes made by the provider to the system through its lifecycle;
- A list of the harmonised standards applied in full or in part the references of which have been published in the Official Journal of the European Union,
- A copy of the EU declaration of conformity,
- A detailed description of the system in place to evaluate the AI system performance in the post-market phase

Our goal is to automatically process as many of those documents as possible in terms of used data (to explain what kind of data he used for training, how he did testing, accuracy, etc.).

4.4 Zero-touch provisioning services

In the contemporary landscape of network management, the escalation of business expansion and the diversification of geographic presence necessitate an advanced approach to network deployment. Traditional methods, which involve manual configuration and extensive human involvement, are not only labour-intensive but also prone to errors and security vulnerabilities. These challenges underscore the need for an innovative solution that can streamline the deployment process while enhancing operational efficiency and security.

Zero-Touch Provisioning (ZTP) emerges as a pivotal technology in this context. ZTP revolutionises network deployment by automating the entire provisioning process, thereby minimising manual intervention and significantly reducing the potential for human errors. This state-of-the-art approach enables businesses to deploy networks rapidly across multiple locations without the traditional burdens of manual setups. It not only expedites the deployment process but also ensures increased security by eliminating the need to ship pre-configured devices that could potentially be compromised.

The operational benefits of ZTP include a substantial reduction in deployment time and costs, heightened security protocols, and enhanced scalability. This makes ZTP an indispensable tool for businesses looking to efficiently scale their network infrastructure in alignment with their growth and the dynamic demands of the market.

4.4.1 Research directions and related work

This research paper: "Time-to-Provision Evaluation of IoT Devices Using Automated Zero-Touch Provisioning" [34] by Ivan Boškov and colleagues, presents a state-of-the-art evaluation of ZTP for IoT devices, highlighting its necessity for efficient network management in large-scale deployments. The paper details two innovative ZTP approaches: one utilising software-enabled access points (Soft-AP) and another based on Bluetooth technology, both designed to automate and streamline the provisioning process without human intervention. These methods aim to tackle the challenges

associated with the manual setup of heterogeneous IoT devices by significantly reducing provisioning time and potential human errors.

The study extensively tests these solutions on a specific testbed, demonstrating that automated ZTP not only outperforms manual provisioning methods in terms of time-to-provision (TTP) but also enhances the overall reliability of network setup processes. This work contributes to the IoT deployment field by providing scalable, efficient, and vendor-independent provisioning solutions that can adapt to the evolving requirements of modern networks, underscoring the potential of ZTP to facilitate the broader adoption and expansion of IoT technologies.

The article "Intent-based zero-touch service chaining layer for software-defined edge cloud networks" [35] explores the innovative integration of Edge Computing, Software Defined Networking (SDN), and Network Function Virtualisation (NFV). This integration facilitates the dynamic and elastic deployment of services as virtualised functions across distributed clouds extended to the network edge, a concept referred to as dynamic service chains.

The paper introduces an intent-based zero-touch service chaining layer that enhances the programmability of service chain paths in edge cloud networks. This layer autonomously adapts service chain paths in response to network conditions like sudden congestion, utilising intent-based directives that simplify network management and reduce the necessity for manual configuration. The experiments conducted in an emulated network environment validate the feasibility of this approach and measure its impact on network resource usage and adaptation overhead.

The backdrop of this study is the rapid evolution of mobile networks, the Internet of Things (IoT), and various smart devices which are creating new application demands in sectors such as telemedicine and industrial automation. These applications benefit from Edge Computing, which provides necessary computing resources closer to the data source, enhancing responsiveness and interactive behaviour.

Traditional provisioning methods for IoT devices, reliant on manual configurations and updates, pose significant security risks and inefficiencies. The integration of embedded SIMs (eSIMs) presented in paper [36] emerges as a robust solution, enhancing secure and flexible identity management in IoT devices. This study introduces a low-cost, zero-touch provisioning system utilising the GSMA Over-The-Air (OTA) IoT-SAFE protocol, facilitating eSIM-based remote provisioning. The system leverages blockchain technology for immutable data storage and verification through Ethereum smart contracts, ensuring enhanced security and integrity across IoT deployments. Through comprehensive simulations and security analysis, the proposed system - dubbed SleSIM- demonstrates superior efficiency and resilience compared to traditional provisioning methods, significantly reducing Time-To-Provision (TTP) and enhancing scalability and security against diverse attack vectors in AIoT environments. This research underscores the potential of eSIM and blockchain in revolutionising IoT device management, paving the way for more secure, efficient, and autonomous IoT ecosystems.

4.4.2 Market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards

ZTP solutions are prevalent in industries where quick and reliable network deployment is essential, such as telecommunications, data centres, and enterprise networks.

- Cisco's DNA Center⁵² offers a centralised network control and management dashboard that facilitates ZTP for switches, routers, and wireless controllers. It automates the process of device configuration and management, making network deployments faster and reducing manual errors.
- Ubiquiti's UniFi platform supports ZTP for scalable network device deployment, particularly useful in managing and expanding enterprise networks with minimal IT assistance.
- Dell's OpenManage Network Manager⁵³ facilitates easy deployment of network configurations and firmware updates, offering ZTP features that help automate and streamline network setup and management.
- Cumulus Linux, an open network operating system, provides ZTP functionalities that help automate the deployment of network devices from a bare metal state.

4.4.3 Beyond State of the Art

ZTP is highly applicable in dynamic and scalable environments like cloud data centres, large corporate networks, and rapidly expanding IoT ecosystems. It facilitates quick and reliable network expansion and upgrades, supports consistent policy enforcement across the network, and enhances security by reducing the attack vectors associated with manual configurations.

As ZTP evolves, it is likely to tackle the increasing complexity and security needs of modern networks with several key developments:

- ZTP will increasingly incorporate AI to optimise configurations and predict network needs, allowing for real-time adjustments and proactive issue management. ZTP will read these optimised configurations from the Orchestrator who at its turn will be notified by other CCC components.
- The configurations lists will be managed by the ZTP who will actively communicate any update appeared in the network to the Orchestrator
- As edge computing expands, ZTP will adapt to manage a wide array of edge devices, ensuring seamless integration and security across distributed architectures.
- ZTP will also handle the K8 clusters configurations using Ansible playbooks. This can be done with MAAS and Juju⁵⁴ open-source component.

While ZTP provides substantial benefits, it also poses challenges such as the need for comprehensive pre-deployment planning and the risk of security vulnerabilities in the automation scripts themselves. Future advancements in ZTP are likely to focus on integrating artificial intelligence to predict and adapt to network changes dynamically and enhancing security measures to safeguard against automated attacks.

⁵² <https://www.cisco.com/c/en/us/products/collateral/cloud-systems-management/dna-center/nb-06-dna-center-data-sheet-cte-en.html>

⁵³ <https://www.dell.com/support/home/de-at/product-support/product/dell-openmanage-network-manager/overview>

⁵⁴ <https://juju.is/>

4.5 Edge-cloud orchestration

4.5.1 Research directions and related work

The major research challenges regarding orchestration in cloud-to-edge continuums are resource visibility [37] dynamic resource allocation [38] (e.g. due to resource uncertainty, energy constraints and dynamic dependencies), dynamic management of application elasticity, and dynamic workload scheduling and resource heterogeneity at the edge [39].

Typically, orchestration was rather focused on cloud settings, while a more recent trend involves edge-oriented solutions. However, the latter, more often than not, employ communication middlewares to facilitate cloud-to-edge interconnection and control using master-worker nodes. One such prevalent solution is FLEDGE [40], a low-resource container orchestrator that is capable of directly connecting to Kubernetes clusters via virtual communication channels and has been proven to be a viable alternative to lightweight K8S approaches such as K3S (further discussed in the next section).

Nonetheless, with the advent of distributed, micro-service based applications that span across the computing continuum, new challenges have been introduced for orchestration. To cope with such challenges specialised orchestration solutions that fully leverage the capabilities of both the cloud and edge resources, while meeting the respective requirements, are necessitated. In this context, several research efforts have been made to investigate orchestration approaches tailored to the Cloud-to-Edge characteristics. For instance, the work in [41] introduces the concept of end-to-end slices. This concept supports the unified management of compute, storage and network resources by creating on-demand, software-enabled and per-tenant resource partitions across the cloud-to-edge continuum. Each slice is built as a fully-isolated set of such resources, allocated on-demand and exposed to a tenant as a single manageable object through proper abstractions, with the guarantee that the service performance will be independent of the status of the services running on other slices. Nevertheless, this approach pertains to resource orchestration to satisfy tenants' needs in multi-tenant environments but does not consider the dynamic scheduling of applications and their components to meet their requirements.

On the contrary, works such as ENORM [42], [43], [44] focus on the application orchestration and dynamic placement within the continuum spectrum, each one with its distinct pros and cons. Indicatively, ENORM enables offloading of computation tasks from cloud to edge and dynamic autoscaling of edge resources but does not support application migration among resources, while the second work presents a modular architecture wherein applications are treated as containerised micro-services, offloaded to edge resources and running in an isolated and scalable manner. Finally, the third solution extends the ETSI NFV MANO standard to achieve improved bandwidth utilisation and delivery time in smart city applications. However, none of them not consider dynamic application demands or infrastructure changes, lacking real-time re-configurations. Many research projects have also addressed the problem of orchestration in the cloud-to-edge continuum, resulting in relevant systems. A lot of them, including DECENTER [45], Capillary [46], SODALITE@RT [47] and PrEstoCloud [48], rely on the TOSCA (Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications) specification to ensure deployment portability. However, their dependence on TOSCA renders them inevitably centralised, while since TOSCA does not provide support for edge deployments, such solutions rely on custom extensions to cater for edge requirements, thus their portability is at stake. Recently some blockchain-based solutions, such as

mF2C [49], RAINBOW⁵⁵ [50] that depart from the traditional centralised management model have emerged. Still, they either do not consider important aspects such as scalability, dynamic application management [53] or infrastructure changes [55], or are focused particularly on the Edge rather than the entire continuum [54]. A thorough overview of the existing Cloud-to-Edge orchestration systems can be found in [51].

However, the current solutions struggle to manage the dynamism (at application and infrastructure) at edge and fog computing environments, as they are primarily inspired by the reliability inherent in the cloud environments. In this direction, MiCADO [52] recently introduced an orchestrator towards cloud-to-edge continuum however it is focused more on the delivery of an operational solution and not on the improvement of the orchestrator's intelligence in dealing with complex and dynamic orchestration needs of applications.

Distributed orchestration approaches to guarantee QoS across Cloud-Edge continuum based on Kubernetes have been introduced [53]. SmartORC [54] also uses a kind of optimisation algorithms and matchmaking related to QoS to support orchestration. Recently, knowledge [55] introduces a cloud-edge continuum that orchestrates AI models execution but it is completely focused on this. Oakestra proposes a hierarchical orchestration framework specifically designed to support service operation over edge infrastructures that incorporates novel features such as federated cluster management, delegated task scheduling, and semantic overlay networking, but the framework is designed to operate under the assumption that network conditions are relatively stable and reliable, while it also inherently sacrifices global optimality for local decision-making efficiency [56].

To deal with resource heterogeneity at the edge, EVE-OS, a universal, open Linux-based operating system for distributed edge computing that provides a flexible foundation for distributed edge deployments with choice of any hardware, application and cloud has been proposed. However deploying an OS on some edge devices is still challenging due to hardware computing limitations [57]. In this regard, BalenaOS, a host operating system based on Yocto Linux which provides a small memory footprint, with the purpose of running Docker containers on embedded devices has been proposed, yet it currently supports only up to 20 different device types [58].

In terms of scheduling, Kubernetes offers his standard scheduler, capable of managing multiple applications, however, as we will see in the papers mentioned next, it comes with its limitations.

In this work [59], the author attempts to improve the Horizontal Pod Autoscaler (HPA) that comes with Kubernetes, creating an HPA+ based on prediction models. He mentions that the default scaler is static and doesn't offer much choice for cases where the applications require a more dynamic approach.

Due to the lack of specific features, this author [60] creates an alternative method to the standard scheduler. He says that the default scheduler of Kubernetes, only has as queue-based scheduler, can only dispatch one at a time, and the pod scheduling time is globally optimal. The author then addresses the increasing need of a better scheduling automation solution, due to increased complexity levels and real-time requirements of large-scale cloud computing systems. The proposed solution is a deep learning and reinforcement learning algorithm, each one charged with a different task. Deep learning for monitoring and prediction, and then combined with the

⁵⁵ RAINBOW_D1,2-RAINBOW-Reference-Architecture, https://rainbow-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/RAINBOW_D1.2-RAINBOW-Reference-Architecture.pdf

reinforcement learning, the task scheduling is altered based on the real-time system state and task characteristics, achieving optimal resource utilisation and maximum efficiency for the task at hand.

The author in [61] wanted to create a custom scheduler due to the Kubernetes limitations regarding the default scheduler. Newer applications required different needs, and so he decided to make a solution that was able to fulfil the requirements of these applications, respecting factors like storage metrics, CPU and RAM metrics, or other resources. In order to do this, he looked at components like etcd⁵⁶, that is utilised to record the current status of the system making state observation available for all, the Scheduler itself, which will be responsible for allocating a time slot for every pod residing in a certain node, the API server in charge of accepting instructions and altering the information for the Kubernetes components, Kubelet⁵⁷ manages the communication between nodes, namespaces allows for same pods with same namespace to interact with each other, and as a monitoring module he uses Prometheus and Kubernetes dashboard to check on pod and node data.

Some pods might require a different approach due to security concerns. Delicate data needs to be handled differently, and that's when network policies come in. Kubernetes already has a plugin⁵⁸ dedicated to this matter, so it's possible to manage the pod affected by these policies, like controlling who communicates with it. The two known states of isolation for these kinds of pods will be "isolation for egress" or "isolation for ingress", meaning that the only connections available from the pod come from an egress list, in case of "isolation for egress", while "isolation for ingress" allows connections into the pod from the pod's node and ingress list, and the default pod configuration is "non-isolated for egress" and "non-isolated for ingress", allowing all types of connections. A pod with the policy "isolated for egress" has a list with the allowed traffic routes from the pod, while the "isolated for ingress" allows traffic for the pod.

4.5.2 Market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards

In recent years, several cloud orchestration solutions have become available, such as Kubernetes, Cloudify⁵⁹ and Docker Swarm⁶⁰. Major cloud providers also offer tools for orchestration, such as Amazon Web Services (AWS) CloudFormation⁶¹ and Google's Deployment Manager⁶². Overall, orchestration solutions are rather focused on cloud-based deployments and, cover only to a lesser extent, emerging Edge-to-Cloud scenarios.

Kubernetes is one of the most recommended tools for container orchestration and broadly used by the industry. Its API is responsible for listening to the other parts of the system and communicating with the orchestration process, so they could manage the applications considering factors like resource allocation, priority orders, container availability and health, and other criteria.

⁵⁶ <https://kubernetes.io/docs/tasks/administer-cluster/configure-upgrade-etcd/>

⁵⁷ <https://kubernetes.io/docs/reference/command-line-tools-reference/kubelet/>

⁵⁸ <https://kubernetes.io/docs/concepts/services-networking/network-policies/>

⁵⁹ <https://docs.cloudify.co/>

⁶⁰ <https://docs.docker.com/engine/swarm/>

⁶¹ <https://aws.amazon.com/cloudformation/>

⁶² <https://cloud.google.com/deployment-manager/docs>

Several lightweight Kubernetes derivatives have been developed (e.g., K3s⁶³, K0s⁶⁴, MicroK8s⁶⁵) to handle the particular requirements of the Edge. There are also platforms designed for the Edge, such as KubeOne⁶⁶, EdgeX Foundry⁶⁷, and Open Horizon⁶⁸ that extend the orchestration logic to the Edge aiming to provide unified management. One notable open-source initiative to handle the connections and orchestration of edge resources is KubeEdge [62]. KubeEdge consists of a cloud part and an edge part, with the cloud part interfacing with the cloud Kubernetes API for edge node management. The edge part is deployed on each device to manage pods. KubeEdge supports bidirectional communication between the edge and the cloud parts to ensure metadata synchronisation, syncing cloud-side resource updates to the edge, and reporting edge-side host and device status changes to the cloud. It also supports MQTT which enables edge devices to access through edge nodes.

Kubernetes supports the customisation of schedulers to better adapt the assignment of application pods to the intended objectives and requirements. Multiple custom schedulers⁶⁹ are currently available, but they all have specific objectives, and they don't offer an option to be fed custom AI model decisions. There are also some Scheduler Plugins⁷⁰ that can be looked further, but a custom scheduler would allow us to create a more appropriate approach to the problem.

This custom scheduler, tailored to specific needs, could receive details about the application requirements, like the type of node demands, either be a high availability node or a standard one, useful for high-availability applications. Following these instructions, the scheduler would search among the available nodes for the best candidate.

For monitoring purposes, Kubernetes⁷¹ already establishes that it works with OpenMetrics⁷², also part of the CNCF⁷³, that extends the Prometheus exposition format. This guarantees a reliable service since we can check how the applications behave when deployed, delivering performance data, resource utilisation metrics, and other useful information to pass on.

4.5.3 Beyond State of the Art

Despite recent advancements in orchestration systems, most approaches do not adequately address the challenges posed by the Edge-Cloud continuum paradigm in terms of dynamic resource discovery and scheduling, scalability, elasticity, heterogeneity, etc. ENACT aims to advance beyond state-of-the-art by providing an AI-powered orchestration engine to explicitly cover novel Edge-Cloud applications and UCs. ENACT is expected to add value to existing solutions (e.g. KubeEdge) by extending them to achieve enhanced, AI-based orchestration decisions across the

⁶³ <https://k3s.io/>

⁶⁴ <https://k0sproject.io/>

⁶⁵ <https://microk8s.io/>

⁶⁶ <https://www.kubermatic.com/products/kubermatic-kubeone/edge/>

⁶⁷ <https://www.edgexfoundry.org/>

⁶⁸ <https://www.lfedge.org/projects/openhorizon/>

⁶⁹ <https://kubernetes.io/docs/tasks/extend-kubernetes/configure-multiple-schedulers/>

⁷⁰ DavidW. (2024, March 8). 11 Kubernetes Custom Schedulers You Should Use. <https://overcast.blog/11-awesome-kubernetes-custom-schedulers-you-should-use-a29e86c82838>

⁷¹ <https://kubernetes.io/docs/tasks/debug/debug-cluster/resource-usage-monitoring/>

⁷² <https://openmetrics.io/>

⁷³ <https://www.cncf.io/>

entire Edge-Cloud spectrum. Task allocation will be performed dynamically aiming to distribute workload across computing nodes considering computational capacity, data properties, available infrastructure and network status.

The communication between Kubernetes API and the other parts of the ENACT architecture is an important step in the orchestration process. The required solution needs to be able to bridge these components to allow the handling of information in real-time, leading to better orchestration decisions.

The customisation of Kubernetes schedulers is extended, to consider the decisions made by the AI Models and execute the deployment solution, that was requested by the DRL component, in the AI layer, that should have updated schedules provided by the AI Forecaster and the GNN, and as a result, the optimisation of resource utilisation and getting the targeted runtime efficiency. It may also be important to use/develop technology capable of interpreting the decisions made by this layer, to be able to translate it to formats that the technology, used for the orchestration tool, can understand.

4.6 AI Algorithms and training environments

Based on recent research outcomes, the orchestration intelligence can be based on approaches such as search-based algorithms, mathematical programming algorithms and game-theoretical or deep learning algorithms. E.g., AI4DL [63] shows how to manage resources by analysing deep learning workloads. Similarly, Theta-Scan leverages behaviour analysis to auto-scale containers in the cloud. RL has also been introduced [64] as a method for cloud-edge-fog orchestration and scheduling.

4.6.1 Research directions and related work

4.6.1.1 AI algorithms for prediction and scheduling

Forecasting the resource demand and provide the optimal allocations are open problems in which multi-factors should be considered. For the resource demand forecasting, factors such as low resource utilisation, unbalanced load and security issues play an important role. Such forecasting is typically based on time series analysis or regression methods to predict request arrival rates and resource usage patterns [65]. Most existing AI-based or ML-based forecasting mechanisms use algorithms including long short-term memory (LSTM) [66] [67] or bidirectional LSTM (Bi-LSTM) [68] to achieve improved accuracy in resource demand predictions, while other approaches such as artificial neural networks (ANNs) [69] or regression algorithms (e.g. support vector regression (SVR)) have been widely used [70] for predicting the application performance. However, such forecasting models have been explored mainly in the context of cloud environments and are usually focused on optimising either workload distribution or application performance [66].

In addition, the provision of the optimal allocation should be also considered as multi-factor problem, trying to optimise the allocation between the network delay, energy consumption, deadline of the application, the processing cost and the number of tasks that have to be executed [71].

A considerable amount of works are using heuristic approaches to schedule the resource demand and allocation. Pasiadis et al. in [72] used a genetic algorithm along with a MILP algorithm to

optimally schedule the resource allocation in an SDN environment. In their solution they are optimising the scheduling based in the network QoS, jitter, delay and bandwidth. Another heuristic solution is presented in [73] where they are trying to provide the optimal scheduling based on minimising the transmission time. However, the resource needs in delay are not taken into consideration along with the deadlines of the applications.

In recent years, the literature suggests that instead of using heuristic algorithms (genetic algorithms, Mixed Integer Linear Programming) one should target for Deep Learning techniques and especially Deep Reinforcement Learning, due to its ability to recognise complex patterns, handle high-dimensional data, continuously improve in new domain data, and enable dynamic allocation of resources based on the current system state, offering personalised and optimised solutions to complex scheduling problems in CCC environments [74]. Deep Reinforcement Learning is found to be applied in several academic papers [75] [76]. However, in their solution they do not take into consideration the duration demand of the applications which request resources and they do not consider any security issues.

4.6.1.2 Graph Neural Networks

The computing continuum refers to the bridge that connects the vast expanse of Internet of Things (IoT) devices, also known as the edge, to the robust infrastructure of high-performance cloud services. With all the amount of data that it is being gathered, transmitted and processed nowadays, arises a pressing need for innovative solutions to keep this data flow viable.

Due to this increase in the amount of data being worked with, new approaches to this problem have had to be considered, such as increasing the data processing capacity in IoT devices to reduce the huge amount of computational work on the high-performance cloud part, so a much lower latency can be achieved, or to avoid an overload in the network that prevents the correct processing of this same data in the cloud.

Using Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) to optimise the functionality of the computing continuum represents a cutting-edge application of AI in enhancing distributed computing environments. GNNs are employed to optimise resource allocation and task offloading across the computing continuum by modelling the heterogeneous computing resources and their interconnections as a graph. Also, they assist in dynamically balancing the load across edge, fog, and cloud computing nodes based on real-time workload and resource availability. By continuously analysing the graph representing the computing continuum, GNNs adaptively adjust resource allocations to prevent bottlenecks and ensure efficient utilisation of computational resources.

As the GNNs are working with real-time data from edge devices, sensors and cloud servers, they can adopt a predictive behaviour by learning complex patterns and correlations in the data graph so they can predict future resource demands and system behaviour, optimising the performance and stability of the computing continuum. Also, the use of GNNs enables intelligent decision-making and inference at the edge devices by deploying lightweight models for real-time data analysis and processing. With this practice, GNNs can decide to leave this computational task to the edge devices achieving reduced latency and bandwidth usage, leading to faster response times and improved privacy.

In terms of how GNNs work, the core of many of their architectures is message passing. Nodes in the graph exchange information with their neighbours iteratively, updating their own

representations based on the aggregated information. This mechanism allows GNNs to capture complex relational dependencies in these graph-structured datasets.

The acronym GNN encompasses a range of algorithms rather than a singular design. Over time, numerous architectures have emerged within this domain. Figure 4 stemming from [77] shows a visual representation showcasing crucial works in the field.

Figure 4: Graph Neural Networks: A Review of Methods and Applications

Below, some of the most notable architectures are reviewed:

- Graph Convolutional Networks (GCNs): GCNs are one of the earliest and most popular types of GNNs. They extend the concept of convolutional layers from regular grids (e.g., images) to irregular structures like graphs. GCNs have been successfully applied in various domains, but they have limitations in capturing long-range dependencies and handling graphs with different sizes.
- Graph Attention Networks (GATs): GATs improve upon GCNs by introducing attention mechanisms, allowing nodes to selectively aggregate information from their neighbours based on learned attention coefficients. This enables them to capture more fine-grained relationships in the graph, leading to improved performance in tasks such as node classification and link prediction.
- Graph Sample and Aggregation (GraphSAGE): GraphSAGE is another popular GNN architecture that samples and aggregates information from a node's local neighbourhood. It addresses scalability issues by operating on large graphs through sampling techniques while maintaining expressive power by aggregating information from different neighbourhood layers.

- **Graph Isomorphism Network (GIN):** GINs are powerful GNN models that can learn permutation-invariant node representations. Unlike GCNs, GINs use MLPs (Multi-Layer Perceptrons) to aggregate information from neighbouring nodes, making them more expressive and capable of capturing global graph structures.

Overall, GNNs have been integrated into reinforcement learning frameworks for tasks involving graph-structured data, such as social network analysis, recommendation systems, and traffic prediction. GNNs can effectively model the interactions between entities in the graph, enabling more effective decision-making in these domains. Despite their success, scalability remains a challenge for GNNs, especially when dealing with large-scale graphs. Research efforts are ongoing to develop scalable architectures and training algorithms that can handle massive graphs efficiently.

4.6.1.3 Virtual Training Environments

In the field of distributed and federated deployment systems, AI, is playing an ever-increasing role in supporting more accurate and reliable predictions of optimal deployment configurations for dynamic and distributed applications. However, the reliability, accuracy and efficacy of AI models is heavily dependent on both the quality of the training data, and the algorithms robustness. In order to ensure the accuracy and reliability of AI models are continually improved, regular training, retraining and recalibration are often required. The use of a Virtual Training Environment (VTE) provides a solution to address the needs of AI models through the provision of a simulated environment that facilitates the training, retraining, and recalibration of AI models through an efficient and controlled approach.

Through the use of virtualisation technologies for the creation of simulated environments, AI models are enabled to interact with synthetic and real-world data. The utilisation of a Virtual Training Environment can allow AI model developers to conduct training, retraining, and recalibration processes on their model, and without the need for extensive infrastructure.

Within the field of VTE's for AI training, there are many recent advancements which further boost the advantages of the VTE in comparison to other typical approaches for AI model training, which may rely on the purchase of additional hardware and software resources to provision required computing capacity. Innovations in the area of VTE have focused on strengthening various aspects related to AI models training such as scalability, cost effectiveness, iterative improvements and accessibility.

In regard to scalability, there are a number of new development areas, for example:

- **Parallel and Distributed Processing** – the VTE can enable the partitioning of an AI or GNN model across multiple nodes or clusters by enabling accelerated parallel training (Model Parallelism), and can also enable the distribution of model training data across multiple nodes (Data Parallelism).
- **Container and Orchestration Technologies** – Through the use of technologies in this field such as Docker or Kubernetes, streamlined deployment, replication, and management of components across distributed environment can be enabled.
- **Autoscaling and Resource Management** – Through the use of ZTP, the VTE can dynamically adjust dynamically the allocated resources of different components of AI models such to help with workload distribution, performance, demand, and cost.

Increased capabilities in terms of scalability allow a greater level of iterative improvement within AI model training with optimisation of this process over distributed and dynamic resources.

In addition, VTE's provide an advantage over previous approaches due their effect on considerations such as cost effectiveness, accessibility, and safety and control. Removing the need for high powered, or extensive physical infrastructure at the development level provides a number of other advantages with the first of which being increased accessibility.

Removing the need for extensive local infrastructure also plays a role in increasing accessibility to AI and AI training, to developers and the wider public with the tool being accessible regardless of local resources or physical location. This effect is also seen in terms of cost effectiveness, with AI developers now able to use the virtual training environments, in which access may be provided under various pricing models, however the large upfront costs associated with AI capable hardware is negated. The final advantage found under this approach is the increase safety and control that can be provided. Through the provision of the virtual training environments, AI developers are afforded a safe and controlled environment for testing and training their AI models, and without the risk of errors or accidents associated with real-world experimentation.

4.6.2 Market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards

4.6.2.1 AI algorithms for prediction and scheduling

To the best of our knowledge, there are not any technologies able to achieve a TRL (8-9) and be ready for Market that adopt AI for prediction and scheduling in CCC.

4.6.2.2 Graph Neural Networks

In the rapidly evolving landscape of AI, Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) have emerged as powerful tools for modelling and analysing complex relational data. As the demand for GNN-based applications continues to grow, the need for robust and accessible tools has become increasingly crucial. The tools presented in this section offer a unique set of functionalities tailored to support the development and deployment of GNN-based models, providing a diverse ecosystem for exploring graph-based ML techniques.

- **PyTorch Geometric**⁷⁴ offers a comprehensive suite of pre-built GNN layers and utilities tailored specifically for graph-based deep learning tasks. Its seamless integration with PyTorch facilitates flexible model definition and easy debugging. Additionally, it supports efficient batching and parallelisation for training large-scale GNN models and includes datasets and data loaders for common graph-based tasks, simplifying the data preprocessing pipeline. However, due to its rich feature set and flexibility, PyTorch Geometric presents a steeper learning curve compared to simpler frameworks. Furthermore, it provides limited support for the Windows operating system compared to other platforms.
- **Deep Graph Library (DGL)**⁷⁵ provides a high-level API for constructing and training GNN models, making it suitable for both beginners and advanced users. It offers support for

⁷⁴ <https://pytorch-geometric.readthedocs.io/>

⁷⁵ <https://www.dgl.ai/>

multiple frameworks, including TensorFlow⁷⁶, PyTorch⁷⁷, and MXNet⁷⁸, and enables dynamic graph construction and manipulation for dynamic graph learning scenarios. Extensive documentation and tutorials for various GNN tasks are available. However, DGL has limited support for advanced features compared to more specialised libraries like PyTorch Geometric and slightly lower performance for certain operations.

- **StellarGraph**⁷⁹ is a specialised library designed for scalable graph ML tasks, particularly suited for large-scale graphs. It provides implementations of state-of-the-art GNN models optimised for efficiency and scalability, supporting heterogeneous graphs and various graph-based learning tasks such as node classification, link prediction, and graph classification. While seamlessly integrating with popular deep learning frameworks like TensorFlow and Keras, StellarGraph offers limited support for PyTorch compared to other libraries. Some advanced features may require familiarity with the underlying graph processing engines for optimal performance.
- **Graph Nets**⁸⁰, developed by DeepMind, offers a flexible framework for building graph-based neural networks supporting both static and dynamic graph scenarios. It provides implementations of various GNN components in the form of demos, illustrating how to create, manipulate, and train graph networks. Despite its flexibility, beginners may encounter a steep learning curve. Graph Nets requires TensorFlow 1⁸¹, which might make it feel outdated for some users.
- **NetworkX**⁸² is a Python library that offers a wide range of algorithms and utilities for graph analysis and visualisation. Primarily focused on the creation and manipulation of small to medium-sized graphs, NetworkX is suitable for prototyping graph-based algorithms and exploring graph structures. However, it has limited support for deep learning-based approaches compared to specialised GNN libraries.

4.6.2.3 Virtual Training Environments

- **Dataiku**⁸³ is an AI and Analytics platform that allows users to extract insights from their data. It is provided in the form of a unified environment designed for use by a range of users levels from data scientists to business users, and allows for collaborative development. The platform provides features such as ML, model deployment, visual workflows and MLOps. In addition, the platforms provides visualisation capabilities that enable users to capture key insights in charts and interactive dashboards. The Dataiku solution is available through free and Paid editions with different feature sets available, and it can be used in the desktop, cloud or on-premise environments.

⁷⁶ <https://www.tensorflow.org/>

⁷⁷ <https://pytorch.org/>

⁷⁸ <https://mxnet.apache.org>

⁷⁹ <https://stellargraph.readthedocs.io/>

⁸⁰ https://github.com/google-deepmind/graph_nets

⁸¹ https://www.tensorflow.org/versions#tensorflow_1

⁸² <https://networkx.org/>

⁸³ <https://www.dataiku.com/>

- **DataRobot AI Platform**⁸⁴ provides an environment for both generative and predictive AI where users can create, deploy and manage AI models. The platform provides a range of features that are designed to cater to different user level. Key feature provided include visual workflows, training and tuning of models, model deployment and monitoring, and access control. In addition, the DataRobot provides capabilities design to ensure accurate documentation and regulatory compliance. The DataRobot AI Platform is only available as a paid on-premise or cloud-based service.
- **Alteryx Designer**⁸⁵ is a tool that enables users to access and manipulate data sources through both visual work flows and code based SDK, and extract insights through embedded AI capabilities. The tool provides an ecosystem of data connectors to access data from a wide range of sources and provides reporting and visualisation features. Features are also provided that cater to both technical and non-technical users. Like the previous one, the Alteryx Designer is available only as a paid solution.
- **H2O.ai**⁸⁶ is an open-source ML platform that is designed for scalability and efficiency. The platform is more focused towards the technical user with the ability to provide custom ai applications for business users. The platforms supports a range of ML algorithms, model creation, deployment and monitoring, and support increased transparency through model interpretability. H2O.ai resources are available as open-source solutions.

When selecting a tool or platform to provide capabilities in AI training, retraining, and recalibration, there are several core considerations that need to be taken into account depending on the intended usage. One such consideration is the usability of the platform, in terms of the intended user base of the. Some platforms such as the Alteryx Designer or the DataRobot platform provider a greater focus on addressing the needs of business users and ensure all operations can be performed through more intuitive visual workflows, whereas tools such as H2o.ai provide a greater focus on supporting tech users such as data scientists or programmers. Another key consideration is the licensing and pricing options available for each solution. A key advantage of H2O.ai in relation to the ENACT project is that it is open-source in nature and, as such, is available for reuse or extension. Although in the other alternatives mentioned that are proprietary, there are free versions available as is the case with Dataiku, these often come with a limited set of features or usage restrictions. It is also important to consider both the scalability and flexibility of each AI training platform, with reflection on support for a range of algorithms and specifically in the case of ENACT, support for GNN based data. For this reason, it is considered that there is no suitable tool on the market, that provides both an open-sources tool and the flexibility required for GNN based data and algorithms.

4.6.3 Beyond State of the Art

4.6.3.1 AI algorithms for prediction and scheduling

As analysed in section 4.6.1.1.1, the AI scheduling and orchestration outcomes from the ENACT Project will advance current Deep Reinforcement Learning techniques by incorporating application

⁸⁴ <https://www.datarobot.com/platform/>

⁸⁵ <https://www.alteryx.com/products/alteryx-designer>

⁸⁶ <https://h2o.ai/platform/ai-cloud/make/h2o/>

duration and security policies into their objective function. Additionally, established Deep Learning algorithms will be employed to predict telemetry data (available resources) for future time steps. This approach will enable the generation of multiple simulated network states and propose resource allocation not only for the current time step (t) but also for the future time step (t').

4.6.3.2 Graph Neural Networks

The application of GNN models in the continuum represents a significant advancement in edge-to-cloud resource management. By harnessing the power of GNNs to support predictive maintenance, automatic scheduling, and efficient decision-making, T5.2 will contribute to enhance the efficiency, resilience of the ENACT continuum.

The GNN models will be designed to capture the complex interdependencies and interactions within the entire cloud-edge continuum. By modelling the system as a dynamic graph, the models will be able to account for factors such as resource heterogeneity, network topology, application dependencies, and environmental conditions. This holistic approach will enable more comprehensive and informed decision-making for orchestration and deployment strategies.

The key innovations are:

- **Real-time optimisation:** By operating on dynamic graph models and processing data in real-time, GNN models will enable continuous optimisation of the edge-to-cloud continuum. This capability to adapt to changing conditions and requirements will set a new standard for efficiency and responsiveness in resource management.
- **Efficiency and resilience:** GNN models will enhance efficiency and resilience in the continuum by providing insights into optimal resource allocation, predicting maintenance needs, and enabling dynamic scheduling based on real-time conditions. This proactive approach will minimise downtime, improve performance, and optimise resource utilisation.
- **Complex decision-making:** GNN models will enable complex decision-making processes by considering a wide range of factors, such as performance metrics, energy efficiency, and network connectivity. This holistic approach will lead to more informed and effective decisions in managing the continuum.
- **Energy-efficient execution optimisation:** The GNN models will prioritise energy efficiency in application execution by identifying the most suitable nodes for executing tasks at any given time. By considering factors like power consumption, workload distribution, and environmental conditions, these models will optimise resource allocation to minimise energy consumption while meeting performance requirements.

4.6.3.3 Virtual Training Environments

The VTE developed in ENACT will be able to make use of a range of compute resources such as VM's, GPU's, and TPU' in a distributed computing framework to enable parallelised processing of data and model training across multiple nodes. In line with current trends, the ENACT VTE will be able to make use of containerisation technologies to encapsulate AI model training workflows and provide data management capabilities for ingesting, preprocessing and storing different types of training data. To support the iterative training and deployment scenarios, the VTE will provide model versioning and control mechanisms for managing different AI model versions, artifacts and metadata. User-centricity will be ensured through capabilities to track manage and monitor AI

model training experiments, hyperparameters, performance metrics and artifacts across different model configurations. In order to optimise the AI model training workflows, the VTE will provide automated ML (AutoML) capabilities to the model development process such as feature engineering, hyperparameter optimisation, and model selection. The users of the VTE will also be supported by the real-time monitoring and alerting mechanisms for the detection of anomalies, errors or performance reduction during AI model training. Security and privacy of the models will be ensured through robust security measures for the protection of sensitive data, model assets and compliance with industry regulations. The VTE will also provide secure APIs, authentication mechanisms and audit trails to maintain data integrity and confidentiality. User centricity will also be supported by an intuitive user interface that includes the availability of visualisation tools for the generation of interactive, charts, graphs and dashboards. To support wider utilisation and exploitation of the VTE, the developed solution will be offered as an open-source resource.

4.7 Application programming models

4.7.1 Research directions and related work

The development of hyper-distributed applications encompasses deploying applications across a diverse range of nodes and devices, including edge computing environments. This requires robust application programming models that offer high-level abstractions to simplify development across different platforms. Key tools and frameworks supporting this include Docker and Kubernetes for containerisation and orchestration, Apache Kafka and RabbitMQ for messaging in event-driven architectures, and Terraform and Ansible for infrastructure automation.

APIs like GraphQL⁸⁷, REST, and gRPC⁸⁸ play a central role by providing straightforward interfaces for data interactions, essential for maintaining consistency in distributed settings. Additionally, SDKs tailored for cross-platform compatibility and integrated security features are vital for accelerating development and ensuring application robustness.

Challenges in this domain include managing the heterogeneity of devices, network variability, and ensuring data consistency. Looking ahead, integrating distributed AI, enhancing edge computing capabilities, and employing blockchain for security are promising directions to address these challenges and push the boundaries of what hyper-distributed applications can achieve. The focus of ENACT project on developing suitable programming models and SDKs is a must for advancing the field in line with these technological trends.

In today's corporate landscape, enterprises are highly distributed, with both applications and users spread across multiple locations. This trend has been escalating, especially with the increased adoption of cloud-based services and the geographic dispersal of workforces triggered by the global pandemic. As a result, companies are compelled to overhaul their network and security frameworks.

This paper [78] outlines a Continuum-aware programming model, designed to optimise the execution of workflows across a compute continuum consisting of cloud, fog, and edge resources. The model seeks to simplify the management of heterogeneous nodes and alleviate the burden on

⁸⁷ <https://graphql.org/>

⁸⁸ <https://grpc.io/>

programmers, thereby fostering innovation. It introduces a meta-model that transforms workflows into autonomous service collaborations with defined contracts and Quality of Service, supporting seamless deployment and management. The paper also discusses the significance of adopting continuum-aware programming models and design patterns for handling ultra-scalable and hyper-distributed applications, aligning with predictions about the necessity for tools that support distributed infrastructure.

The proposed in [79] model promises to revolutionise the development experience by simplifying the creation of sophisticated, intelligent solutions that span across different computing environments, from centralised cloud servers to decentralised edge locations.

Although data is mostly collected in IoT devices, 80% of its processing takes place in data centres and centralised computing facilities such as clouds. This paradigm strongly relies on the network infrastructure and incurs high communication latencies and significant energy consumption while under-utilising the computing resources embedded in the IoT devices. Fostering architectures that empower end-users leveraging the collaborative capacities of IoT, edge and far-edge devices will reduce the dependence on the Cloud and the network overload and will enable IT systems with higher responsiveness, accuracy, and energy efficiency.

Currently, IoT and Edge devices are treated as surrogates to the Cloud not only from an application processing point of view; the control of the application and the infrastructure are hosted in the Cloud too. This has a strong impact on the design of hyper-distributed applications since developers must be concerned about the deployment of the different components of the application instead of focusing on solving the problems specific to their core business and area of knowledge.

4.7.2 Market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards

In the realm of hyper-distributed applications, there are several market-ready, commercial, and industrial solutions that leverage cutting-edge technologies to address the complexities of deploying and managing applications across diverse computing environments, including edge, fog, and cloud infrastructures. These solutions (described in what follows) are instrumental in achieving the goals set forth by the ENACT project and advancing the state-of-the-art in distributed computing.

Azure IoT Edge⁸⁹ is a fully managed service built on Azure IoT Hub. It allows data processing directly on IoT devices, enabling edge computing. This solution facilitates the deployment of cloud workloads, including AI, Azure services, and custom logic, directly to IoT devices. By bringing analytics closer to the data source, it reduces latency, improves efficiency, and ensures quicker responses. Some of the main features are: seamless integration with Azure cloud services, support for containerised workloads using Docker, enhanced security with built-in compliance and simplified deployment and management through Azure portal.

AWS IoT Greengrass⁹⁰ extends AWS cloud capabilities to local devices, enabling them to act locally on the data they generate while still using the cloud for management, analytics, and durable

⁸⁹ <https://azure.microsoft.com/en-us/products/iot-edge>

⁹⁰ <https://docs.aws.amazon.com/greengrass/>

storage. It supports local execution of AWS Lambda functions, Docker containers, and ML models, and ensures secure communication between devices.

Key features include the local execution of AWS Lambda functions, support for Docker containers, ML inference at the edge or secure data communication and management.

Google Cloud IoT Edge⁹¹ allows the deployment and execution of applications at the edge of the network, providing low-latency and high-performance solutions. It integrates with Google Cloud services, enabling edge devices to process data locally and send aggregated data to the cloud for further processing and analytics.

Smart manufacturing solutions like AWS IoT Greengrass and Azure IoT Edge are being deployed to enable predictive maintenance, quality control, and real-time monitoring of production lines. These technologies reduce downtime, improve product quality, and enhance operational efficiency by processing data locally and making real-time decisions.

Google Cloud IoT Edge and IBM Edge Application Manager⁹² are used in smart city applications to manage traffic, monitor environmental conditions, and enhance public safety. By processing data at the edge, these solutions provide real-time insights and responses to dynamic urban environments.

In healthcare, edge computing solutions from Cisco and Microsoft enable remote patient monitoring, real-time diagnostics, and enhanced data security. These technologies ensure low-latency data processing and reliable communication, crucial for critical healthcare applications.

By leveraging edge computing, containerisation, AI, and secure data management, these solutions address the challenges of latency, scalability, and security, paving the way for innovative and efficient distributed applications. The ENACT project can build upon these existing solutions to further enhance its programming models and SDKs, driving forward the development of robust and dynamic hyper-distributed applications.

4.7.3 Beyond State of the Art

Novel data management and processing frameworks oppose this resource-greedy, centralised management mechanisms and establish new control planes distributed across the Continuum integrating the -- compute, store, connectivity and cyber-physical -- capabilities of the devices with seamless management across providers, connectivity types and network zone. These next-generation computing and data technologies pave the way for the raise of new programming environments that ease the programming, deployment, and maintenance of hyper-distributed applications on the Continuum.

APM will be designed as a framework of languages, libraries, and tools for building applications and services that offer characteristics such as dynamism, adaptation, elasticity, load balancing, replication, portability, identification, secure communication, etc. The APM will provide high-level abstractions and APIS that will simplify the interactions between all ENACT components in order to create flows according to predefined scenarios. For example, it can help at integrating the results of the AI Forecaster that optimises configurations and predicts network needs with the Orchestrator that will deploy these configurations to the destination. Another example is to provide functions

⁹¹ <https://cloud.google.com/iot-core>

⁹² <https://www.ibm.com/mysupport/s/topic/0TO0z000000ZhYRGA0/edge-application-manager>

that export the implementation of secured data access and sharing mechanisms along with risk assessment tools that ensure data integrity.

4.8 Application control

4.8.1 Research directions and related work

The increasing availability and capabilities of edge devices raise the opportunity to share the application workloads between edge and cloud resources. Lately a lot of emphasis has been put on the sustainability and energy efficiency of edge and cloud infrastructures through better virtual and physical resource management. In this context, ENACT brings forward an additional opportunity for optimising the performance and environmental aspects of applications running on the edge and cloud infrastructure. This opportunity is realised by developing an application programming model and application-level adaptation strategies that guide the design and execution phases of distributed applications.

Application-level adaptation has been investigated in existing literature with two main objectives, that is a) the objective to optimise the performance and energy efficiency of the applications, and b) the objective to optimise the utilisation of underlying (compute and storage) edge and cloud resources. In the first category, several context-aware dynamic adaptation solutions for mobile applications have been proposed based on different mechanisms such as polymorphic methods [80] and reflection. In the edge computing domain, self-adaptive frameworks have been studied [81] that enable the applications to monitor their execution and adapt system behaviour.

Similarly, in the cloud computing domain, In [82], the authors focus on CPU usage as a way for determining where to redirect the workload of a task, based on the existing correlation between CPU usage and power consumption. Considering the application level, [83] proposes an approach based on the workload prediction to have a faster rearrangement of the system with the aim of reducing energy consumption.

In the second category, resource allocation algorithms are used to decide the best location of application components. The decision of such algorithms depends on the policies focusing on the optimal utilisation of the resources, also taking into account the energy efficiency perspective. An example can be found in [84], where resources are allocated using a bin packing algorithm based on an energy-aware heuristic. Moreover, algorithms considering eco-metrics for the deployment of distributed applications have been considered by eco4clouds [85], where a two-layer algorithm has been proposed for optimal resource utilisation in the multi-cloud environment. Similarly, in the edge computing, an adaptive resource allocation mechanism is developed for effective resource utilisation in dynamic settings [86]. The proposed mechanism is adaptable to a maximum number of incoming requests application deployment along with optimising the utilisation of limited resources at the edge node. In the edge-cloud infrastructures, a Software Defined Network (SDN) based approach is proposed [87] that provides a flexible load-balancing mechanism to allocate the required edge and cloud resources according to traffic load. Additionally, a dynamic resource allocation algorithm for cloud-edge environment is proposed in [88], which consists of a resource scheduling algorithm and a resource matching algorithm. The results achieved through experimentation of this algorithm indicate that proposed algorithms can effectively reduce network delay and enhance QoS of distributed edge and cloud applications.

In ENACT, the focus is on interlinking the compute and storage resources across the edge-cloud continuum and therefore the information coming from the monitoring the connected (edge-cloud) infrastructure is used to take decisions about the best deployment configurations in terms of energy efficiency, resource utilisation and quality of service (QoS) aspects among other relevant ones. Moreover, ENACT also considers application-level elasticity and scalability needs to extend the scope of adaptation actions that can help with the energy efficiency and QoS of applications. ENACT aims to realise such adaptivity through the design of an Application Controller that, ENACTing the right adaptation strategy for a given context, allows the improvement of the trade-off between QoS, resource utilisation, energy efficiency and other application-level constraints and optimisation parameters.

4.8.2 Market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards

Application-level adaptation has been deeply investigated in the mobile application domain, where constraints on energy consumption and limited resource availability necessitates dynamic adjustments in application behaviours based on user needs and interactions. In this respect, for Android-based mobile applications, the Xposed framework allows to modify the application aspects and behaviour at runtime without modifying any Android application package (APK).

Other solutions to support application-level adaptation include: **OpenTelemetry**⁹³, which is an observability framework and toolkit that provides a neutral approach for the collection and exportation of telemetry data such as metrics, traces, logs, events, and profiles. As a framework OpenTelemetry addresses the limitations of existing tools, through the facilitation of a range of systems monitoring tools such as Prometheus, Jaeger and Zipkin. Through this approach, OpenTelemetry provides a standardised framework for the collection of metrics and observability signals. Alongside this, OpenTelemetry provides a range of inbuilt tools such as the Collector, designed to support common procedures with performance monitoring operations. Open Telemetry is available as an Open-Source solution.

Similarly, **Prometheus**⁹⁴ is an open-source systems monitoring and alerting toolkit. The tool has widespread adoption across the industry with a vast range of companies and organisations using it. Prometheus provides the capability to collect and store metrics as time-series data while also logging additional key value pairs in labels. The tool provides a multi-dimensional data model, flexible query language, and operates in a pull based fashion to collect time series data over HTTP. Alongside this, there is no reliance on distributed storage and inbuilt autonomy for individual server nodes. Prometheus is also available as an Open-source framework.

Jaeger⁹⁵ is another open-source, end to end distributed tracing solution that is design for the monitoring, analysis, and troubleshooting of microservice based applications. The tool provides monitoring and analysis of dependencies, latencies, and performance bottlenecks, to support the identification and resolution of issues. Jaeger supports the tracing of path request between microservice to visualise a chain of events and provide insights on system behaviour. Through this approach Jaeger can monitor data movement, identify performance bottlenecks, and identify the

⁹³ <https://opentelemetry.io/>

⁹⁴ <https://prometheus.io/>

⁹⁵ <https://www.jaegertracing.io/>

root cause of issues to support distributed tracing. Jaeger is available as an Open-Source solution and can be used in the microservice architecture.

Lastly, **Zipkin**⁹⁶ is a distributed tracing system that is designed to gather real time, time series metrics in order to trouble shoot issues in microservice based architectures. The tool provides a focus on supporting integration, scalability, and problem resolution. Zipkin also provides the capability to trace requests as it travels through the system to enable the identification of bottlenecks, errors, and issues. Through the collection of data at different points in the system, Zipkin also provides through a web-based UI, detailed view of the system and data flows. Like other solutions described in this section, Zipkin is also available as an Open-source resource.

4.8.3 Beyond State of the Art

In the field of dynamic and distributed deployment, application adaptation strategies have emerged as vital means for ensuring the optimal performance and user experience of applications across a diverse range of platforms and environments. These strategies or mechanisms can encompass a wide range of techniques that aim to tailor software application behaviour to suit different device capabilities, network conditions, and user preferences.

Figure 5: Application Control in ENACT

For the development of application adaptation strategies, it is first essential to understand the deployment requirements and the metrics that needs to be monitored and taken into consideration by the application in order to perform the relevant adaptation actions. The work in (T6.2 of) ENACT will therefore focus on developing the set of metrics that can be used for effective monitoring of application behaviour and infrastructure utilisation at various layers in the edge-

⁹⁶ <https://zipkin.io/>

cloud ecosystem. Two key layers will be considered in ENACT, an Infrastructure layer from where resource related metrics (such as resource utilisation, energy consumption, environmental impact, etc.) from Sites, Hosts, devices and VM's will be gathered. Additionally, the metrics at Application layer will consider the metrics related to performance, energy and resources consumption of (various components of) distributed applications. The analysis of metrics from both layers, will enable the adaptation strategies to optimise the performance, resource utilisation and energy aspects of applications during runtime.

In ENACT, the application-level adaptation strategies will be implemented within a component called Application Controller, which will be part of the distributed application architecture, following the guidelines prescribed in the ENACT Application Programming Model. The Application Controller, will be responsible for performing 2 key operations, as shown in the above figure: a) monitoring of application (all relevant components) in terms of performance and resource consumption, and b) making intelligent decisions to perform runtime adaptations in the application execution behaviour or its deployment configuration. The adaptation decisions may correspond to the following:

- Turn On/Off application components/containers (to help with energy efficiency);
- Request (ENACT Orchestrator) changes in application deployment e.g. move containers (to help with load-balancing);
- Request (ENACT Orchestrator) Increase/Decrease allocated resource (to help with elasticity and cost aspects).

The above decisions will be made based on the analysis of (different types of metrics) and the application specific optimisation function (e.g. energy efficiency, load balancing, cost reduction, etc.). The application specific optimisation function can be configured at design/deployment time or at runtime e.g. through an API of the application controller.

The envisioned functionalities of the Application Controller provide new opportunities for developing more intelligent applications that can not only react to the dynamic changes and new opportunities in the compute continuum but also take proactive actions to optimise their execution through behavioural adjustments or deployment reconfigurations.

Within the ENACT Application Development Layer, while there are similarities in across technologies referenced by each component, it is important to also understand the distinction between components. In particular, the Application Controller and Application Policy Model will be discussed. The SDK is a component in which users can define their application deployment configuration and enable defined functions and services available in the APM within the ENACT architecture. One such service may be the definition of an Application Policy Model that contains a particular runtime constraint on the application. When an application is deployed within the ENACT ecosystem, it is deployed alongside an instance of the Application Controller which holds and enforces all policies. When particular constraints are met, the Application Controller will take action directly, for example by enabling or disabling individual containers, or, request redeployment from the ENACT Orchestrator.

4.9 Software development kits

4.9.1 Research directions and related work

The development of SDKs for hyper-distributed applications requires addressing several key research challenges. Research on abstracting the heterogeneity of devices and networks to simplify application development. Techniques such as model-driven engineering and middleware solutions can provide unified interfaces and protocols. Projects like FogFlow⁹⁷ focus on dynamic workflows across IoT, fog, and cloud environments, addressing the heterogeneity challenge.

Tools like GitHub Copilot⁹⁸ and DeepCode⁹⁹ use ML to provide intelligent code suggestions and identify potential issues early in the development process.

Using Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT) like Hyperledger¹⁰⁰ and Ethereum¹⁰¹ to develop decentralised applications, promoting trust and transparency in transactions, which is crucial for edge-cloud orchestration and zero-touch provisioning services. Research has been performed on blockchain-based decentralised IoT frameworks, such as "Blockchain for IoT Security and Privacy: The Case Study of a Smart Home" by Dorri et al. [89].

4.9.2 Market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards

To develop the ENACT Software Development Kit (SDK) effectively, it's essential to understand the existing tools to create SDKs. A list of such tools is comprised from developer tools that are either frameworks or IDEs as described in what follows.

- **Apache Mesos**¹⁰² is a platform that enhances the scalability and efficiency of distributed systems by abstracting resources such as CPU, memory, and storage, facilitating deployment across diverse infrastructures.
- **Kubernetes**¹⁰³ stands as a leading tool in managing containerised applications, Kubernetes automates the deployment, scaling, and management of distributed applications. It supports a wide range of programming languages and platforms, highlighting its versatility for development needs.
- **Eclipse Che**¹⁰⁴ is a cloud-based IDE tailored for developing distributed applications, supporting multiple languages and frameworks. It allows for the extension with plugins and supports collaborative development environments.
- **Visual Studio Code**¹⁰⁵, known for its extensive support through plugins for languages like Python and Java, Visual Studio Code integrates well with Docker, Kubernetes, and Azure, facilitates the development of cloud-native and distributed applications.

⁹⁷ <https://github.com/smartfog/fogflow>

⁹⁸ <https://github.com/features/copilot>

⁹⁹ <https://snyk.io/platform/deepcode-ai/>

¹⁰⁰ <https://www.hyperledger.org/>

¹⁰¹ <https://ethereum.org/en/>

¹⁰² <https://mesos.apache.org/>

¹⁰³ <https://kubernetes.io/>

¹⁰⁴ <https://eclipse.dev/che/>

- **Spring Boot**¹⁰⁶ is a primarily for the Java ecosystem, Spring Boot simplifies the development of microservice architectures with comprehensive libraries and supports resilience and fault tolerance. It also accommodates Kotlin, offering flexibility to developers.
- **Django**¹⁰⁷ and **Flask**¹⁰⁸ for Python are important frameworks for developers looking to build microservices efficiently. Django offers a high-level framework designed for rapid development and clean, pragmatic design, while Flask provides a more lightweight and flexible approach.

In the context of the ENACT Software Development Kit (SDK) for realising hyper-distributed applications, there are several market-ready, commercial, and industrial solutions that provide a foundation to start from.

- **Eclipse Che** is a cloud-based IDE that supports the development of distributed applications across multiple languages and frameworks. As the ENACT SDK is to be designed as a plugin for the Eclipse SDK, Eclipse Che provides a familiar environment for developers to leverage the power of microservices and edge computing.
- **Cisco Edge Intelligence**¹⁰⁹ simplifies data extraction, transformation, and delivery from connected assets at the edge to multiple destinations, supporting real-time data processing.
- **Red Hat OpenShift**¹¹⁰ is a Kubernetes-based platform that provides a comprehensive environment for deploying and managing containerised applications. It supports a wide range of programming languages and offers tools for continuous integration and delivery.
- **Oracle Cloud Infrastructure (OCI)**¹¹¹ provides a robust platform for deploying and managing applications in the cloud. It offers extensive support for containerised applications, serverless functions, and machine learning.

These solutions are widely adopted in finance, retail, manufacturing, industrial IoT, healthcare, and government sectors.

4.9.3 Beyond State of the Art

To go beyond the current state of the art in SDK development, we need to explore emerging technologies and innovative approaches that extend beyond the capabilities of the existing tools.

Using DLT enablers like Hyperledger Ethereum can facilitate the development of decentralised applications promoting trust and transparency in transactions like the edge-cloud orchestrations or zero provisioning services.

Including modules that support quantum computing development could prepare the platform for the next era of computing power and problem-solving capabilities.

¹⁰⁵ <https://code.visualstudio.com/>

¹⁰⁶ <https://spring.io/projects/spring-boot>

¹⁰⁷ <https://www.djangoproject.com/>

¹⁰⁸ <https://flask.palletsprojects.com/en/3.0.x/>

¹⁰⁹ <https://www.cisco.com/c/en/us/solutions/internet-of-things/edge-intelligence.html>

¹¹⁰ <https://www.redhat.com/en/technologies/cloud-computing/openshift>

¹¹¹ <https://www.oracle.com/cloud/>

As the SDK will provide a concrete implementation of the APM, the SDK will be an Eclipse plugin that offers the developers the possibility to implement the scenarios like the ones mentioned in section 4.7.

The SDK will allow the developers to create and manage the interaction with all ENACT components via the APM specifications.

The SDK will be implemented as an Eclipse plugin with UI that allows the developer to easily load ENACT components exposed interfaces. This will further allow the user to see the connections between components and update specific configurations. One potential use case for the SDK is to create scenarios without even writing Python or Java code, but instead using the UI or the markup language interpreted by the SDK to create Python or Java scripts.

One of the strong points of the SDK is that it can interconnect the ENACT components and provide a “birds-eye-view” of the platform. Another potential strong point is that it could ease the Continuous Delivery of the platform in a scalable and elastic manner.

4.10 Quality and security for distributed applications

4.10.1 Research directions and related work

Distributed Applications offer several benefits in comparison to traditional centralised applications such as flexible placement of services near geographic areas of high demand and rapid scaling depending on user requests. Despite their benefits distributed applications often introduce complexity due to their nature. Moreover, modern containerisation and service orchestration frameworks, such as Kubernetes (K8s), introduce several layers of abstraction and introduce additional complexity to application development and infrastructure management [90]. Proper configuration and fine-tuning of such tools is a necessary step to ensure that applications can scale properly with little effort in an automated and secure manner.

Ensuring the quality, security and privacy of distributed applications in modern hyper-converged cloud environments is a challenging task though [91]. It involves many monitoring techniques and methods accompanied by complex policies to ensure that services operate in their optimal condition securely and privately where unauthorised communication is not permitted. Moreover, securing and ensuring the privacy of distributed applications in large geographical and diverse infrastructure environments is crucial in maintaining user trust, protecting sensitive data, and aligning with regulatory bodies.

The increased communication between microservices containers renders the process of tracing difficult while also introducing additional network policies the administrator has to take into account when configuring the underlying networking infrastructure [92]. Kubernetes relies on Container Network Interface (CNI) plugin technologies such as Calico and Cilium, to manage all networking aspects of container communication and security, thus making the CNI an important element of each cloud environment. Most modern CNIs offer additional capabilities in terms of tracing and monitoring network traffic, exposing APIs, metrics and events to third-party tools and also provide SDKs to simplify the development of Control Plane applications that manage the underlying infrastructure. Additionally, CNIs provide extensive APIs to enforce network policies on a pod or cluster-wide scale.

Given that many distributed applications may span across multiple clusters, Service Meshes have emerged lately as a solution to multi-cluster interconnection. A Service Mesh will inject a sidecar container on each K8s pod responsible for handling all inbound and outbound traffic. Sidecar containers can easily be integrated with existing distributed applications without the need for altering the application logic at the cost of higher resource usage.

In light of the aforementioned challenges it is evident that flexible, adaptive and fine-grained monitoring methods are necessary to ensure distributed applications function as expected. Moreover, the underlying infrastructure should offer mechanisms and interfaces to enforce, design and implement complex policies related to placement of services and data.

4.10.2 Market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards

There is a large number of tools available to the community capable of monitoring distributed applications in many levels. Many tools offer tracing capabilities, offering enriched information to administrators related to events and how information flows between containers. Tools such as Jaeger and Istio Service Mesh offer such capabilities. Other tools focus on log collection analysis and reporting through visual front-end interfaces. Tools like ELK Stack and Splunk collect logs and process them efficiently to provide interactive visualisations. Finally, many security features and policies cannot be realised without a scalable and flexible network fabric. Calico, Cilium and Flannel are three of the most widely used CNI plugins in Kubernetes deployments. A description of the main feature each tool offer is listed below:

Monitoring Tools:

- **Prometheus**¹¹² is an open-source monitoring and alerting tool used for collection and recording of real-time events and metrics while also supporting some basic pre-processing of data before storing. It is a highly scalable application suitable for cloud-native and highly distributed environments without introducing much overhead in terms of processing needs. Thanks to its flexible querying language administrators can easily express complex queries and obtain insights, generate alerts, or even push data to visualisation tools like Grafana¹¹³. Prometheus can easily scale multi-node clusters by deploying agents on each node, whereas a server is responsible to collect, store data, produce alerts and export data to Grafana.
- **ELK Stack**¹¹⁴ is a set of three tools that when combined together provide a dynamic logging and monitoring platform capable of processing large volumes of events and logs in structured and unstructured formats. At its core the Elastic Stack uses Elasticsearch¹¹⁵, a distributed search and analytics engine optimised for text-based analytics that is accompanied by a REST-based querying language. ELK Stack also focuses on the preprocessing of data by exploiting Logstash, a data processing pipeline capable of ingesting large volumes of data, transforming them and even enriching them with additional information before appending them to Elasticsearch. Log and metrics collections on nodes is achieved using the Beats tool, a lightweight agent deployed on each node capable of

¹¹² <https://prometheus.io/>

¹¹³ <https://grafana.com/>

¹¹⁴ <https://www.elastic.co/elastic-stack>

¹¹⁵ <https://www.elastic.co/elasticsearch>

collecting logs and metrics. There are several UC specific Beats such as FileBeat¹¹⁶ (focusing on log files monitoring) or MetricBeat¹¹⁷ (focusing on system metric collection). Finally, Kibana is the main graphical use interface that visualises complex entries of Elasticsearch offering insights and interactive dashboards.

- **Splunk**¹¹⁸ is a software platform like ELK Stack that can process, index and analyse text, numeric in structured and unstructured formats. Splunk can easily make correlations between events Splunk proprietary indexing database offers unparallel querying speeds while its unified service model ensure smooth interoperability between its components.
- **Zabbix**¹¹⁹ is another server-client infrastructure monitoring solution that is popular in the IT sector. Zabbix deploys agents on nodes capable of operating system processes, network status and unlike other solutions it is capable of monitoring services like databases, websites and virtual machines. The Zabbix server is responsible for aggregating logs and metrics of agents, store them and produce reports that are can be delivered through various methods. Administrators can interact through a dashboard that offers interactive visualisations and notifications in a user-friendly environment.
- **Jaeger**¹²⁰ is a Distributed tracing observability platform designed specifically for distributed applications. Using Jaeger administrator can efficiently monitor all interactions between microservices in a distributed applications and identify bottlenecks, analyse request flows and identify root causes between microservices. Jaeger can export these metrics to popular tools like Grafana.
- **Zipkin**¹²¹ is an open-source distributed tracing tool designed for monitoring microservices. Developed can trace interactions between containers. Zipkin traces interactions between containers by monitoring calls and sending traces to a centralised server using Tracers, software applets that reside inside the distributed application.
- **Apache SkyWalking**¹²² is an open-source application performance monitoring software designed for distributed cloud environments and cloud architectures. It provides cluster wide observability and behaviour monitoring of distributed applications by collecting and analysing infrastructure logs, applications traces and telemetry data. SkyWalking offers support for multiple programming languages and can easily be integrated to existing distributed applications without much effort.

CNIs and Service Mesh Tools:

- **Cilium**¹²³ is a popular open-source project that provides networking, service monitoring and security capabilities for containerised environments. Cilium Container Network Interface

¹¹⁶ <https://www.elastic.co/beats/filebeat>

¹¹⁷ <https://www.elastic.co/beats/metricbeat>

¹¹⁸ https://www.splunk.com/en_us/products.html

¹¹⁹ <https://www.zabbix.com/>

¹²⁰ <https://www.jaegertracing.io/>

¹²¹ <https://zipkin.io/>

¹²² <https://skywalking.apache.org/>

¹²³ <https://cilium.io/>

(CNI) relies upon extended Berkley Packet Filters (eBPF)¹²⁴ Linux kernel feature to insert security, policies, and network control in the Linux kernel. This enables Cilium to handle packets as early as possible before being processed by the Linux network stack, thus offering higher overall performance, finer grained monitoring of communication between distributed application containers and superior security features compared to traditional solutions. Using Cilium Policies administrators can express complex communication policies between microservices, monitor inter-container communication and effectively and efficiently identify bottlenecks across the cluster. Cilium provides additional tools to express policies, monitor the cluster and APIs to communication with various Cilium Stack components.

- **Project Calico**¹²⁵ is an open-source networking and security solution designed for cloud native containerised environments. Calico CNI offers an OSI Layer 3 data plane fabric capable of interconnecting containers, virtual machines, and native host environments. Calico project also provides a network policy suite offering administrators tools to express complex communication policies between containers.
- **Flannel**¹²⁶ is another popular CNI framework that is used in many Kubernetes deployments and is popular for its simplicity and low overall resource utilisation. Flannel relies on Kubernetes etcd¹²⁷ distributed data store to store all its information.
- **Istio Service Mesh**¹²⁸ is an open-source service mesh platform that provides enhanced security, observability and control of distributed services. Istio operates on orchestration platforms such as Kubernetes to provide transparent, policy-driven communication between distributed applications using sidecar proxies while also focusing on privacy and security establishment between communicating entities.
- **Open Service Mesh (OSM)**¹²⁹ is an open-source service mesh platform that aims to provide a lightweight, easy to use and flexible means of traffic management, observability tracing and security of distributed applications. OSM adopts a simple and customizable architectural design focusing on ease of use while also adopting best practices with respect to security and integration with existing orchestrating platforms.

4.10.3 Beyond State of the Art

Distributed applications require sophisticated tools capable of monitoring services on multiple points and in many layers. Altering the core logic of containerised applications can easily become a challenging process for developers. To this end, sophisticated monitoring solutions that track the performance of applications should be employed. Given the multiple layers of abstraction present in modern virtualised environments, these solutions should be able to operate in containerised applications without the need to alter the distributed application. Moreover, monitoring on multiple

¹²⁴ <https://ebpf.io/>

¹²⁵ <https://www.tigera.io/project-calico/>

¹²⁶ <https://github.com/flannel-io/flannel>

¹²⁷ <https://etcd.io/>

¹²⁸ <https://istio.io/latest/about/service-mesh/>

¹²⁹ <https://openservicemesh.io/>

layers (i.e. application, networking, cluster) ensures the best possible acquisition of metrics and logs.

Any monitoring process should not consume resources when compared to the distributed application. In past years, enhanced programmability has emerged as a means of offering the developer more freedom in developing custom solutions that are not bound to hardware-specific implementations. Infrastructure programmability has resulted in more efficient use of hardware. Acceleration of computing and networking tasks using hardware-specific devices can reduce overall energy consumption without impacting total system performance [93] [94].

Based on the aforementioned points, UOWM undertakes the development of an infrastructure monitoring tool capable of collecting metrics of multi-cluster environments across the edge-to-cloud continuum focusing on minimizing unnecessary data transfers and on using efficient monitoring methods to provide alerts and metrics to other ENACT components. Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine is a tool based on open-source technologies and frameworks combined with custom solutions following the microservices approach. The tool collects low level infrastructure metrics, stores them efficiently and forwards them to other components. Moreover, the Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine will produce alerts when certain performance indicators are met and notify other components by producing events.

4.11 Overview of technologies and projects

These sections provide an overview of technologies and projects that are relevant to the ENACT project.

4.11.1 Relevant components and technologies

Component title	TRL (pre/post)	Justification
Orchestration tool - Kubernetes	9/9	By using Kubernetes, we will be able to use the custom schedulers functionality, so that we can make a component capable of executing deployment orders coming from the AI layer.
Edge Orchestration - KubeEdge	9/9	Allows for orchestration capabilities at edge level.
Keycloak	9/9	Used for Identity and Access Management
Eclipse Dataspace Components	8-9/9	Allows for interconnection with other ENACT components, setting data usage policies and ensuring data sovereignty
A Resource reference model for Data-Intensive Applications	3 / 5	Provides a rich semantic representation of the concepts for the overall description of service / application, resource and telemetry data (three models) in the context of data-intensive security-critical applications
Security Risk Modeller	3/6	Provides an interface to perform security risk analysis on the system models developed by the user.
Gephi	9/9	Permits visualising and analysing large networks and graphs

Table 5: Relevant components and technologies

4.11.2 Relevant projects

Project Title	Brief description	Potential strategies / Related Objective(s)
SERRANO	It aims to create a seamless and secure cloud computing ecosystem. It introduces an abstraction layer to integrate distributed edge, cloud, and high-performance computing (HPC) resources into a unified infrastructure.	The ARDIA Framework will be closely examined for the development of the ENACT CCC models. Other technologies of this project can be also examined, given its close relevance to ENACT.
TERMINET	The project aims to design and develop the next generation IoT architecture based on cutting-edge technologies such as Software-Defined Networking (SDN), Multiple Access Edge Computing (MEC) and Federated Learning.	TERMINET outputs and results and lessons learnt related to infrastructure and networking technologies will be examined and evaluated and taken into consideration.
DECICE	DECICE aims to develop an open and portable management framework for AI-based adaptive execution and optimisation of applications in computing continuum.	Sharing common objectives such as AI-based scheduling for orchestration of the application workload on the cloud-edge infrastructure, virtual training capabilities, security-compliant service deployment.
CODECO	CODECO aims to contribute to a smoother and more flexible support of services across the Edge-Cloud continuum via a unique, smart, and cross-layer orchestration between the decentralised data flow, computation, and networking services, to address Edge-Cloud challenges derived from the rising Internet and IoT service decentralisation.	Sharing common such as automated deployment, dynamic workload scheduling, decentralised learning and metadata management.
AC3	AC3 offers a common and secure federated platform that manages data source, CECC resources, and application behaviour in a unified and harmonised manner to ensure the desired SLA and save energy consumption. Moreover, the AC3 platform can adapt to a different context and events happening in the network, such as lack of resources, data deluge, or mobility of data source, by managing (i.e. deploying or migrating) micro-services across CECC infrastructures.	Sharing common objectives such as zero-touch management and configuration, AI-based resource forecasting and scheduling, focus on data management and integration with Data Spaces
DataCloud	Aiming to create a novel paradigm for Big Data pipeline processing over heterogeneous resources encompassing the Computing Continuum, covering the complete lifecycle of managing Big Data pipelines.	Although focused on Big Data Pipelines management, there are shared objectives such as intelligent resource management across the computing continuum with an infrastructure drift adaptability and decentralised data storage.

RE4DY	RE4DY mission is to demonstrate how European industry can jointly build unique data-driven manufacturing and supply network active resilience strategies and yet sustain competitive advantages through digital continuity and sovereign data spaces across all phases of product and process lifecycle	Sharing common objectives such as sovereign data spaces and AI-enabled cognition
knowlEdge	The knowlEdge project developed a framework that provides means for the secure management of distributed data and the computational infrastructure to execute the needed analytic algorithms and redistribute the knowledge towards a knowledge exchange society.	Sharing common objectives such as distributed AI training and deployment, data modelling, distributed data storage, metadata management and data governance
Zero-SWARM	The project establishes a unique forum where separately maturing technologies of 5G and cloud-edge continuum, data technologies and analysis (including data spaces and GAIA-X) and operational technology (automation and agility) break their siloes to co-design and co-create	Sharing common objectives such as zero-touch management, distributed intelligence for managing distributed applications, adaptability to changing conditions, distributed automation over the decentralised data and intelligence infrastructures
SCENE	SCENE develops a scalable and flexible framework, streamlining the entire film production process from pre-production to distribution. Through a network of interconnected and autonomous cognitive systems	Sharing common objectives such as cognitive AI, distributed data sharing, and monitoring of alignment with privacy and security regulations
MobiSpaces	MobiSpaces provides end-to-end mobility-aware and optimised data governance platform. It aims to achieve a common data space for the mobility data through in-situ processing with all the security and privacy related functionalities.	Within MobiSpaces, security risk analysis is manual based on direct access to pilot data which will be automated in ENACT.

Table 6: Relevant projects

5. ENACT platform specifications

The functional and technical specifications of the ENACT platform components were elicited based on the methodology described in section 3.3 of this Deliverable. The templates used for each component include the component, its modules and functions (if applicable) and the filled-in tables are provided in the next sections for each individual component.

5.1 Virtual Training Environment (VTE) component

Component Name
Intro / Overview

Virtual Training Environment

The Virtual Training Environment (VTE) for training, retraining, and recalibration of AI models is a workbench that helps users without skills in Data Analytics, Data Science, and AI techniques to train their own AI/ML algorithms. The component is composed of four main modules:

- The **Model Manager** is the entry point to the workbench where any of the algorithms present in the platform can be trained with their respective training/validation datasets. The Model Manager is also the place where all trained models are listed and can be finally configured prior to their execution in the target system. Within this module, the user can connect to data pipelines for serving the trained models predicting the purpose of the selected model.
- The **Execution Engine** is the module where the real execution of the trained models occurs. This module is based on Kubernetes pods and Docker containers to allow these models to be executed elsewhere.
- **Federated Learning (FL) Module** implemented on infrastructures or clusters within the CCC. Each cluster performs local training on its data, and the FL module aggregates these local models into a comprehensive global model, ensuring data privacy and efficient training.
- In addition, a **General module** is provided which contains all remaining components that may span across several modules such as the user interface, visualisation and security features.

Extracted Modules

- Model Manager
- Execution Engine
- Federated Learning
- General

Component Workflow

To illustrate the component workflow that takes place within the ENACT Virtual Training Environment, diagrams reflecting the interaction and workflow between components can be seen below.

External Component

Interaction with the ENACT Virtual Training Environment is realised through the ENACT

Interaction

Data Space. Users upload their input in the form of models and datasets, from which the ENACT virtual training environment can gain access. Within the UI of the component, operations are configured and once complete, the output is published back to the ENACT data space. In the case where exchanging models and datasets through the ENACT Data Space is not possible, Federated Learning Mechanisms will be explored and deployed. AI models will be exchanged only where edge node models will be used to train and update a common ‘master’ model in the cloud.

Prototypical Mock-ups

Login Page: The following image shows the Login Page which will greet users who try to enter the ENACT Virtual Training Environment and will request for authentication. A “Register” button will also be provided allowing new users to create an account within the ENACT ecosystem.

Home Page: Once users have successfully logged in on the page above, they will be

greeted with a Home screen. Here, the user can find an intro to the tool and links to documentation, as well as a top menu bar from where they can access the New Models page, My Models Page, and the virtual assistant. In the top right corner there are buttons to change the language settings, sign out of the application, and access to the logged in users account details.

New Model Page – Type of Algorithm: The following image show the New Models Page which can be accessed from the top menu bar. Here, three types of algorithms are displayed and available for selection, for a user to create a new ML/AI Model.

New Model Page – Supervised Algorithms: The following image displays the

Unsupervised Algorithms Page when selecting the type of algorithm in the previous page. Here a range of unsupervised ML algorithms are available for selection for the creation of a new model.

New Model Page – Unsupervised Algorithms: The following image displays the Supervised Algorithms Page when selecting the type of algorithm on the previous page. Here a range of supervised ML algorithms are available for selection for the creation of a new model.

New Model Page – Image Recognition Algorithms: The following image displays the Image Recognition Algorithms Page when selecting this type of algorithm on the previous

page. Here a range of image recognition ML algorithms are available for selection for the creation of a new model.

My Models Page: The My Models page can be accessed via the navigation bar at the top of the page and displays a user’s previously created models, from where they can select a particular model to view its details, and request further model specific information.

Selected Model Page: When selecting a specific model on the previous My Models page, a user will arrive at a page dedicated to that model. Here the user will find, a summary and details of the model and its configuration. Information surrounding the datasets used to train the model, any model results, and insights and visualisations related to the model

execution. Buttons will also be provided to the users, allowing them to output the model results and visualisation in a both PDF and HTML report formats.

TRL

Current: TRL-2
Expected: TRL-5

Potential Use-cases Layer

Applicable in all pilot scenarios

- ENACT Cognitive Computing Orchestration Layer
- ENACT AI Layer
- ENACT Modelling Layer

Technologies

The Virtual Training Environment is powered by the following technologies:

Programming Languages:

- Python¹³⁰
- Typescript¹³¹
- Java¹³²

¹³⁰ <https://www.python.org/>

¹³¹ <https://www.typescriptlang.org/>

Interfaces

Frameworks:

- Angular¹³³: a TypeScript-based free and open-source single-page web application framework run on Node.js.
- Node.js¹³⁴: a cross-platform, open-source JavaScript runtime environment
- TensorFlow¹³⁵: an open-source framework for ML.
- PyTorch¹³⁶: A popular ML library for dynamic computation graph capabilities.
- Flower (Federated Learning Framework)¹³⁷: A framework for building federated learning systems, facilitating the orchestration of distributed training and model aggregation.

Libraries:

- Numpy¹³⁸: a library for the Python programming language, adding support for large, multi-dimensional arrays and matrices, along with a large collection of high-level mathematical functions to operate on these arrays.
- Scipy¹³⁹: a library for scientific and technical computing
- Pandas¹⁴⁰: an open-source data analysis and manipulation tool.
- Scikit-learn¹⁴¹: an open-source library for ML
- SHAP¹⁴²: an open-source library to support the explanation of ML models.

Model Manager Interface:

- **Overview:** The Model Manger Interface facilitates communication with Model Manager module and can execute requests to the Execution Engine. Through the Model Manager Interface, a user can perform CRUD operation on existing models, as well as request the execution of particular model. In addition, the interface provides endpoints for the upload of training and test data for model training operations. The Model Manager Interface also supports the configuration of models to allow data ingestion from MQTT and AMQP sources.
- **Type:** REST API
- **State:** Synchronous
- **Data Format:** JSON

Initialisation Interface:

- **Overview:** This interface is responsible for initialising the federated learning process by distributing the initial model to the virtual edge nodes. It sets up the necessary environment for each node to begin local training.
- **Type:** REST API
- **State:** Synchronous
- **Data Format:** JSON

Local Training Interface:

¹³² <https://www.java.com/en/>

¹³³ <https://angular.dev/>

¹³⁴ https://nodejs.org/en#_blank

¹³⁵ <https://www.tensorflow.org/>

¹³⁶ <https://pytorch.org/>

¹³⁷ <https://flower.dev/>

¹³⁸ <https://numpy.org/>

¹³⁹ <https://scipy.org/>

¹⁴⁰ <https://pandas.pydata.org/>

¹⁴¹ <https://scikit-learn.org/>

¹⁴² <https://shap.readthedocs.io/>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Overview: Facilitates the actual training of ML models on local data available at client devices. It ensures models are trained using appropriate configurations and optimisation techniques. ● Type: REST API ● State: Asynchronous ● Data Format: JSON <p>Model Aggregation and Update Interface:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Overview: This interface aggregates the locally trained models from different client devices into a single global model. It ensures that model updates are appropriately weighted and combined. ● Type: REST API ● State: Synchronous ● Data Format: JSON <p>Validation and Testing Interface:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Overview: Validates and tests the aggregated model to ensure it meets specified performance and accuracy criteria. This interface is crucial for certifying the model before deployment. ● Type: REST API ● State: Synchronous ● Data Format: JSON <p>Deployment and Monitoring Interface:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Overview: Deploys the validated model to real-world edge devices and cloud servers. This interface also provides continuous monitoring of the model's performance, ensuring it remains effective and efficient in real-world applications. ● Type: REST API ● State: Asynchronous ● Data Format: JSON
Deployment Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Java¹⁴³ ● Software as a Service ● Docker Containers <p>The current deployment form of the virtual training environment is a series of docker containers. The component is also provided with a docker-compose script that allows for the deployment of all containers in the stack. The component requires minimum resources of 4GB RAM and 2 CPU cores.</p>
Authorisation Definition	<p>Given authentication is provided and validated in the ENACT Security and User Management system, all users will be able to access the ENACT Virtual Training Environment and its available AI/ML models. For the trained AI/ML models, a permissions system will be implemented allowing users to configure the access policies to their trained models. A permissions policy will be implemented to allow users to make their models either private and only visible/accessible to the model creator, or public, so that it can be discovered by other users in the ENACT Platform.</p>
Licence	Apache 2.0

Table 7: Virtual Training Environment Component specification

¹⁴³ <https://www.java.com/en/>

5.1.1 Model Manager module

Module Name	Model Manager	Priority	Must
Description	The Model Manager is the entry point to the workbench where any of the algorithms present in the platform can be trained with their respective training/validation datasets. The Model Manager is also the place where all trained modules are listed and can be finally configured prior to their execution in the target system. Within this module, the user can connect to data pipelines for serving the trained models predicting the purpose of the selected model.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Execution Engine • General / Other module 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Ingestor • Data Pipelines • ML Library • Model Uploader • Model Configurator • Model Validator • Model Registry • Model Orchestrator • Model Deployer 		
Success Criteria	All Module functions have been evaluated to be successful from their success criteria.		

Table 8: Model Manager module specification

Data Ingestor function

Function Name	Data Ingestor	Priority	Must
Description	This Data Ingestor allows for the ingestion of data. These ingested data are the ones to be used for training the different algorithms that will create the respective models. Usually, for training a model, a sample of structured datasets is needed and this sample is composed of static data for the achievement of a good model. These data are typically represented using either a CSV or a JSON file format. Other file formats include results from queries against a database (e.g., MySQL, SQL Server, PostgreSQL, etc.).		
Interacts with			
Success Criteria	The Data Ingestor should be able to ingest a range of datatypes and formats including MQTT, AMQP, REST and File Upload		

Table 9: Data Ingestor function specification

Data Pipelines function

Function Name	Data Pipelines	Priority	Must
Description	The Data Pipelines function manages the different input and output data pipelines that		

will serve the data for the execution of the model (e.g., from an IoT sensor) and store the results (e.g., in a database for future reference).

Interacts with

Success Criteria

The Data Pipelines function should be able to manage different input and output data types for use in the model execution. The function should also effectively transfer results of the model execution to the persistency layer.

Table 10: Data Pipelines function specification

ML Library function

Function Name	ML Library	Priority	Must
Description	The ML Library is a collection of ML/AI algorithms, classified by families (covering both Supervised and Unsupervised) for the training of the data. After the training of such data, the analytical models can be obtained. The intention of the product is to have a couple of algorithms present per family to cover a good range of analytical needs.		
Interacts with			
Success Criteria	The Model Reporter should be able to provide in report format visualisations and insights regarding metrics and KPIs of a given model. The Model Reporter will be able to provide reports in both HTML and PDF formats.		

Table 11: ML Library function specification

Model Uploader function

Function Name	Model Uploader	Priority	Must
Description	The Model Uploader provides the capability to upload external analytical models. External models are considered to be those that are trained outside of the Model Trainer within the ENACT Virtual Training Environment. Currently, this is performed via REST API, but will also be exposed through an additional API interface.		

Interacts with	<pre> graph LR DP[Data Pipelines] -- "data (Untrained Model)" --> ML[ML Library] ML -- "data (Trained Model)" --> MU[Model Uploader] MU -- "data (Trained Model)" --> MC[Model Configurator] MC -- "data (Trained Model)" --> MU style MU stroke:#f00,stroke-width:2px </pre>
Success Criteria	The Model Uploader should be able to upload a range of model types and formats for use within the model registry or model deployer.

Table 12: Model Uploader function specification
Model Configurator function

Function Name	Model Configurator	Priority	Must
Description	This Model Configurator helps to configure a model (both local and global ones in case of Federated Learning) that is going to be deployed in the execution engine with regards to data pipelines for data ingestion or sink, etc.		
Interacts with	<pre> graph LR MU[Model Uploader] -- "data" --> MC[Model Configurator] MC -- "data" --> MV[Model Validator] style MC stroke:#f00,stroke-width:2px </pre>		
Success Criteria	The Model Configurator should be able to manage a range of different configuration parameters for a model including the data input and output of a given model.		

Table 13: Model Configurator function specification
Model Validator function

Function Name	Model Validator	Priority	Must
Description	This Model Validator will automatically validate the models that have been trained using technologies other than the Model Trainer with respect to metadata and model descriptors, such as the RMSE, predictors, features and output parameters.		
Interacts with	<pre> graph LR MC[Model Configurator] -- "data" --> MV[Model Validator] MV -- "data" --> MR[Model Registry] style MV stroke:#f00,stroke-width:2px </pre>		
Success Criteria	The Model Validator should be able to review and validate any given model for its configuration parameters and compatibility within the ENACT Virtual Training Environment.		

Table 14: Model Validator function specification
Model Registry function

Function Name	Model Registry	Priority	Must
Description	This Model Registry is for registering the models deployed so that they can be configured, monitored or selected for execution. This component represents the actual database (currently implemented over MySQL) for the persistency and management of deployed models. This component is expected to be replaced/revamped using MLFlow technology stack.		

Interacts with	<pre> graph LR MV[Model Validator] -- data --> MR[Model Registry] MR -- data --> MO[Model Orchestrator] </pre>
Success Criteria	The Model Registry should be able to store a range of types of models while providing basic CRUD functionality to the registry.

Table 15: Model Registry function specification

Model Orchestrator function

Function Name	Model Orchestrator	Priority	Must
Description	The Model Orchestrator orchestrates the execution of the different deployed models while ensuring that the data is ready for its ingestion at the model entry points. This component is expected to provide the different metrics/KPIs such as such execution performance, data ingestion rate, accuracy of prediction, etc.		
Interacts with	<pre> graph LR MR[Model Registry] -- data --> MO[Model Orchestrator] MO -- data --> MD[Model Deployer] </pre>		
Success Criteria	The Model Validator should be able to review and validate any given model for its configuration parameters and compatibility within the ENACT Virtual Training Environment.		

Table 16: Model Orchestrator function specification

Model Deployer function

Function Name	Model Deployer	Priority	Must
Description	The Model Deployer is used for deploying the different analytical models to a production system as this acts as the bridge with the Model Trainer for those models trained with the Model Trainer. This is the final component for deploying a model in the production system and fed by the Model Trainer and the Model Validator.		
Interacts with	<pre> graph LR MO[Model Orchestrator] -- data --> MD[Model Deployer] MD -- data --> ME[Model Executor] </pre>		
Success Criteria	The Model should be able to deploy all validated models. Those provided by the ENACT Virtual Training Environment and those uploaded by external sources.		

Table 17: Model Deployer function specification

5.1.2 Execution Engine module

Module Name	Execution Engine	Priority	Must
Description	The Execution Engine is the module where the real execution of the trained models		

Interacts with	occurs. This module is based on Kubernetes pods and Docker containers to allow these models to be executed elsewhere.
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Model Trainer • Model Manager • Data Sink • Data Pipelines • Model Executor • Model Executor Metering • Visualisation
Success Criteria	All Module functions have been evaluated to be successful from their success criteria.

Table 18: Execution Engine module specification

Model Executor function

Function Name	Model Executor	Priority	Must
Description	The Model Executor is in charge of the actual execution of the deployed models.		
Interacts with	<pre> graph TD MD[Model Deployer] -- data --> ME((Model Executor)) ME -- data --> M[/Model/] M -- data --> MEM[Model Executor Metering] M -- data --> MM[Model Monitor] M -- data --> AE[AI Explainability] M -- data --> DS[Data Sink] </pre>		
Success Criteria	The Model Executor should be able to effectively execute all provided and validated models.		

Table 19: Model Executor function specification

Model Executor Metering function

Function Name	Model Executor Metering	Priority	Must
Description	The Model Executor Metering measures and computes the different execution metrics/KPIs as needed by the Model Manager.		

Interacts with	<pre> graph TD ME[Model Executor] -- data --> M[/Model/] M -- data --> MEM[Model Executor Metering] MEM -- data --> V[Visualisation] </pre>
Success Criteria	<p>The Model Executor Metering function should be able to accurately measure and compute simultaneously a range of different execution metrics as set by the Model Manager.</p>

Table 20: Model Executor Metering function specification

Model Monitor function

Function Name	Model Monitor	Priority	Must
Description	<p>This Model Monitor is used for informing the user about the KPIs related to the execution of a given analytical model. It should evaluate metrics/KPIs such as execution performance, data ingestion rate, accuracy of prediction, etc.</p>		
Interacts with	<pre> graph TD ME[Model Executor] -- data --> M[/Model/] M -- data --> MM[Model Monitor] MM -- data --> V[Visualisation] </pre>		

Success Criteria

The Model Monitor should be able to simultaneously monitor and evaluate multiple analytical models against key metrics and KPI's that have been configured.

Table 21: Model Monitor function specification

AI Explainability function

Function Name	AI Explainability	Priority	Must
Description	The AI Explainability function is used for explaining the output of any ML model that has been trained. This output is represented using Shapley values, which are a widely used approach from cooperative game theory that come with desirable properties. It is implemented using the SHAP library ¹⁴⁴ .		
Interacts with	<pre> graph TD A[Model Executor] -- data --> B[/Model/] B -- data --> C[AI Explainability] C -- data --> D[Reporting] </pre>		
Success Criteria	The AI Explainability function should be able to provide accurate explanations of the output of any ML model that has been trained. The explanations should be provided and represented through Shapley values.		

Table 22: AI Explainability function specification

Data Sink function

Function Name	Data Sink	Priority	Must
Description	This Data Sink is needed for acting as a bridge to store the data used for the execution and the result of the execution so an audit trail can be followed.		

¹⁴⁴ <https://shap.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>

Interacts with	<pre> graph TD ME[Model Executor] -- data --> M[/Model/] M -- data --> DS[Data Sink] DS -- data --> IDS[(Internal Data Store)] DS -- data --> ENADS[(ENACT Data Store)] </pre>
Success Criteria	The Data Sink should be able to accurately store the available data from both the execution and execution result to form an audit trail.

Table 23: Data Sink function specification

5.1.3 General module

Module Name	General	Priority	Must
Description	The General module houses remaining components that are used across the ENACT Virtual Training Environment.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Model Manager Execution Engine 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Web UI User Management Security Visualisation Model Reporter 		
Success Criteria	All module functions have been evaluated to be successful from their success criteria.		

Table 24: General module specification

Web UI function

Function Name	Web UI	Priority	Must
Description	The Web UI component provides the point of interaction for the intended end users. It		

Interacts with	will be offered via web address and accessible via the internet. The Web UI will provide a means to interact with all modules and functions in the ENACT Virtual Training Environment.
Success Criteria	The Web UI should be accessible over HTTPS and secured effectively. It should provide a positive user experience and be intuitive in nature. It should effectively provide access to the solution's Model Manager, Model Trainer, and Execution Engine modules.

Table 25: Web UI function specification

User Management function

Function Name	User Management	Priority	Must
Description	The User Management function manages user account and checks which users have access to which models. Currently this is based on ad-hoc login mechanisms although Keycloak is being assessed as an open-source alternative for its implementation.		
Interacts with			
Success Criteria	The User Management function should effectively manage the user account of each user, while also effectively managing access to different stored models based on the permissions configured.		

Table 26: User Management function specification

Security function

Function Name	Security	Priority	Must
Description	The security function manages and enforces the user and permissions based access to models and training data. Working with the User Management module, the security function will provide the authentication and authorisation mechanisms to enforce secure Models, Training Data, and Model Results.		

Interacts with	
Success Criteria	The security function should provide authentication and authorisation mechanism to the User Management function, to support effective user-based access control.

Table 27: Security function specification

Visualisation function

Function Name	Visualisation	Priority	Must
Description	The Visualisation function is in charge of generating a range of charts, plots and visualisations. The function will generate lightweight plots that can generated from the results of the execution of a given analytical model, while being easier to generate and maintain. The visualisation function will also generate professional heavyweight plots which can form dashboards for professional use. The heavyweight charts will be able to facilitate the use of complex-linked charts and the creation of dashboards for viewing both the results of the execution and the trained data.		
Interacts with			
Success Criteria	The Visualisation should provide easy-to-generate and maintain light weight visualisations. It should provide heavyweight visualisations for professional UCs. It should provide the ability to create dashboards from multiple plots or charts. It should be able to generate charts reflecting trained data and the results of a model execution.		

Table 28: Visualisation function specification

Model Reporter function

Function Name	Model Reporter	Priority	Must
Description	The Model Reporter is expected to plot in a graphical way (UI) the results of the execution as well as the monitoring KPIs of the deployed analytical model. This component		

Interacts with	<p>represents the actual plotting libraries together with the collection of tables and HTMLs to show the results.</p> <pre> graph TD A[AI Explainability] -- data --> R[Reporting] V[Visualisation] -- data --> R style R stroke:#f00,stroke-width:2px </pre>
Success Criteria	<p>The Model Reporter should be able to provide in report format visualisations and insights in regards to metrics and KPIs of a given model. The Model Reporter will be able to provide reports in both HTML and PDF formats.</p>

Table 29: Model Reporter function specification

5.1.4 Federated Learning module

Module Name	Federated Learning	Priority	Must
Description	<p>The Federated Learning (FL) module within the Virtual Training Environment (VTE) is designed to facilitate the training, validation, and deployment of AI models across distributed nodes such as edge devices and cloud servers. This module ensures that data remains localised, maintaining privacy while enabling collaborative model training. The VTE's capabilities for simulation, validation, and optimisation are leveraged to support efficient federated learning.</p>		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Execution Engine Model Validator General / Other module 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Initialisation Local Training Model Aggregation Validation and Testing Deployment and Monitoring 		
Success Criteria	Different for each function		

Table 30: Federated Learning module specification

Initialisation function

Function Name	Initialisation	Priority	Must
Description	<p>Initialises the federated learning process by distributing the initial model to the virtual edge nodes simulated in the VTE. This function sets up the necessary environment for each node to begin local training.</p>		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Model Manager: To access initial models and configure training parameters. 		

Success Criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Execution Engine: To initiate the process of distributing the initial model to nodes.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The initial model is successfully distributed to all nodes.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training parameters are correctly configured and aligned with the Model Manager.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No initialisation errors occur, ensuring a smooth start to the training process.

Table 31: Initialisation function specification

Local Training function

Function Name	Local Training	Priority	Must
Description	<p>Training involves the actual training of the ML model on the local data available on the client device. The training process may be repeated for multiple epochs to allow the model to learn from the data effectively. To improve efficiency, optimisation and model compression techniques are used.</p> <p>Model compression techniques may be applied to reduce the size of the trained model before sending updates to the central server. Model compression helps minimise communication overhead by reducing the amount of data transmitted between client devices and the central server. Techniques such as quantisation, pruning, or knowledge distillation may be used for model compression, depending on the requirements of the federated learning scenario.</p> <p>Optimisation techniques are applied to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of the training process. Techniques like regularisation, dropout, or learning rate scheduling may be employed to prevent overfitting, enhance convergence, and improve generalisation. Early exit may also be used to halt training when the model performance on a validation dataset starts deteriorating, thus preventing unnecessary computation.</p>		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Model Manager: To retrieve data pipelines and training configurations. • Execution Engine: To manage the execution of training processes on nodes. <div style="text-align: center; margin-top: 10px;"> </div>		
Success Criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Each node completes local training within the specified timeframe. • Models are trained using the correct local data without errors. • Training results are accurately reported back to the VTE. 		

Table 32: Local Training function specification

Model Aggregation and Update function

Function Name	Model Aggregation and update	Priority	Must
Description	<p>Aggregation determines how model updates from different client devices are combined to update the global model. Common aggregation techniques include simple averaging, weighted averaging, or more sophisticated methods like Federated Averaging or Secure</p>		

Interacts with	Aggregation. Aggregation techniques ensure that each client's contribution to the global model is appropriately weighted based on factors like data quality or model performance. Model Manager: To manage aggregated model updates. Execution Engine: To facilitate the collection and aggregation of model updates from nodes.
Success Criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All node updates are successfully aggregated into a single global model. • The aggregation process completes without data loss or corruption. • The aggregated model demonstrates improved performance metrics over individual node models.

Table 33: Model Aggregation and Update function specification

Validation and Testing function

Function Name	Validation and Testing	Priority	Must
Description	The aggregated model is validated and tested within the VTE to ensure it meets performance and accuracy criteria.		
Interacts with	Model Validator: To validate and test the model under various scenarios. Model Manager: To ensure the model meets required standards.		
Success Criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The aggregated model passes all validation tests with specified accuracy and performance metrics. • No critical errors are found during the testing phase. • The model is certified as ready for deployment based on validation results. 		

Table 34: Validation and Testing function specification

Deployment and Monitoring function

Function Name	Deployment and Monitoring	Priority	Must
Description	Once validated, the model is deployed to real-world edge devices and cloud servers. The VTE continues to monitor the model's performance and provides feedback for continuous improvement. This function ensures that the model remains effective and efficient in real-world applications.		
Interacts with	Execution Engine: For deploying the model to real-world environments. Model Manager: For continuous performance monitoring and feedback.		
Success Criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The model is successfully deployed to all targeted edge devices and cloud servers. • Continuous monitoring is established without interruptions. • Performance metrics are collected and analysed to provide actionable feedback for model improvements. 		

Table 35: Deployment and Monitoring function specification

5.2 Application Controller component

Component Name	Application Controller
-----------------------	------------------------

Intro / Overview

The application controller will be deployed alongside containerised components of all ENACT applications. It will monitor and collect application metrics and dynamically realise and implement application adaptation mechanisms to enable applications to modify their behaviour or configuration based on feedback from the environment or user preferences. Adaptation actions will focus on the following strategies to help optimise the application execution behaviour:

- Load balancing
- Elasticity
- Energy efficiency

Extracted Modules

- Application Adaptation Engine
- Application Adaptation Strategies
- Application Data Manager

Component Workflow

To illustrate the component workflow that takes place within the ENACT Virtual Training Environment, diagrams reflecting the interaction and workflow between components can be seen below.

External Component Interaction

The application controller will be deployed by the ENACT Orchestrator as a sidecar container alongside each of the components (containers) of a given application.

The application controller will be deployed with a set of user-defined or ENACT-recommended adaptation strategies for the given application.

On deployment, the application will report application telemetry data back to the Orchestrator. The tool will provide an interface for application components to interact with the ENACT Data Layer. Finally, the Application Controller will retrieve, read and enforce policies defined in the Application Policy Model via redeployment requests to the Orchestrator.

Prototypical Mock-ups
TRL

N/A

Potential Use-cases
Layer
Technologies

Current: TRL – 0
Expected: TRL – 3

All pilot scenarios

Application Development Layer

The Virtual Training Environment is powered by the following technologies:
Programming Languages:

- Python
- Typescript

Frameworks:

- Angular: a TypeScript-based free and open-source single-page web application framework run on Node.js.
- Node.js: a cross-platform, open-source JavaScript runtime environment

Libraries:

- OpenTelemetry¹⁴⁵: Observability framework and toolkit.
- Prometheus¹⁴⁶: Monitoring and alerting toolkit.
- Jaeger¹⁴⁷: Distributed tracing platform

Interfaces

Application Manager Interface:

- **Overview:** The Application Manager Interface provides the entry point to the application controller, allowing communication with the Orchestrator to support deployment and redeployment, as well as the feedback of application telemetry data.
- **Type:** REST API
- **State:** Synchronous
- **Data Format:** JSON

¹⁴⁵ <https://opentelemetry.io/>

¹⁴⁶ <https://prometheus.io/>

¹⁴⁷ <https://www.jaegertracing.io/>

	Application Data Manager Interface: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: The Application Data Manager Interface facilitates the communication between deployed application components and the ENACT Data Layer. • Type: REST API • State: Synchronous • Data Format: JSON
Deployment Type	The application controller will be deployed as a sidecar container alongside each application
Authorisation Definition	The Application Controller will be available to all ENACT users.
Licence	Apache 2.0

Table 36: Application Controller Component specification

Application Manager function

Function Name	Application Manager	Priority	Must
Description	The Application Manager is the core function within the Application Controller, responsible for coordinating the actions of sub-modules and functions within the component, and for communication with external interfaces. The function will connect to the Application Adaptation Engine, and execute required operations including the execution of requests to the Orchestrator for load balancing or increased elasticity, as well as connecting directly to application containers to execute the energy efficiency strategy. The Application Manager also connects to the Application Data Manager in order to forward application telemetry data through to the orchestrator as needed.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application Adaptation Engine • Application Data Manager 		
Success Criteria	The Application Manager must be able to successfully coordinate the operation of the Application Adaptation Engine and the Application Data Manager. It must be able to communicate with the Orchestrator for the transfer of telemetry data, and to request changes in deployment configuration.		

Table 37: Application Manager function specification

5.2.1 Application Adaptation Engine module

Module Name	Application Adaptation Engine	Priority	Must
Description	A set of implementable mechanisms that can be used to execute a given application adaptation strategy when a threshold or trigger point is met.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application Adaptation Strategies • Application Manager 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relocation Requester • Resource Allocation Requester • Container Enabler 		
Success Criteria	All Module functions have been evaluated to be successful from their success criteria.		

Table 38: Application Adaptation Engine module specification

Relocation Requester function

Function Name	Relocation Requester	Priority	Must
Description	An adaptation strategy, or multiple strategies that can be triggered upon defined		

Interacts with	conditions to request a change in the deployment of the application from the ENACT Orchestrator.
	Load Balancing Application Adaptation Strategy
Success Criteria	The Relocation Requester must be able to effectively read present load balancing application adaptation strategies, and when set criteria are met, must be able to execute a request to the ENACT Orchestrator that requests for a redeployment of components to meet application demands.

Table 39: Relocation Requester function specification

Resource Allocation Requester function

Function Name	Resource Allocation Requester	Priority	Must
Description	An adaptation strategy, or multiple strategies that can be triggered upon defined conditions to request a change in the deployment of the application from the ENACT Orchestrator.		
Interacts with	Elasticity Application Adaptation Strategy		
Success Criteria	The Resource Allocation Requester must be able to effectively read present elasticity application adaptation strategies, and when set criteria are met, must be able to execute a request to the ENACT Orchestrator that requests a change to the allocated resources for specific app component.		

Table 40: Resource Allocation Requester function specification

Container Enabler function

Function Name	Container Enabler	Priority	Must
Description	An executable mechanism that can be used to implement the energy efficiency application adaptation strategy. The mechanism enables the Application Controller to turn individual application components or containers off and on as needed in order to optimise energy usage.		
Interacts with	Energy Efficiency Application Adaptation Strategy		
Success Criteria	The Container Enabler must be able to effectively read present energy efficiency application adaptation strategies, and when set criteria are met, must be able to turn off and on individual application components to support energy efficiency requirements.		

Table 41: Container Enabler function specification

5.2.2 Application Adaptation Strategies module

Module Name	Application Adaptation Strategies	Priority	Must
Description	A set of user define or ENACT recommended adaptation strategies for a given application.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application Adaptation Engine • Application Manager 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Load Balancing • Elasticity • Energy Efficiency 		
Success Criteria	All Module functions have been evaluated to be successful from their success criteria.		

Table 42: Application Adaptation Strategies module specification

Load Balancing function

Function Name	Load Balancing	Priority	Must
Description	An adaptation strategy, or multiple strategies that can be triggered upon defined		

Interacts with	conditions to request a change in the deployment of the application from the ENACT Orchestrator.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Relocation Requester
Success Criteria	The Load Balancing application adaptation strategy must include a defined procedure for the request of a change in deployment location of application containers, including metrics and trigger points for the strategy to be implemented.

Table 43: Load Balancing function specification

Elasticity function

Function Name	Elasticity	Priority	Must
Description	An adaptation strategy or multiple strategies that can be triggered upon defined conditions to request a change in the allocated resources of the application from the ENACT Orchestrator		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Resource Allocation Requester 		
Success Criteria	The Elasticity application adaptation strategy must include a defined procedure for the request of a change in the allocated resources of application containers, including metrics and trigger points for the strategy to be implemented.		

Table 44: Elasticity function specification

Energy Efficiency function

Function Name	Energy Efficiency	Priority	Must
Description	An adaptation strategy, or multiple strategies that can be triggered upon defined conditions to request to turn off or on individual application containers.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Container Enabler 		
Success Criteria	The Energy Efficiency application adaptation strategy must include a defined procedure including metrics and trigger points that enable the Application Controller to turn individual containers off and on as needed.		

Table 45: Energy Efficiency function specification

5.2.3 Data Manager module

Module Name	Data Manager	Priority	Must
Description	A set of mechanisms designed to support the operations of the Application Controller. Functions provided to support the monitoring of telemetry data from application components, and to enable the execution of requests to the ENACT Orchestrator.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENACT Orchestrator Application Containers User Access and Sharing Interfaces Application Manager 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Telemetry Data Manager Application Data Manager 		
Success Criteria	All Module functions have been evaluated to be successful from their success criteria.		

Table 46: Data Manager module specification

Telemetry Data Manager function

Function Name	Telemetry Data Manager	Priority	Must
Description	A mechanism that enables the capture, monitoring, and reporting of application		

Interacts with	telemetry data for both enabling adaptation strategies on their trigger points and reporting back to the ENACT Orchestrator. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Application Containers Application Adaptation Strategies Application Manager
Success Criteria	The Telemetry Data Manager must be able to capture, monitor and report application telemetry data from running application components and report data back to the ENACT Orchestrator

Table 47: Telemetry Data Manager function specification

Application Data Manager function

Function Name	Application Data Manager	Priority	Must
Description	A mechanism that provides access to the ENACT Data Layer for application, allow the application to access and store user data in a central repository		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Application Adaptation Strategies Application Adaptation Engine Application Manager 		
Success Criteria	The Application Data Manager function is must be able to provide effective access to the ENACT Data Layer for deployed applications. The function must be able to support CRUD operations for each deployed application and facilitate data access and storage.		

Table 48: Application Data Manager function specification

5.3 Graph Neural Network (GNN) Models component

Component Name	ENACT Graph Neural Network (GNN) models
Intro / Overview	<p>The ENACT GNN models, developed using ML-based GNN algorithms, will permit the scheduling and dynamic optimisation of ENACT hyper-distributed applications.</p> <p>By leveraging graph representation, the models enable a more efficient and effective analysis of relationships between diverse nodes. They proficiently model the connections among various services and accurately predict optimal configurations to improve service availability, latency, and other performance metrics.</p>
Extracted Modules	N/A
Component Workflow	N/A
External Component Interaction	<p>The Dynamic Graph Modeller is responsible for constructing and updating the graph structure based on incoming telemetry data, which will feed the updated graph data into the AI Forecaster to predict trends and the continuum’s behavioural patterns. With these sub-optimal schedules generated by the ML algorithms employed by the AI Forecaster, the GNN uses this data to perform graph-based learning tasks, such as node classification or link prediction. By doing this, the GNN refines and optimises these sub-optimal schedules and sends them to the DRL for further decision-making and deployment.</p> <p>In parallel, based on the performance metrics and potential new data, models used by the GNN in order to perform this computations on the schedules are constantly being updated within the Virtual Training Environment, adjusting the GNN model's parameters to enhance its accuracy and generalisation capabilities for subsequent use.</p>

Prototypical Mock-ups
TRL

N/A

Potential Use-cases
Layer
Technologies

Current: TRL-2
Expected: TRL-5

Applicable in all pilot scenarios

ENACT Cognitive Computing Orchestration Layer

The Graph Neural Network is powered by the following technologies:

Programming languages:

- Python

Framework:

- PyTorch
- TensorFlow

Libraries / Tools:

- PyTorch Geometric
- NVIDIA CUDA Toolkit
- cuDNN

Interfaces

Inference Interface:

- **Overview:** The Interface provides the necessary communication between the AI Forecaster component and the GNN component in order to both receive the sub-optimal schedules that require optimisation and transfer them back to the AI Forecaster for further deployment.
- **Type:** REST API
- **State:** Synchronous
- **Data Format:** JSON

Retraining Interface:

- **Overview:** This interface would serve to transfer the models used by the GNN to

Deployment Type	<p>the VTE, a component that is responsible for re-training the models to make them more accurate and efficient to be used by the GNN for future optimisations.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Type: REST API • State: Synchronous • Data Format: JSON <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI as a Service (AlaaS) • Docker Containers <p>The AI model will be accessible to other services via a REST API, allowing seamless integration and interaction with its capabilities. Additionally, the API will be dockerised, ensuring easy deployment and scalability across different environments.</p>
Authorisation Definition	<p>Authorisation for accessing the ENACT GNN models will be facilitated through a RESTful API, with authentication being provided and validated by the ENACT Security and User Management system. Upon successful authentication, the API will enforce authorisation rules to determine whether the authenticated user has the necessary permissions to access the GNN models.</p>
Licence	<p>Apache 2.0</p>

Table 39: Graph Neural Network Component specification

Inference function

Function Name	Inference	Priority	Must
Description	Users can leverage this component to interact with the model, providing inputs for processing and receiving corresponding predictions or results in return.		
Interacts with	AI Forecaster: To pass the updated sub-optimal schedules.		
Success Criteria	The component should consistently provide predictions or results without errors or unexpected behaviour.		

Table 40: Inference function specification

Retraining function

Function Name	Retraining	Priority	Must
Description	GNN models should possess the capability to update their parameters through local retraining techniques within the Virtual Training Environment, leveraging events to enhance the cognitive capabilities of the ENACT edge-to-cloud continuum.		
Interacts with	Virtual Training Environment: To update the improved models used for optimising the deployments.		
Success Criteria	The model can be re-trained with new data within the Virtual Training Environment.		

Table 41: Retraining function specification

Evaluate function

Function Name	Evaluate	Priority	Should
Description	GNN models should be capable of generating relevant and understandable evaluation metrics reflecting their performance across various tasks and datasets. These metrics should be quantifiable, interpretable, and provide meaningful insights into the accuracy, robustness, efficiency, and other important characteristics of the models.		
Interacts with	N/A		
Success Criteria	GNN models should enable reproducible and consistent assessment of their performance over time and across different environments.		

Table 42: Evaluate function specification

Data converter function

Function Name	Data converter	Priority	Should
Description	Before realising the inference/training of the model with the data, GNN models should be capable of converting the ENACT data type format received into a format they can work with, such as arrays, in order to execute these functions.		
Interacts with	N/A		
Success Criteria	The component should correctly generate data that is compatible with the ENACT format provided.		

Table 43: Data converter function specification

5.4 Dynamic Graph Modeller (DGM) component

Component Name	Dynamic Graph Modeller		
Intro / Overview	<p>The Dynamic Graph Modeller obtains data from a deployment in the ENACT environment, processes and converts it into a visual graph (edges and nodes). In addition, users can also edit this graph or send it to other tools like GNN to modify it to be more suitable regarding features like better latency, power efficiency, etc.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Data Requester is the entry point of data to feed the component, it gather the info of the rest of the components and prepares it to be transferred to the Graph Modeller component. • The Graph Modeller is in charge of convert the entry data into a graph structure of nodes and edges. • The Graph Visualiser represents the graph data structures providing a graphical way to ENACT operators. 		
Extracted Modules	N/A		
Component Workflow	<p>To depict the ENACT Dynamic Graph Modeller workflow, a diagram has been used to represent the interaction between internal components.</p> <pre> graph LR subgraph DC [] direction TB TDC[Telemetry Data Collector] O[Orchestrator] end DR[Data Requester] GM[Graph Modeller] GV[Graph Visualizer] subgraph AF [] direction TB AF[AI Forecaster] end DC --> DR DR -- "Raw Data" --> GM GM -- "Graph Data" --> GV GM --> AF </pre>		
External Component Interaction	<p>The Dynamic Graph Modeller had a series of connectors that are used to interact with other components in the ENACT environment. The components that provide data to the DGM are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine • Orchestrator <p>The components that receive data from the DGM are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI Forecaster • Security Risk Modeller 		

Prototypical Mock-ups

Home Page: This is the first page users will see once they open the tool. On the left side there is the menu in which there are two main options:

- Deployment graph
- Risk modeller graph

Deployment graph option: The following image shows the graph tab. In this tab, the user can see the current graph of their deployment.

Risk Modeller graph option: This option represents or shows the info provided by the Risk Modeller component. The GUI of the Risk Modeller component is probably going to be embedded in the Graph Modeller.

TRL

Current: TRL-2
Expected: TRL-5

Potential Use-cases Layer

Applicable in all pilot scenarios

- ENACT Modelling Layer

Technologies

The Dynamic Graph Modeller is powered by the following technologies:

Programming languages:

- Python

Interfaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Typescript <p>Frameworks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Node.js: a cross-platform, open-source JavaScript runtime environment <p>Libraries:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networkx¹⁴⁸: Python package for the creation, manipulation, and study of the structure, dynamics, and functions of complex networks. • Sigma.js¹⁴⁹: JavaScript library aimed at visualising graphs of thousands of nodes and edges
	<p>Data Requester Interface:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: The Data Requester is in charge of gathering (requesting) all the info from the Telemetry Data Collector& Monitoring Engine and Orchestrator. • Type: REST API • State: Synchronous • Data Format: JSON <p>Graph Modeller Interface:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: The Graph Modeller receives the data of the system structured as a graph and represents it in a visual way. • Type: REST API • State: Synchronous • Data Format: GEXF, GRAPHML (graph formats)
Deployment Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Software as a Service • Docker Containers • Helm Chart <p>The deployment form of the Dynamic Graph Modeller will be a containerised solution in Docker that can be easily deployed in a Kubernetes environment with the use of Helm. The solution will be packaged as a Helm chart and will be ready to deploy by the Kubernetes orchestrator.</p>
Authorisation Definition	<p>Authorisation for accessing the ENACT Dynamic Graph Modeller will be facilitated through a RESTful API, with authentication being provided and validated by the ENACT Security and User Management system. Upon successful authentication, the API will enforce authorisation rules to determine whether the authenticated user has the necessary permissions to access the DGM.</p>
Licence	<p>Apache 2.0</p>

Table 44: Dynamic Graph Modeller Component specification

Data Requester function

Function Name	Data Requester	Priority	Should
Description	This function enables requesting and interacting with the components responsible for gathering the information about the actual state of the deployment (Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine and Orchestrator) and prepare and sending it to the Graph Modeller Function.		

¹⁴⁸ <https://networkx.org/>

¹⁴⁹ <https://www.sigmajavascript.org/>

Interacts with	
Success Criteria	The Data Requester should be able to request and receive all the data related to a deployment in the ENACT environment.

Table 45: Data Requester function specification

Graph Modeller function

Function Name	Graph Modeller	Priority	Must
Description	This function receives the raw data of a deployment as input and converts it into a graph format as output.		
Interacts with			
Success Criteria	The function is able to convert raw data from a deployment in a graph format compatible with the Graph Control Panel function (.GEXF or .GRAPHML).		

Table 46: Graph Modeller function specification

Graph Visualiser function

Function Name	Graph Visualiser	Priority	Must
Description	This function represents the graph data in a graphical way.		
Interacts with			
Success Criteria	Represent correctly the graph data info gathered converted into a graph in as output in the Graph Modeller function.		

Table 47: Graph Visualiser function specification

5.5 CCC Models

The CCC Models are not an actual ENACT component but rather a set of data models that facilitate interoperability among other ENACT platform components. In this section, they are presented following the templates established for the definition of components and modules.

Component Name	CCC Models
Intro / Overview	The models provide a rich semantic representation of the concepts for the overall description of Service/Application, Resource/Device and Telemetry data, in the context of

Extracted Modules	<p>dynamic heterogeneous complex distributed systems. The models will be used for internal communication of the relevant ENACT components as well as for the definition of high-level Service/Application deployment requirements, the specification of infrastructure Resource/Device characteristics and capabilities, and the collection and storage of Telemetry data for various purposes.</p>
Component Workflow	<p>The term “modules” is not relevant in the case of the CCC Models. However, they include three main sub-models:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application / Service Model • Resource / Device Model • Telemetry Data Model
External Component Interaction	<p>The CCC Models are not a tangible component, but rather a collection of data models utilised by other ENACT components for interoperability / communication and data storage purposes. As such, no specific workflows can be presented here; however the CCC Models are utilised in the background within the workflows of other ENACT components and their interactions with each other.</p> <p>The CCC Models are utilised by the following ENACT components:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • API for application deployment: This is not an ENACT component, but it is shown in architecture diagram. As far as the CCC Models are concerned, this is relevant as far as the specification of the application characteristics and high-level deployment requirements / goals of the application are concerned (e.g., low latency, GDPR-compliance, etc.). • Dynamic Graph Modeller • Orchestrator • AI Forecaster • Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine • Data Manager • APM • Application Controller • Application Policy Model
Prototypical Mock-ups	<p><i>Not applicable.</i></p>
TRL	<p>Current TRL: 3 Expected TRL: 5</p>
Potential Use-cases Layer	<p>Applicable in all pilot scenarios</p> <p>The CCC Models are utilised at various ENACT layers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ENACT Modelling Layer • ENACT Cognitive Computing Orchestration Layer • ENACT AI Layer • ENACT Data Layer • ENACT Physical Layer • ENACT App Development Layer
Technologies	<p>The ENACT CCC Models will be powered by the following technologies and standards, as required:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OASIS Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications (TOSCA) • Resource Description Framework (RDF) • Unified Modelling Language (UML) • Workflow Description Language (OpenWDL) • YAML Ain't Markup Language (YAML) • Extensible Markup Language (XML) • JavaScript Object Notation (JSON)

Interfaces	<i>Not applicable.</i>
Deployment Type	<i>Not applicable.</i>
Authorisation	<i>Not applicable.</i>
Definition	
Licence	Apache 2.0 or MIT

Table 48: CCC Models specification

5.5.1 Application/ Service Model

Module Name	Application / Service Model	Priority	Must
Description	The Application / Service Model includes the parameters that can be used for the high-level description of an application to be deployed to the ENACT Continuum, along with its characteristics and the user-set deployment objectives / goals. Based on these parameters, the application deployment can be optimised by the ENACT platform mechanisms. The Application/Service model includes parameters such as the application usage demand, service level (e.g., reliability, accuracy), application performance (e.g., total execution time, response latency, hardware acceleration and its type, parallelisation), data storage and data transfer, network, security and privacy (e.g. encryption, legal framework), energy consumption, deployment cost, timeframe, in-depth technical details (e.g., programming language, execution environment), etc.		
Interacts with	The Application / service model is to be utilised by the following ENACT components: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • API for application deployment • AI Forecaster • APM • Application Controller • Application Policy Model 		
Extracted Functions	<i>Not applicable.</i>		
Success Criteria	The model should enable the adequate description of the parameters of interest of each particular application / service and the requirements that they should satisfy, in order to facilitate their optimal deployment and execution in the ENACT Continuum. The relevant ENACT components should utilise the developed data models for exchanging data and interacting with each other successfully.		

Table 49: Application / service model specification

5.5.2 Resource/ Device Model

Module Name	Resource / Device Model	Priority	Must
Description	The Resource / Device Abstraction model can be utilised for representing the hardware and software resources that will be part of the ENACT Continuum along with their detailed characteristics and attributes. The model is extensible and the entities can be extended to incorporate new hardware types in the future. A hardware resource (Node) can have various attributes (e.g., CPU, Memory, Network, Storage), execution capabilities (e.g., trusted execution enclaves, vector extensions, streaming extensions, software extensions) and one or more attached resources (e.g., GPUs, FPGAs, SmartNICs). A software resource aggregates and handles multiple hardware resources with different capabilities and offers functional facilities on top (e.g., storage service, execution service).		
Interacts with	The Resource / device model is to be utilised by the following ENACT components: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dynamic Graph Modeller • Orchestrator 		

Extracted Functions Success Criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI Forecaster • Application Controller • Application Policy Model
	<i>Not applicable.</i>
	The elements of the Resource / Device Model should enable the efficient expression of all the resources linked to the ENACT platform and their characteristics. The resource parameters captured by the model can be utilised by the relevant ENACT components and orchestration mechanisms for optimal deployment of applications to the ENACT Continuum.

Table 50: Resource / device model specification

5.5.3 Telemetry Data Model

Module Name	Telemetry Data Model	Priority	Must
Description	The Telemetry Data Model captures the infrastructure runtime measurements of the various resources and components that comprise the ENACT Continuum. Its aim is to adequately describe the state of the hardware and software components available for allocation and usage. It builds on time series streams that refer to the current state of the hardware and low-level software resources available, and covers various telemetry information categories, such as compute, memory, disk, network and hardware. For each of the categories more in-depth metrics are provided that describe the current state of the infrastructure and enable the ENACT platform components to act on various resources, as required.		
Interacts with	The Telemetry Data Model is to be utilised by the following ENACT components: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dynamic Graph Modeller • Orchestrator • AI Forecaster • Application Controller • Application Policy Model • Data Manager 		
Extracted Functions	<i>Not applicable.</i>		
Success Criteria	The elements of the Telemetry Data Model should facilitate the sharing and potentially the storage of telemetry data from all the resources linked with the ENACT platform in a predefined format. The historical telemetry data should be linkable to particular services characteristics and cover their whole lifecycle. The telemetry parameters captured by the model can be utilised by the relevant ENACT components and orchestration mechanisms for optimal deployment of applications to the ENACT Continuum.		

Table 51: Telemetry data model specification

5.6 Data Access and Sharing Interfaces component

Component Name	Data Access and Sharing Interfaces
Intro / Overview	The Data Access and Sharing Interfaces will provide mechanisms for accessing and retrieving data stored in the distributed data sources. They include data connectors and APIs, to enable other components and applications to interact with the distributed data store and perform read and write operations.
Extracted Modules	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • APIs

Component Workflow

- Data Connectors

There are no internal interactions; legacy APIs and Data Connectors are used for forwarding read/write requests of and transferring data to other ENACT components

External Component Interaction

External components interact with the Data Access & Sharing Interfaces by making API calls to either dedicated endpoints or a connector’s interface. These API calls serve various purposes, including:

- Requests to read or write telemetry data or resource data
- AI training logs and datasets
- Requests to read health monitoring logs

Overall, these interfaces act as an intermediary between the Data Layer and the ENACT platform. All project components and applications aiming to share, store and/or consume (mainly historical) data should be able to interact with distributed data space. We currently consider that the ENACT Data Space communicates with:

1. The Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine to record the collected telemetry data.
2. The Virtual Training Environment, which retrieves datasets to be used for AI training.
3. The Application Controller to provide it with telemetry, but also access tokens and health logs and diagnostics.

Prototypical Mock-ups

In the case of communicating through the connector, the latter determines the access to data based on pre-specified data usage policies. Once a request is received, it is forwarded to the Data Manager for further processing.

For authorised data read requests, the relevant data is sent back to the requester. If the request involves telemetry data, matching stored data, but also relevant access tokens, are sent to the Application Controller. Health logs and alerts might also be requested and delivered to the Application Controller. For requests coming from VTE for data for AI training, the appropriate datasets are returned from the respective data store to VTE.

The Data Layer is not expected to have a UI. Some of the available UIs from available data connectors. Some examples:

**TRL
Potential Use-cases
Layer
Technologies**

Expected TRL: 9

In all three pilot cases, while general data transfer can be considered regarding historical data

ENACT Data Layer

- REST APIs
- gRPC APIs (optional)
- Eclipse Data Space Connectors¹⁵⁰. The Data Connectors are built upon:
 - JSON-LD¹⁵¹ for connecting Linked Data

¹⁵⁰ <https://github.com/eclipse-edc/Connector/tree/main/>

¹⁵¹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/json-ld11/>

Interfaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ DCAT¹⁵² to enable interoperability between data catalogues ○ Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL)¹⁵³ to define policies
	<p>API Interfaces:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: Used for the communication between the ENACT Data layer and external ENACT components • Type: REST API • State: Synchronous • Data Format: JSON <p>Data Connector Interfaces:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: Used for the communication between the ENACT Data layer and external ENACT components • Type: Eclipse Dataspace Protocol • State: Synchronous • Data Format: JSON
Deployment Type	Software
Authorisation Definition	Data space connectors may can help to setup some data access/sharing mechanisms and to define the data usage policies.
Licence	Apache License 2.0

Table 52: Data Access and Sharing Interfaces Component specification

5.6.1 APIs module

Module Name	APIs	Priority	Must
Description	API endpoints for communication between the ENACT Data layer and external ENACT components		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other Data Access and Sharing Interfaces • Data Manager • Telemetry Data Connector • VTE • Application Controller 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Read Data • Write Data 		
Success Criteria	Satisfies authorised read/write requests. Returns data expressed as indicated by the ENACT CCC models.		

Table 53: API's module specification

Read Data function

Function Name	Read Data	Priority	Must
Description	To allow retrieving data (telemetry, health logs and datasets for AI training) from the ENACT data store.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other Data Access and Sharing Interfaces • Data Manager • Telemetry Data Connector • VTE • Application controller 		

¹⁵² <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/>

¹⁵³ <https://w3c.github.io/poe/model/>

Success Criteria Other components are able to retrieve stored data.

Table 54: Read Data function specification

Write Data function

Function Name	Write Data	Priority	Must
Description	To allow recording data (telemetry, health logs and datasets for AI training) in the ENACT data store.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other Data Access and Sharing Interfaces • Data Manager • Telemetry Data Connector • VTE • Application controller 		
Success Criteria	Relevant (historical) data are stored in the ENACT data store.		

Table 55: Write Data function specification

5.6.2 Data Connector module

Module Name	Data Connectors	Priority	Must
Description	Data Connectors for communication between ENACT Data layer and external ENACT components.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other Data Access and Sharing Interfaces • Data Manager • Telemetry Data Connector • VTE • Application Controller 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Read Data • Write Data 		
Success Criteria	Satisfies authorised read/write requests based on predefined data usage policies. Returns data expressed as indicated by the ENACT CCC models.		

Table 56: Data Connector module specification

Read Data function

Function Name	Read Data	Priority	Must
Description	To allow retrieving data (telemetry, health logs and datasets for AI training) from the ENACT data store.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other Data Access and Sharing Interfaces • Data Manager • Telemetry Data Connector • VTE • Application controller 		
Success Criteria	Only authorised parties are able to retrieve stored data without violating the predefined data usage policies.		

Table 57: Read Data function specification

Write Data function

Function Name	Write Data	Priority	Must
Description	To allow recording data (telemetry, health logs and datasets for AI training) in the ENACT		

Interacts with	data store. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Other Data Access and Sharing Interfaces Data Manager Telemetry Data Connector VTE Application controller
Success Criteria	Relevant (historical) data sent by authorised parties are stored in the ENACT data store.

Table 58: Write Data function specification

5.7 Data Manager component

Component Name	Data Manager
Intro / Overview	<p>A distributed data store/space for the whole computing continuum. ENACT will adopt data sovereignty and governance principles as they are derived from leading initiatives like IDSA, GAIAx, etc. Therefore, the component will provide distributed storage services by including subcomponents like Data Connectors for sovereign data sharing among different parties. In particular, the ENACT Data Manager will consist of the following subcomponents:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Data Stores which will reside in nodes/devices distributed across the continuum 2. The Metadata Manager which handles the metadata, including data location, attributes, access permissions, etc. <p>In addition, ENACT endeavours to provide two auxiliary subcomponents as well, namely:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Monitoring Services to keep track of the Distributed Data Storage performance, monitor its health and provide associated alerts and diagnostics • The Security and Access Control Manager for identity and access management <p>Moreover, ENACT will try to move a step further on data sharing and storage, by supporting an innovative sharing of objects between the applications in the CCC.</p>
Extracted Modules	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Store(s) Metadata Manager Monitoring Services (optional) Security and Access Control (optional)
Component Workflow	The following diagram illustrates the interactions and workflow between the ENACT Data Manager modules.

First, the request is directed to the Security and Access Control Manager. This manager is responsible for verifying the requesting entities' credentials and determining whether they are authorised to perform actions such as reading stored data, writing new data, or obtaining monitoring logs. Authorisation logs are generated and sent back to the applications. Additionally, to ensure that data is securely stored it may apply encryption techniques.

If a data read/write request is authorised, the request is forwarded to the Metadata Manager. In case of write requests, the Metadata Manager enriches the data or objects to be stored with proper indices indicating their source, attributes, etc. Subsequently, the data is distributed and securely stored in the data store.

For authorised data read requests, the relevant data is sent back to the requester. If the request involves historical telemetry data, the stored data is filtered to retrieve the matching data from the data store wherein they reside. For requests involving data for AI training, the appropriate datasets are fetched from the respective data store. Telemetry and AI training data pass through the metadata manager.

If access to health logs is authorised, the request is forwarded to the Monitoring Services, which generate health logs and alerts.

External Component Interaction

The Data Manager interacts with the ENACT platform via the Data Access & Sharing Interfaces of the Data Layer.

Prototypical Mock-ups

There is not any UI expected to be developed for the Data Manager.

TRL

Expected TRL: 5

Potential Use-cases

In all three pilot cases, while general data transfer can be considered regarding historical data.

Layer

ENACT Data Layer

Technologies	<p>The technologies being considered currently for the implementation of the Distributed Data Space include:</p> <p>For the Data Store:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elastic Search¹⁵⁴ to enable distributed data storing and search <p>For the Metadata manager:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elastic Search to enable distributed metadata mapping and search <p>For the Security & Access Control Manager:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Keycloak¹⁵⁵ framework for identity and access management • OpenID Connect • OAuth 2.0 • SAML 2.0 <p>For the Monitoring Services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prometheus for performance monitoring <p>Moreover, technologies such as Docker and Node.js for component containerisation and the deployment of the Distributed Data Storage across the ENACT continuum nodes will be utilised.</p> <p>The aforementioned technologies and frameworks utilise various programming languages, including Javascript, SQL and ODRL.</p>
Interfaces	<p>Data Store Interfaces:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: Used for the execution of CRUD operations • Type: REST API • State: Synchronous • Data Format: JSON <p>Metadata Manager Interfaces:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: Used for the execution of data/metadata write operations • Type: REST API • State: Synchronous • Data Format: JSON <p>Security & Access Control Manager Interfaces:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: Used for handling the authentication and access requests, and forwarding of CRUD requests • Type: REST API • State: Synchronous • Data Format: JSON <p>Monitoring Services Interfaces:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: Used for the execution of health logs read requests • Type: REST API • State: Synchronous • Data Format: JSON
Deployment Type	Software – Containerisation approach will be used for the packaging and deployment of various components of ENACT Data Store/Space.
Authorisation Definition	Access granted based on predefined authentication/authorisation rules.

¹⁵⁴ <https://www.elastic.co/elasticsearch/>

¹⁵⁵ <https://www.keycloak.org/>

Licence Apache License 2.0

Table 59: Data Manager Component specification
5.7.1 Data Store module

Module Name	Data Store	Priority	Must
Description	Individual computing devices, servers, etc. that store and manage data in the distributed system (or in CCC)		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Stores residing in other Nodes Metadata Manager 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Storage Data Retrieval 		
Success Criteria	Availability (to support data storage and retrieval), connection with other components		

Table 60: Data Store module specification
Data Storage function

Function Name	Data Storage	Priority	Must
Description	Pertains to storing telemetry and resource data, as well as data/models for AI training.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Management Data Retrieval 		
Success Criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stored data must be expressed as indicated by the ENACT CC models. Data stores distributed across different nodes should be synchronised. 		

Table 61: Data Storage functional specification
Data Retrieval function

Function Name	Data Retrieval	Priority	Must
Description	Returns requested data.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Storage Data Retrieval 		
Success Criteria	Returned data must be expressed as indicated by the ENACT CC models.		

Table 62: Data Retrieval function specification

5.7.2 Metadata Manager module

Module Name	Metadata Manager	Priority	Must
Description	It provides indexing/de-indexing of data and filters stored metadata to retrieve matching data from the corresponding data store to satisfy read requests.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Store • Security and Access Control Manager • Data Access and Sharing Interfaces 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Indexing • Filtering • Data de-indexing 		
Success Criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metadata stored and retrieved by communication interfaces. • Stored metadata linked to data/objects. • Metadata are expressed as indicated by the ENACT CC models. 		

For the sake of comprehensibility, telemetry data and AI training-related data transfers are represented by bi-directional arrows. However, the exact workflow is as follows:

- For writing requests, data are indexed to include metadata and then stored in data store(s).
- For authorised read requests, data are filtered to be retrieved from the relevant data store(s) and then de-indexed before returned to Data Access & Sharing Interfaces.

Table 63: Metadata Manager module specification

Data Indexing function

Function Name	Data Indexing	Priority	Must
Description	It provides indexing of data prior to storing, to include metadata information such as data objects, their location, attributes, access permissions, etc.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Storage • Data Access & Sharing Interfaces 		

Table 64: Data Indexing functional specification

Data Filtering function

Table 65: Data Filtering function specification

Data De-indexing function

Table 66: Data De-indexing functional specification

5.7.3 Security & Access Control module

Table 67: Security & Access Control module specification

Identity Verification function

Function Name	Identity Verification	Priority	Should
Description	It supports verification of credentials.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Access & Sharing Interfaces • Monitoring Services • Data Indexing • Data Filtering 		
Success Criteria	Authentication mechanisms are in place.		

Table 68: Identity Verification functional specification
Access Control function

Function Name	Access Control	Priority	Should
Description	It supports the definition and enforcement of access control policies.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Access & Sharing Interfaces • Monitoring Services • Data Indexing • Data Filtering 		

Success Criteria Access is restricted to authorised parties.

Table 69: Access Control function specification

5.7.4 Monitoring Services module

Module Name	Monitoring Services	Priority	Nice to have
Description	Monitoring services to provide visibility over the distributed storage system's performance, health, and utilisation. Services will include logging, alerting, and diagnostic functionalities.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Security and Access Control Manager • Data Access and Sharing Interfaces 		
Extracted Functions	Currently none.		
Success Criteria	Health logs, alerts and diagnostics provided to applications.		

Table 70: Monitoring Services module specification

5.8 AI forecaster component

Component Name	AI Forecaster
Intro / Overview	<p>This tool harnesses the power of AI algorithms to efficiently forecast network data and propose a plan to allocate computing resources across the continuum for future timesteps taking into consideration the network QoS.</p> <p>The component is composed of 3 modules:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Data analysis module is responsible for analysing and preprocess network data from the network environment. • The AI forecasting module is the core engine of the component, aiming to provide a forecast of the network based on application demands, security concerns and network changes to the GNN and DRL to obtain the optimised forecasted schedule • The Data exchange module is responsible for handling the data throughput from/to the AI Forecaster component.
Extracted Modules	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data analysis module • AI forecasting module • Data exchange module
Component	The following diagram illustrates the internal workflow and the communication between

Workflow

the modules.

External Component Interaction

The figure below describes the component interactions with its connected components of the ENACT platform.

Prototypical Mock-ups
TRL

This component is operating as a backend component. No UIs are going to be created.

Current: TRL-2
Expected: TRL-5

Potential Use-cases
Layer

Applicable in all pilot scenarios
ENACT Cognitive Computing Orchestration Layer

Technologies
Interfaces

Python Programming Language, PyTorch, TensorFlow, FLASK REST API, FLASK webSockets

- **Overview:** Interface to exchange data with other components
- **Type:** e.g. REST/WebSockets
- **State:** Synchronous or asynchronous
- **Data Format:** JSON

Deployment Type
Authorisation

Either as a Docker container or K8S pod.

Authorisation will be implemented through SSL WebSocket's APIs

Definition	
Licence	Contact CERTH for using the software.

Table 71: AI Forecaster Component specification

5.8.1 Data Analysis module

Module Name	Data Analysis	Priority	Must
Description	The module is responsible for analysing and preprocess network data from the network environment.		
Interacts with	AI forecasting module		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> processData 		
Success Criteria	All module functions have been evaluated to be successful from their success criteria defined in unit tests.		

Table 72: Data Analysis module specification

ProcessData function

Function Name	ProcessData	Priority	Must
Description	This function obtains the data from the external components namely: DRL,GNN,VTE and Graph Modeller and applies preprocessing based on the AI forecaster internal requirements.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> GetData ProcessInput RunForecast 		
Success Criteria	Successfully process data and deliver them to the AI Forecasting module of the AI Forecaster component based on the defined unit tests.		

Table 73: ProcessData function specification

5.8.2 AI Forecaster module

Module Name	AI Forecasting	Priority	Must
Description	The module is the core engine of the component, aiming to provide the forecasted network based on application demands, security concerns and network changes to the GNN and DRL to obtain the optimised forecasted schedule.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data analysis module Data exchange module 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> RunForecast ProcessInput 		
Success Criteria	All Module functions have been evaluated to be successful from their success criteria.		

Table 74: AI Forecaster module specification

RunForecast function

Function Name	RunForecast	Priority	Must
Description	This function is triggered to forecast the needs in telemetry data for a specific future time step.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Process Data Process input SendData 		

Success Criteria	Pass the unit tests defined for this function.
-------------------------	--

Table 75: RunForecast function specification

ProcessInput function

Function Name	ProcessInput	Priority	Should
Description	Obtain the data preprocessed by the processData function and deliver them to the runForecast function.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RunForecast • ProcessData 		
Success Criteria	Pass the unit tests defined for this function.		

Table 76: ProcessingInput function specification

5.8.3 Data Exchange module

Module Name	Data Exchange	Priority	Must
Description	The module is responsible for handling the data throughput from/to the AI Forecaster component.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DRL • Graph Modeller • GNN • VTE 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GetData • SendData 		
Success Criteria	All Module functions have been evaluated to be successful from their success criteria.		

Table 77: Data Exchange module specification

GetData function

Function Name	GetData	Priority	Must
Description	This function obtains the data from the external components and moves them to the ProcessData function.		
Interacts with	ProcessData		
Success Criteria	Pass the unit tests defined for this function.		

Table 78: GetData function specification

SendData function

Function Name	SendData	Priority	Must
Description	This function delivers the output of the RunForecast function to the external components.		
Interacts with	RunForecast		
Success Criteria	Pass the unit tests defined for this function.		

Table 79: SendData function specification

5.9 Deep Reinforced Learning (DRL) Agent component

Component Name	Deep Reinforcement Learning Agent		
Intro / Overview	This component harnesses the power of AI Reinforcement learning to efficiently optimise the placement of application demands within the network infrastructure.		

Extracted Modules

The component is composed of 3 modules:

- The **Data analysis** module is responsible to analyse and preprocess network data from the network environment.
- The **AI scheduling** module is the core engine of the component, aiming to provide the optimised schedule for the application needs.
- The **Data exchange** module is responsible to handle the data throughput from/to the DRL agent component.

- Data Analysis module
- AI Scheduling module
- Data Exchange module

Component Workflow

The following diagram illustrates the internal workflow and the communication between the modules.

External Component Interaction

The figure below describes the component interactions with its connected components of the ENACT platform.

Prototypical Mock-ups
TRL

This component is operating as a backend component. No UIs are going to be created.

Current: TRL-2
Expected: TRL-5

Potential Use-cases
Layer

Applicable in all pilot scenarios
ENACT Cognitive Computing Orchestration Layer

Technologies
Interfaces

Python Programming Language, PyTorch, TensorFlow, FLASK REST API, FLASK webSockets

- **Overview:** Interface to exchange data with other components
- **Type:** e.g. REST/WebSockets

Deployment Type Authorisation Definition Licence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • State: Synchronous or asynchronous • Data Format: JSON
	Either as a Docker container or K8S pod.
	Authorisation will be implemented through SSL WebSocket's APIs.
	Contact CERTH for using the software.

Table 80: Deep Reinforced Learning Component specification

5.9.1 Data Analysis module

Module Name	Data Analysis	Priority	Must
Description	The module is responsible to analyse and preprocess network data from the network environment.		
Interacts with	AI Scheduler		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ProcessData 		
Success Criteria	All module functions have been evaluated to be successful from their success criteria		

Table 81: Data Analysis module specification

ProcessData function

Function Name	ProcessData	Priority	Must
Description	This function obtains the data process them and forwards them to the AI scheduling module.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RunOptim • ProcessInput • GetData 		
Success Criteria	Pass the unit tests defined for this function.		

Table 82: ProcessData function specification

5.9.2 AI Scheduler module

Module Name	AI Scheduler	Priority	Must
Description	The module is the core engine of the component, aiming to provide the optimised schedule for the application needs.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Analysis module • Data Exchange module 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RunOptim • ProcessInput 		
Success Criteria	All Module functions have been evaluated to be successful from their success criteria.		

Table 83: AI Scheduler module specification

RunOptim function

Function Name	RunOptim	Priority	Must
Description	This function executes the RL agent to calculate the optimal schedule		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ProcessInput • SendData • ProcessData 		

Success Criteria	Pass the unit tests defined for this function.
-------------------------	--

Table 84: RunOptim function specification

ProcessInput function

Function Name	ProcessingInput	Priority	Should
Description	This function takes the preprocessed data and forwards them to the RunOptim function.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ProcessData • RunOptim 		
Success Criteria	Describes the minimal criteria, which the implementation should fulfil, related to the requirements of D2.1.		

Table 85: ProcessInput function specification

5.9.3 Data Exchange module

Module Name	Data Exchange	Priority	Must
Description	The module is responsible to handle the data throughput from/to the AI Forecaster component.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AIForecaster • Orchestrator • Security Risk Modeller 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GetData • SendData 		
Success Criteria	All Module functions have been evaluated to be successful from their success criteria.		

Table 86: Data Exchange module specification

GetData function

Function Name	GetData.	Priority	Must
Description	This function obtains the data from the external components and moves them to the ProcessData function.		
Interacts with	ProcessData		
Success Criteria	Pass the unit tests defined for this function.		

Table 87: GetData function specification

SendData function

Function Name	SendData	Priority	Must
Description	This function delivers the output of the RunForecast function to the external components.		
Interacts with	RunForecast		
Success Criteria	Pass the unit tests defined for this function.		

Table 88: SendData function specification

5.10 Orchestrator component

Component Name	Orchestrator
Intro / Overview	The Orchestrator component is responsible for executing the deployment orders requested by the AI Layer (ENACT component DRL), that will give direct instructions about which mapping should be enforced between applications and clusters resources (Deployment Plans). A best effort will be performed to satisfy the mapping with the nodes

and resources available. If a mapping cannot be satisfied due to unavailability of resources, then new deployment plans will be requested to the AI Layer.

The Orchestrator will be able to perform deployments over a heterogeneous range of nodes in the edge-cloud continuum, abstracting the technological details related to the deployment.

The Orchestrator will also maintain an updated view of the deployment of all the applications over the cluster(s), combining consumption of resources with detailed information about the physical nodes where each component of each application is deployed (or are scheduled for deployment).

The Orchestrator main functions are:

- Receiving deployment plans from the DRL component and converting these instructions to be executed by the Orchestrator.
- Monitor applications deployment over clusters.
- Handle requests from the application controller including rescheduling plans or stopping/disabling pods.
- Request new deployment plans if needed.

Extracted Modules
Component
Workflow

N/A

Inside the Orchestrator component, the flow of information should be as follows:

External Component Interaction	<p>The diagram illustrates the ENACT Orchestrator's interactions across four layers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Modelling Layer: Contains the Graph Modeler, which sends 'Request new deployment plans / Cluster Deployment Information' to the Orchestrator. AI Layer: Contains the DRL (Deep Reinforcement Learning) component, which sends 'Deployment Plans' to the Orchestrator. App Development Layer: Contains the Application Controller, which sends 'Request/Response feedback on Application Actions' to the Orchestrator. Orchestration Layer: Contains the Telemetry data collector and ZTP Service. The Telemetry data collector sends 'Network/Application metrics, status reports, alerts' to the Orchestrator. The ZTP Service sends 'Resource descriptions / configurations' to the Orchestrator.
Prototypical Mock-ups	N/A
TRL	Current: TRL-2 Expected: TRL-6
Potential Use-cases	Applicable in all pilot scenarios
Layer Technologies	ENACT Orchestration Layer The Orchestrator component is composed by the following technologies: Programming Languages: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Go • JavaScript Frameworks: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kubernetes: Automation of deployment, auto scaling and management of containerised applications. • Docker: Build applications and run them in multiple containers, with a shared image. • KubeEdge: Extends orchestration and deployment capabilities to the edge.
Interfaces	TDCME Interface: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: Interface to retrieve metric data from Telemetry Data Collection & Monitoring Engine • Type: MQTT • State: Synchronous • Data Format: JSON ZTP Interface: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: Interface to exchange device information and configurations between Orchestrator and ZTP component • Type: REST API • State: Synchronous • Data Format: JSON DRL Interface: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: Interface to receive deployment plans from the DRL component

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Type: REST API State: Synchronous Data Format: JSON <p>Application Controller Interface:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overview: Interface to receive optimisation requests/deployment feedback from the Application Controller Type: REST API State: Synchronous Data Format: JSON <p>Graph Modeller Interface:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overview: Interface to provide information about the cluster state to the Graph Modeller and to request new deployment plans Type: REST API State: Synchronous Data Format: JSON
Deployment Type	Docker Containers (The Orchestrator in its own pod will run alongside the other containers).
Authorisation Definition	To send information and to request data from the Orchestrator, the other components must be authenticated prior to the operation and be authorised to handle these.
Licence	MIT license

Table 89: Orchestrator component specification

Application Manager Handler function

	Application Manager Handler	Priority	Must
Description	<p>This function handles the requests/feedback that deployed Application Controllers send to the Orchestrator. Those requests may include moving application components to other cluster nodes (e.g. to reduce communication delays or due to node performance degradation), requesting for more resources or asking the Orchestrator to activate/deactivated specific application components that are not being used (e.g. to optimise energy consumption).</p> <p>After the request from an Application Controller is analysed, an internal request is sent to the Deployment Plan Handler to ask for changes in the deployment to the Application Components.</p>		
Interacts with	<pre> graph TD AC[Application Controller] -- "Request/Response feedback on Application Actions" --> AMH[Application Manager Handler] AMH -- "Deployment / Redeployment Requests" --> DPH[Deployment Plan Handler] style AMH stroke:#f00,stroke-width:2px </pre>		

Success Criteria	The Application Manager Handler should be able to collect incoming requests from an Application Controller and redirect them to the Deployment Plan Handler for execution of the orders.
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Table 90: Application Manager Handler function specification

Deployment Plan Handler function

Function Name	Deployment Plan Handler	Priority	Must
Description	<p>The Deployment Plan Handler (DPH) function will receive deployment information from the DRL and deployment-change requests from the Application Manager Handler.</p> <p>When deployment plans are received from the DRL, they are validated and transformed, generating deployment descriptions aligned with the technologies used/understood by the cluster. Those deployment descriptions may be autocompleted with deployment-specific information, required for a more precise deployment instruction. The processed data is then sent to the scheduler, ready for execution.</p> <p>Requests to update Application deployments originated from the Application Manager Handler are also processed in this function. Based on the information received, the Orchestrator may decide to adjust the implementation of the deployment plans. However, if the requests of an Application Controller require significant changes to the application deployment that impact the implementation of the Optimal Deployment plan provided by the DRL, then new deployment plans will be requested from the Graph Controller.</p>		
Interacts with	<pre> graph TD DPH((Deployment Plan Handler)) DRL[DRL] -- Deployment Plans --> DPH AMH[Application Manager Handler] -- Deployment / Redeployment Requests --> DPH DPH -- Resource Description --> DM[Deployment Monitoring] DPH -- Scheduler-Ready Information --> S[Scheduler] S -- Request new deployment plans --> GM[Graph Modeller] GM -- Request new deployment plans --> DPH GM --> Arrow[] style Arrow fill:none,stroke:none </pre>		
Success Criteria	The DPH is able to generate valid deployment descriptions base on the Optimal Deployment Plan received from the DRL. Also, DPH is able to adjust deployments based on requests from the Application Manager Handler.		

Table 91: Deployment Plan Handler function specification

Deployment Monitoring function

Function Name	Deployment Monitoring	Priority	Must
Description	As the name implies, the Deployment Monitoring function is responsible for monitoring all the data coming from the cluster/deployment or the data received from the TDCME and ZTP. By combining this information, this function will build a complete view of the cluster state. This cluster is used by the Deployment Plan Handler to complete the Deployment descriptions, and provided to the Dynamic Graph Modeller on request.		
Interacts with	<pre> graph TD TDC[TDC] -- "Network/Application metrics, status reports, alerts" --> DM((Deployment Monitoring)) ZTP[ZTP] -- "Resource descriptions / configurations" --> DM Clusters((Clusters)) -- "Resource Description" --> DM DM -- "Cluster Deployment Information" --> GMod[Graph Modeller] DM -- "Resource Description" --> DPH[Deployment Plan Handler] </pre>		
Success Criteria	This Deployment Monitoring function should be able to create an accurate view of the Cluster State useful the Deployment Plan Handler and Dynamic Graph Modeller.		

Table 92: Deployment Monitoring function specification

Scheduler function

Function Name	Scheduler	Priority	Must
Description	The Scheduler function provides the interface between the Orchestrator and the Cluster, with the role of executing the received deployment orders. As such, the Scheduler will handle the details of the used technology to support the deployment of applications in the Edge-Cloud Continuum and capable of deploying application on heterogeneous systems over multiple clusters.		
Interacts with	<pre> graph TD DPH[Deployment Plan Handler] -- "Scheduler-Ready Information" --> Scheduler((Scheduler)) Scheduler -- "Deployment Specification" --> Clusters((Clusters)) </pre>		

Success Criteria	The Scheduler should be able to handle deployment descriptions, execute them and keep this type of deployment as close as possible to the desired state, considering resource availability, heterogeneity of nodes and application requirements.
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Table 93: Scheduler function specification

5.11 AI Act Compliance Check component

Component Name	AI Act Compliance Check
Intro / Overview	<p>With the introduction of the AI Act, it is important for solution developers to ensure compliance with these acts to avoid potential legal problems and financial repercussions.</p> <p>The AI Act compliance check module is responsible for executing automatic check of the developed application against the AI Act provisions (and potentially other relevant legislation/policies). It will use meta information provided by the application as well as user manuals, descriptions and other relevant documents to, for example, categorise the application (from the AI Act perspective), assess the completeness and the quality of the provided documentation, together with recommendations on the required changes.</p> <p>AI Act compliance check module consist of two modules:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Compliance Logic represents the main method, checking compliance of the solution with the AI Act, leveraging data submitted by the application and the Knowledge base. The module should receive information about the data planned to be used by the application, together with the relevant meta data, and provide assessment from the compliance with the AI Act perspective. • The AI Act Knowledge base in the form of AI model/LLM and supporting RAG features, trained for analysis of the AI Act. The module has to be able to provide/generate answers to questions about the AI act, to assess compliance of an application and, potentially, provide suggestions on how to fix potential issues. <p>Further, through the interaction with the Application controller module, the AI Act Compliance check module will obtain access to the representative data used for training the AI model to assess it from the AI Act perspective as well as make it available in the AI training data sets data space.</p>
Extracted Modules	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ComplianceLogic • AIAct Knowledge Base
Component Workflow	<pre> graph TD subgraph AIActComplianceChecker [AI Act compliance checker] CL[Compliance Logic] <-.-> AIKB[AIAct KnowledgeBase] end AC[Application Controller] <--> CL subgraph ENACT [ENACT Application Development Layer] AC end </pre>

<p>External Component Interaction</p>	<pre> graph TD AC[Application controller] --> AI[AI Act Compliance check] AI --> CF[Compliance feedback] CF --> AC AI --> AM[App type, metadata, documentation + data used training Ai models] AM --> AC </pre>
<p>Prototypical Mock-ups</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>TRL</p>	<p>TRL1 – TRL4</p>
<p>Potential Use-cases</p>	<p>Applicable in all pilot scenarios and main platform developments.</p>
<p>Layer</p>	<p>ENACT Application Development Layer</p>
<p>Technologies</p>	<p>Programming Languages:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • C#/.NET • Python <p>Services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Azure OpenAI: A cloud service that provides access to OpenAI's powerful language models for various applications, such as text generation, translation, and code completion. • Azure AI Search: A cloud search service that enables developers to easily add scalable search capabilities to their applications. • Azure Blob Storage: A cloud object storage solution for storing large amounts of unstructured data, such as text or binary data. • Azure Prompt Flow: A development tool for building, testing, and deploying large language model (LLM) applications with customizable workflows and prompt engineering. <p>Libraries:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NumPy: A library for the Python programming language, adding support for large, multi-dimensional arrays and matrices, along with a large collection of high-level mathematical functions to operate on these arrays. • SciPy: A library for scientific and technical computing. • Pandas: An open-source data analysis and manipulation tool. • Scikit-learn: An opensource library for Machine Learning
<p>Interfaces</p>	<p>Score API Interface</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: This API accepts content information (metadata, content, additional details) as input and returns a determination of whether the content aligns with the AI Act requirements. • Update knowledge database - This API recreates a knowledge base based on newly uploaded documents.

Deployment Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Type: REST API State: Synchronous Data Format: JSON Update knowledge database Interface
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overview: This API recreates a knowledge database based on newly uploaded documents. Type: REST API State: Synchronous Data Format: JSON
Authorisation Definition	TBD. Open-source being considered.
Licence	TBD

Table 94: AI Act Compliance Check Component specification

5.11.1 ComplianceLogic module

Module Name	ComplianceLogic	Priority	Must
Description	The main method, checking compliance of the solution with the AI Act, leveraging data submitted by the application and the Knowledge base.		
Interacts with	Application Controller		
Extracted Functions	TBD		
Success Criteria	The module should receive information about the data planned to be used by the application, together with the relevant metadata, and provide an assessment of compliance with the AI Act perspective.		

Table 95: ComplianceLogic module specification

ComplianceLogicScore function

Function Name	ComplianceLogicScore	Priority	Must
Description	This API will accept content information (metadata, content, additional details) as input and return a decision on whether and to what extent the content complies with the requirements of the AI Act.		
Interacts with	Application Controller		
Success Criteria	The ability to successfully determine the compliance of input data with the AI Act.		

Table 96: AI ComplianceLogicScore function specification

5.11.2 AIActKnowledgeBase module

Module Name	AIActKnowledgeBase	Priority	Must
Description	The AIActKnowledge base in the form of AI model/LLM and supporting RAG features, trained for analysis of the AI Act.		
Interacts with	ComplianceLogic		
Extracted Functions	AIActKnowledgeBaseUpdate		
Success Criteria	The module should receive information about the data planned to be used by the application, together with the relevant metadata, and provide assessment from the		

compliance with the AI Act perspective.

Table 97: AIActKnowledgeBase module specification

AIActKnowledgeBaseUpdate function

Function Name	AIActKnowledgeBaseUpdate	Priority	Must
Description	This REST API function will recreate a knowledge database based on newly uploaded documents. The database is initially created with an initial set of documents		
Interacts with	ComplianceLogic		
Success Criteria	The ability to successfully update local knowledge database		

Table 98: AIActKnowledgeBaseUpdate function specification

5.12 Application Programming Model (APM) component

Component Name	Application Programming Model
Intro / Overview	The APM is a framework comprising languages, libraries, and tools designed to build applications and services with characteristics such as dynamism, adaptation, elasticity, load balancing, replication, portability, identification, secure communication, self-registering, etc. APM abstracts these complexities, providing a set of APIs, high-level objects, and concepts for developers to create and manage distributed applications efficiently.
Extracted Modules	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • APM Data Services • APM Dynamic Querying Layer • APM Abstraction Layer
Component Workflow	<p>APM Data Services offers CRUD operations through APIs for communication with data sources.</p> <p>APM Dynamic Querying Layer supports querying language functionalities for dynamic data interactions.</p> <p>APM Abstraction Layer provides high-level objects and concepts to simplify application development.</p>
External Component Interaction	Should provide / implement functions for all ENACT components to ensure any scenario. Example:

Prototypical Mock-ups

CRUD operation editor:

Data Services Interface: Interface to access CRUD operations and dynamic querying.

Abstraction Layer Interface: High-level coding interface for developers.

Expected: TRL-5

TRL

Potential Use-cases	Applicable to all Use Cases.
Layer	App Development Layer
Technologies	<p>Programming Languages: Python, Java, Markup Language</p> <p>Frameworks: Flask (for REST API), Kubernetes (for container orchestration)</p> <p>Libraries: Prometheus (for monitoring and telemetry), Scikit-learn (for AI/ML algorithms)</p>
Interfaces	<p>APM Data Services API</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Type: REST API State: Synchronous Data Format: JSON <p>APM Dynamic Querying API</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Type: REST API State: Synchronous Data Format: JSON <p>APM Abstraction Layer API</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Type: REST API State: Synchronous Data Format: JSON or YAML or Markup Language
Deployment Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Software as a Service (SaaS) Docker Containers
Authorisation Definition	Authentication and authorisation are managed through the ENACT Security and User Management system (GUI part). Access control policies can be defined to restrict or allow access to specific models and data pipelines.
Licence	Apache License 2.0

Table 99: APM component specification

5.12.1 APM Data Service module

Module Name	APM Data Service	Priority	Must
Description	The APM Data Services module will provide the functions to interact with the Data Layer.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Layer SDK 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High-level APIs List of available data sources 		
Success Criteria	Performance Indicators are registered and Events are generated based on indicator violations.		

Table 100: APM Data Service module specification

High-level function

Function Name	High-Level APIs	Priority	Must
Description	This function will provide the necessary abstraction for interacting with different types of data sources easily and intuitively.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Layer SDK 		
Success Criteria	The function success criteria are provided by the ability to interact with multiple data sources intuitively.		

Table 101: High-level function specification

List of Available Data Sources function

Function Name	List of Available Data Sources	Priority	Must
Description	This function will provide a list of all available data sources that are connected at a given time as well as one for what types of data sources can be connected.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Sources 		
Success Criteria	The ability to provide the list of available connected data sources, as well as the one for available types of data sources, that can be connected.		

Table 102: List of Available Data Sources function specification

5.12.2 APM Dynamic Querying Layer module

Module Name	APM Dynamic Querying Layer	Priority	Must
Description	The APM Dynamic Querying Language module will provide the functions to query and interact with data sources.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Sources 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CRUD Specification 		
Success Criteria	The success criteria of each function are described individually below.		

Table 103: APM Dynamic Querying Layer module specification

CRUD Specification function

Function Name	CRUD Specification	Priority	Must
Description	This function will provide the necessary specification on what should be given to each of the four operations in CRUD so it can function as expected, and be able to interact with the data sources.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Sources 		
Success Criteria	The ability to specify a complete and comprehensive specification of each of the four CRUD operations.		

Table 104: CRUD Specification function specification

5.12.3 APM Abstraction Layer module

Module Name	APM Abstraction Layer	Priority	Must
Description	The APM Abstraction Layer will provide the capability to communicate with various data sources and display a common interface for interacting with all the available data sources and/or with the AI layer.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Sources SDK AI Layer 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Connector Markup UI 		
Success Criteria	The ability to be able to connect and communicate with a specific data source.		

Table 105: Abstraction Layer module specification

Connector function

Function Name	Connector	Priority	Must
Description	This function will provide the connection to a specific data source. For each data source, a connector will need to be specified.		

Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Sources
Success Criteria	The ability to be able to connect and communicate with a specific data source.

Table 106: Connector function specification
Markup UI function

Function Name	Markup UI	Priority	Must
Description	This function will provide a UI that only contains the high-level components necessary for interacting with the connectors and the data sources.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Connector 		
Success Criteria	The ability to be easily interacted with and to communicate successfully with the connectors.		

Table 107: Markup UI function specification

5.13 Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine (TDCME) component

Component Name	Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine
Intro / Overview	The TDCME component is a set of software agents and tools utilised to monitor multi-mode virtualised infrastructures. It aggregates real-time data from distributed nodes deployed at each site and monitors applications Quality indicators and Policies as specified by administrators and users.
Extracted Modules	<p>Policy Monitoring: Policy Module is responsible for monitoring distributed Applications and ensure Policies, as defined by the user/administrator, are not violated.</p> <p>Quality Monitoring: collects infrastructure and application metrics, preprocesses them and distributes them to other authorised entities.</p> <p>Log Exporter: offers infrastructure logs to other components</p> <p>Query Engine: performs intelligent queries on distributed data nodes.</p> <p>Alert module: produces alerts based on policy violations of infrastructure events.</p>
Component Workflow	
External Component Interaction	<p>Orchestration Layer: provides metrics, push events.</p> <p>Data Layer: forward sdata and events for permanent storage or sharing with third parties.</p> <p>Modelling Layer: provides metrics and events to the Graph Modeller.</p>

Prototypical Mock-ups	<pre> graph LR TDCM[Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine] -- "Push metrics, alerts" --> GM[Graph Modeller] TDCM -- "Push metrics, alerts" --> O[Orchestrator] TDCM -- "Push metrics, alerts and store them" --> DAS[Data Access & Sharing Interfaces] </pre>
TRL	Current TRL: 2 Expected TRL: 5
Potential Use-cases	All ENACT UCs
Layer	Orchestration Layer
Technologies	Prometheus, Kubernetes, Cilium, Golang, Python, Elasticsearch
Interfaces	Quality Monitoring Interface: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overview: exposes methods to register/delete/retrieve quality indicators and their values Type: REST State: Synchronous Data Format: JSON Policy Monitoring Interface: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overview: exposes methods to register/delete/retrieve policies monitored Type: REST State: Synchronous Data Format: JSON Alert Monitoring Interface: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overview: exposes methods to export alerts to other components Type: REST State: Synchronous Data Format: JSON
Deployment Type	<i>Helm chart (software)</i>
Authorisation	<i>None</i>
Definition	
Licence	<i>Probably Apache 2.0</i>

Table 108: Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine component specification

5.13.1 Quality Monitoring module

Module Name	Quality Monitoring	Priority	Must
Description	The Quality Monitoring module is responsible for monitoring infrastructure logs and produce events when certain Performance Indicators violate threshold values as defined by the user.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Alert module Query Engine 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Register Quality Indicator Calculate Quality Indicator Retrieve Quality Indicator Remove Quality Indicator 		
Success Criteria	Performance Indicators are registered and Events are generated based on indicator violations.		

Table 109: Quality Monitoring module specification

Register Quality Indicator function

Function Name	Register Quality Indicator	Priority	Nice to have
Description	Provides an API to register a quality indicator for monitoring a distributed application.		
Interacts with	Alert module		
Success Criteria	The quality indicator is registered and alerts are produced successfully.		

Table 110: Register Quality Indicator function specification

Calculate Quality Indicator function

Function Name	Calculate Quality Indicator	Priority	Must
Description	Calculates a quality indicator based on infrastructure metrics.		
Interacts with	This is an internal function.		
Success Criteria	A valid computed value is calculated and temporarily stored.		

Table 111: Calculate Quality Indicator function specification

Retrieve Quality Indicator function

Function Name	Retrieve Quality Indicator	Priority	Must
Description	Returns a list of quality indicators registered or a specific quality indicator value.		
Interacts with	Alert module		
Success Criteria	The value is retrieved and successfully pulled by the Alert module to produce an alert.		

Table 112: Retrieve Quality Indicator function specification

Remove Policy function

Function Name	Remove Policy Function	Priority	Nice to Have
Description	Removes a policy and no longer monitors if violated.		
Interacts with	Alert Module		
Success Criteria	An enforced policy successfully removed and is not longer monitored.		

Table 113: Remove Policy function specification

5.13.2 Policy Monitoring module

Module Name	Policy Monitoring	Priority	Must
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Description	The Policy Monitoring module is responsible for monitoring infrastructure logs and generating events when violation of system or user-defined policies are attempted.
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Alert module Query Engine
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Register Policy Retrieve Policy
Success Criteria	Policies to be monitored are registered and events are generated when a violation is attempted.

Table 114: Policy Monitoring module specification

Register Policy function

Function Name	Register Policy	Priority	Nice to Have
Description	Registers a policy to monitor		
Interacts with	Alert module		
Success Criteria	An enforced policy successfully registered and monitored.		

Table 115: Register Policy function specification

Retrieve Policy function

Function Name	Retrieve Policy	Priority	Nice to Have
Description	Retrieves a list of monitored policies for a given distributed application.		
Interacts with	Alert module		
Success Criteria	Return a list of monitored polices and counters of violation attempts.		

Table 116: Retrieve Policy function specification

Remove Policy function

Function Name	Remove Policy	Priority	Nice to Have
Description	Removes a policy and no longer monitors if violated		
Interacts with	Alert module		
Success Criteria	An enforced policy successfully removed and is no longer monitored.		

Table 117: Remove Policy function specification

5.13.3 Log Exporter module

Module Name	Log Exporter	Priority	Nice to have
Description	The Log exporter offers raw infrastructure logs to other components.		
Interacts with	Alert module		
Extracted Functions	Forward Logs		
Success Criteria	Logs are delivered to registered applications.		

Table 118: Log Exporter module specification

Forward Logs function

Function Name	Forward Logs Function	Priority	Must
Description	Forwards infrastructure logs to registered services/components.		
Interacts with	Forwards an alert to registered components		

Success Criteria	Alerts are successfully delivered to registered services.
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Table 119: Forward Logs function specification

5.13.4 Query Engine module

Module Name	Query Engine	Priority	Must
Description	The Query Engine is responsible for forming queries related to infrastructure metrics and events and returning results efficiently, ensuring fast and accurate data access for other modules.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quality Monitoring module Policy Monitoring module Log Exporter 		
Extracted Functions	N/A		
Success Criteria	Queries are executed in a distributed manner.		

Table 120: Query Engine module specification

5.13.5 Alert module

Module Name	Alert	Priority	Must
Description	Exposes an API to other components for registering Policies, Quality Indicators and forwards alerts on these components.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quality Monitoring module Policy Monitoring module 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Push alert 		
Success Criteria	Alerts are generated and delivered to registered Applications.		

Table 121: Alert module specification

Push Alert function

Function Name	Push alert	Priority	Must
Description	Forwards alerts to other components		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quality Monitoring module Policy Monitoring module 		
Success Criteria	An alert is successfully delivered to registered components.		

Table 122: Push alert function specification

5.14 Zero-Touch Provisioning (ZTP) component

Component Name	The Zero-Touch Provisioning Service		
Intro / Overview	The ZTP Service automates the provisioning and configuration of edge and IoT devices, ensuring they are securely onboarded to the network and managed without manual intervention.		
Extracted Modules	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ZTP Manager for Devices ZTP Manager for K8 Clusters 		
Component Workflow	The ZTP Service follows a secure and automated workflow to onboard and manage devices: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Device Discovery detects new devices connecting to the network. 		

- Secure Bootstrapping authenticates and securely configures devices. This can be done via Ubuntu MAAS.
- Configuration Management applies initial and updated configurations (DHCP).
- Firmware Update Manager manages firmware updates to ensure devices are running the latest software (TFTP).

To illustrate the general concept the following diagram serves as an overview of the concept:

External Component Interaction

Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine: Provides data for monitoring device health and performance.
 Orchestrator: Coordinates provisioning tasks and schedules updates.

Prototypical Mock-ups
 TRL
 Potential Use-cases
 Layer
 Technologies

N/A
 TRL-4

- Industrial IoT Deployments
- Smart Cities
- Remote Monitoring Systems

 ENACT Orchestration Layer

- Programming Languages: Python, Java

Interfaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frameworks: Django, Flask • Libraries: OpenSSL, Paramiko • Tools: Ansible, Puppet, Chef
	Device Discovery API <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: Detects and lists new devices. • Type: REST API • State: Asynchronous • Data Format: JSON
	Secure Bootstrapping API <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: Authenticates and configures devices. • Type: REST API • State: Synchronous • Data Format: JSON
	Configuration Management API <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: Manages device configurations. • Type: REST API • State: Asynchronous • Data Format: JSON
	Firmware Update API <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: Manages and deploys firmware updates. • Type: REST API • State: Asynchronous • Data Format: JSON
Deployment Type	On-Premises
Authorisation	Requires authentication through the ENACT Security and User Management system.
Definition	Elevated user authorisation needed
Licence	GPL

Table 123: Zero-Touch Provisioning (ZTP) Service specification

5.14.1 ZTP Manager for Devices module

Module Name	ZTP Manager for Devices	Priority	Must
Description	The ZTP Module manager exposes all the functions of the ZTP component		
Interacts with	Orchestrator		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discovery of devices • Secured bootstrapping for devices • Configuration Management for devices and K8 clusters 		
Success Criteria	The success criteria of each function are described individually below		

Table 124: ZTP Manager for Devices module specification

Discovery of Devices function

Function Name	Discovery of Devices	Priority	Must
Description	This function will provide list with newly discovered devices. This list will be used by the Configuration Management		
Interacts with	Configuration Management		
Success Criteria	The function will return either a null or a list with correctly defined devices		

Table 125: Discovery of Devices function specification

Secured Bootstrapping of Devices function

Function Name	Secured bootstrapping of devices	Priority	Must
Description	This function will expose the DHCP server and the TFTP server functionalities.		
Interacts with	Configuration Management		
Success Criteria	The interaction of the DCHP and TFTP with the devices are successful		

Table 126: Secured Bootstrapping of Devices function specification

Configuration Management of Devices function

Function Name	Configuration Management of Devices	Priority	Must
Description	This function will expose the configuration settings available for various types of discovered devices in the local network.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discovery of Devices Secured Bootstrapping 		
Success Criteria	The configurations are available and correctly deployed, and the list of the updated devices is stored correctly		

Table 127: Configuration Management of Devices function specification

5.14.2 ZTP Manager for K8 Clusters module

Module Name	ZTP Manager for K8 Clusters Module	Priority	Must
Description	The ZTP Module manager exposes all the functions of the ZTP component		
Interacts with	Orchestrator		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ClusterDiscovery Configuration Management 		
Success Criteria	The success criteria of each function are described individually below		

Table 128: ZTP Manager for K8 Clusters module specification

ClusterDiscovery function

Function Name	ClusterDiscovery	Priority	Must
Description	This function will provide list with newly discovered K8 clusters. This list will be used by the Configuration Management		
Interacts with	Configuration Management		
Success Criteria	The function will return either a null or a list with correctly defined devices		

Table 129: ClusterDiscovery function specification

Configuration Management function

Function Name	Configuration Management of devices and K8	Priority	Must
Description	This function will expose the configuration settings available for existing clusters in the local network.		
Interacts with	ClusterDiscovery		
Success Criteria	The configurations are available and correctly deployed, and the list of the updated clusters is stored correctly		

Table 130: Configuration Management of Devices and K8 function specification

5.15 Security Risk Modeller (SRM) component

<p>Component Name Intro / Overview</p>	<p>Security Risk Modeller (SRM)</p> <p>SRM performs security risk analysis on the system model which represents the structural and functional aspects of the applications and infrastructure of the ENACT. It also includes various processing components and their interconnections. Physical objects (such as data, databases, processes, servers, etc.) are represented as nodes in the system model which are termed as assets. The interaction between these assets is referred to as connections.</p> <p>SRM will provide control strategies to lower the security risk. The controls may include authentication mechanisms, encryption algorithms, access controls, intrusion detection/prevention systems, and secure coding practices.</p>
<p>Extracted Modules</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interface • System Model (SM) • Risk Treatment Plan (RTP)
<p>Component Workflow</p>	<p>To illustrate the component workflow that takes place within the Security Risk Modeller, diagrams reflecting the interaction and workflow between components can be seen below.</p>
<p>External Component Interaction</p>	<p>Interaction with the SRM is performed through the Graph Modeller which collects data about infrastructure and application. This graph data is processed by SRM which auto-generates system models to perform risk analysis. The outcomes of risk assessment are visualised in the Graph Modeller and also used by DRL component to provide updated deployment schedules based on the risk and compliance standards. The outcomes of the SRM will be displayed in the Graph Modeller GUI.</p>

Prototypical Mock-ups

Login Page: This is the first page which appears to the user to get access to the SRM tool. The sign-in credentials are managed via Keycloak.

Home Page: Home page provides the modelling environment where a user can create a system model by dragging and dropping of different asset. Users can also select the connection type between assets, as there can be more than one connection available. The controls are generated once the system model is completed and risk analysis is performed.

TRL	Current: TRL-3 Expected: TRL-6
Potential Use-cases	Applicable in all pilot scenarios
Layer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENACT Modelling Layer
Technologies	Programming Languages: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Java Typescript SPARQL Python Frameworks: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Docker AngularJS Node.js Gradle Libraries: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nginx proxy server Tomcat Server MongoDB JenaDB Keycloak
Interfaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> iframe
Deployment Type	Software Docker container
Authorisation Definition	Keycloak Open-source Identity and Access Management
Licence	Apache 2.0

Table 131: Security Risk Modeller (SRM) Component specification

5.15.1 Interface module

Module Name	Interface	Priority	Should
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Description	Interface provides the frontend modelling environment and access to the SRM interface via Keycloak.
Interacts with Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Web UI • KeyCloak • Mongo DB
Success Criteria	The interface should provide access to the modelling environment.

Table 132: Interface module specification

Web UI function

Function Name	Web UI	Priority	Must
Description	The Web UI provides the Graphical User Interface for the modelling environment.		
Interacts with	<p>The diagram illustrates the Security Risk Modeller (SRM) architecture. It is divided into three main sections: Interface, Data Transformation, and System Model Development. The Interface section contains the Web UI (circled in red), Keycloak Authentication data, and MongoDB database. The Data Transformation section includes a Graph Modeller, Data Transformation, and Transformed Data. The System Model Development section contains Jena DB (Knowledgebase and System Model Details), Threat and Risk Modelling, and OWASP GDPR ISO27005. Arrows indicate the flow of data: Graph Data from Graph Modeller to Data Transformation; nq format data from Data Transformation to Transformed Data; Transformed Data to System Model; System Model to System Model Details; System Model Details to Knowledgebase; Knowledgebase to Threat and Risk Modelling; Threat and Risk Modelling to OWASP GDPR ISO27005; and finally, OWASP GDPR ISO27005 to Risk Treatment Plan.</p>		
Success Criteria	Web UI should provide a user-friendly access to the SRM.		

Table 133: Web UI function specification

Keycloak function

Function Name	Keycloak	Priority	Must
Description	Keycloak manages the user access to the SRM tool by allowing single sign-on with identity and access management.		

Interacts with	
Success Criteria	Keycloak prevents unauthorised access to the SRM interface.

Table 134: Keycloak function specification

MongoDB function

Function Name	MongoDB	Priority	Must
Description	MongoDB stores authorisation data (access rights of the users) and model metadata (last edit data, last user logged in etc.).		
Interacts with			
Success Criteria	MongoDB maintains data about model metadata.		

Table 135: MongoDB function specification

5.15.2 System Model module

Module Name	System Model (SM)	Priority	Must
Description	SM represented the assets and their relationships. This is developed from the deployment configuration received from the Graph Modeller. SM is analysed through SRM for possible		

Interacts with	attack paths.
Extracted Functions	SM interacts with RTP <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Transformation • System Model Development
Success Criteria	SM correct mapping to the devices and processes of ENACT deployment configuration.

Table 136: System Model module specification

Data Transformation function

Function Name	Data Transformation	Priority	Must
Description	<p>This Data Transformation will be a wrapper which performs the conversion of nodes and edge information from the Graph Modeller into acceptable format for the SRM. The SRM stores and processes the system models in N-Quads (nq) format. System model details are taken from JenaDB which are needed for the correct transformation of nodes information to asset types in the SRM.</p>		
Interacts with			
Success Criteria	<p>The Data transformation should process graph data and generate nq file format for system model development module.</p>		

Table 137: Data Transformation function specification

System Model Development function

Function Name	System Model Development	Priority	Must
Description	<p>System Model Development is performed based on the transformed data using JenaDB. This step is performed using system asset information from JenaDB.</p>		

Interacts with	
Success Criteria	<p>The system model development function should auto-generate the system model for risk analysis in the SRM tool.</p>

Table 138: System Model Development function specification

5.15.3 Risk Treatment Plan (RTP) module

Module Name	Risk Treatment Plan	Priority	Must
Description	Threats and controls (i.e. security measures); may include authentication mechanisms, encryption algorithms, access controls, intrusion detection/prevention systems.		
Interacts with	System Model		
Extracted Functions	Risk Mitigation Strategies		
Success Criteria	Overall risk to the system is reduced.		

Table 139: Risk Treatment Plan (RTP) module specification

Risk Mitigation Strategies function

Function Name	Risk Mitigation Strategies	Priority	Must
Description	Risk Mitigation Strategies are computed based on the risk of every security threat in the system. Threat and risk modelling is carried out on the system models and is checked for GDPR and OWASP based on ISO 27005 risk assessment procedure already defined in the knowledge base.		

Interacts with	
Success Criteria	Overall risk to the system is reduced.

Table 140: Risk Mitigation Strategies function specification

5.16 Software Development Kit (SDK) component

Component Name Intro / Overview	<p>Software Development Kit (SDK)</p> <p>The SDK provides developers with tools, libraries, and documentation to develop and integrate applications within the ENACT ecosystem. It facilitates the development of portable apps capable of distributed management of data by mobile devices.</p>
Extracted Modules	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SDK Libraries Development tools Documentation
Component Workflow	<p>SDK Libraries provide essential libraries for building ENACT-compatible applications. Development tools include tools for coding, debugging, and testing. Documentation offers comprehensive guides and API documentation. TBD. Sample Applications demonstrate best practices and common UCs.</p>
External Component Interaction	
Prototypical Mock-ups	<p>SDK Dashboard is the central hub for accessing tools, libraries, and documentation. Code editor provides an integrated development environment with syntax highlighting and debugging features. API Explorer is an interface for exploring and testing available APIs.</p>

TRL
Potential Use-cases

Expected: TRL-6

- Application development
- Edge Computing Applications
- Data analytics and visualisation

Layer
Technologies

ENACT App Development Layer

- Programming Languages: Python, JavaScript, Java
- Frameworks: Angular, React
- Libraries: Axios, Lodash
- Tools: Visual Studio Code, Git, Jenkins

Interfaces

- SDK Libraries API**
- Overview: Provides essential functions and methods for application development.
 - Type: REST API
 - State: Synchronous
 - Data Format: JSON
- Development Tools API**
- Overview: Offers tools for debugging and testing applications.
 - Type: REST API
 - State: Synchronous
 - Data Format: JSON
- Documentation API**
- Overview: Access to guides and API documentation.
 - Type: REST API
 - State: Synchronous
- Data Format: HTML or DOCX or MD

Deployment Type
Authorisation
Definition

Software
Access to the SDK requires authentication. Permissions are managed through the ENACT Security and user management system. Developers must have appropriate permissions to access certain modules and functions.

Licence

Apache 2.0 or BSD

Table 141: Software Development Kit (SDK) Component specification

5.16.1 SDK Libraries

Module Name	SDK Libraries	Priority	Must
Description	The SDK Libraries module provides the necessary interactions with different platforms and components to create hyper-distributed applications.		
Interacts with	Other (Maybe All) ENACT Components		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Libraries that interact with platforms (devices and clusters) Libraries that interact with ENACT Components 		
Success Criteria	The success criteria of each function are described individually below.		

Table 142: SDK Libraries specification

Libraries that interact with platforms function

Function Name	Libraries that interact with platforms	Priority	Must
Description	This function will provide the necessary libraries to interact with the different types of platforms that will be included in the ENACT project to asset types in the SRM.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> APM 		
Success Criteria	The ability to correctly interact with the different types of platforms.		

Table 143: Libraries that interact with platforms function specification

Libraries that interact with ENACT function

Function Name	Libraries that interact with ENACT	Priority	Must
Description	This function will provide the necessary libraries to interact with the components in the ENACT architecture.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> APM Other ENACT Components 		
Success Criteria	The ability to correctly interact with the ENACT components (architecture).		

Table 144: Libraries that interact with ENACT function specification

5.16.2 Development Tools

Module Name	Development Tools	Priority	Must
Description	The Development Tools module will provide utilities to be able to interact with the ENACT platform.		
Interacts with	Other (Maybe All) ENACT Components		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> APM Functions Various functions which act like wrappers of exposed by the ENACT components 		
Success Criteria	The success criteria of each function are described individually below.		

Table 145: Development Tools specification

Libraries that interact with platforms function

Function Name	Libraries that interact with platforms	Priority	Must
Description	This function will provide the necessary libraries to interact with the different types of platforms that will be included in the ENACT project.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> APM 		

Success Criteria	The ability to correctly interact with the different types of platforms.
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Table 146: SDK Libraries function specification

Libraries that interact with ENACT function

Function Name	Libraries that interact with ENACT	Priority	Must
Description	This function will provide the necessary libraries to interact with the components in the ENACT architecture.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> APM Other ENACT Components 		
Success Criteria	The ability to correctly interact with the ENACT components (architecture).		

Table 147: Libraries that interact with platforms function

5.16.3 Documentation module

Module Name	Documentation	Priority	Must
Description	The Documentation module provides the documentation on the usage of each library and module development inside the ENACT SDK.		
Interacts with	N/A		
Extracted Functions	N/A		
Success Criteria	The success criteria are offered by the ease of understanding of the documentation of ENACT SDK.		

Table 148: Documentation module specification

5.17 Application Policy Model component

Component Name	Application Policy Model		
Intro / Overview	<p>The Application Policy Model offers distributed application owners a mechanism to specify runtime policies that the underlying infrastructure should cover, ensuring that applications adhere to desired performance, security, and compliance requirements while dynamically adapting to changing conditions and resource availability.</p> <p>Distributed application owners can specify networking, storage, computational and locality policies.</p>		
Extracted Modules	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Network Policies Module: this module validates runtime policies related to networking such as packets per second, desired bandwidth, minimum delay, etc. Storage Policies Module: this to validates runtime policies related to storage such as desired I/O, underlying encryption technology, etc. Computational Policies Module: this module to validates runtime policies related to computational capabilities such as accelerators, number of cores, etc. Locality Policies Module: this module validates runtime policies related to placement of components across the Edge-to-cloud continuum. Policies Datastore Module: this module is responsible for efficiently storing policies. Policy Manager Module: this module acts as an interface between external components and internal modules. The Policy Manager forwards policies to their respected modules and provides a unified interface. 		

Component Workflow

External Component Interaction

Prototypical Mock-ups

N/A

TRL	Current TRL: 2 End TRL: 5
Potential Use-cases	all ENACT UCs
Layer	App Development Layer
Technologies	etcd, Go/Python
Interfaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: provides a user-friendly and secure way for application owners and administrators to manage runtime policies. It supports operations to create, read, update, and delete (CRUD) runtime policies. • Type: probably REST, though considering gRPC • State: synchronous • Data Format: JSON if REST, else protobuf if gRPC
Deployment Type	containerised application, helm chart
Authorisation	probably basic authentication
Definition	
Licence	probably Apache 2.0

Table 149: Application Policy Model Component specification

5.17.1 Network Policies module

Module Name	Network Policies	Priority	Must
Description	The Network Policies Module is responsible for validating and storing runtime policies related to networking. These policies cover aspects such as packets per second, desired bandwidth, minimum delay, and other quality of service (QoS) parameters. This module ensures that distributed application owner network requirements are documented and can be utilised by other components to perform intelligent operations.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policies Datastore module • Policy Manager 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validate network Policy • Store network Policy • Retrieve network Policy • Delete network Policy 		
Success Criteria	Network Policies are validated, inserted, retrieved and safely removed from the datastore.		

Table 150: Network Policies module specification

Validate Network Policy function

Function Name	Validate Network Policy	Priority	Must
Description	If the policy is valid, it is stored to the policy datastore.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Policy Datastore 		
Success Criteria	A network policy is checked for any violations.		

Table 151: Validate Network Policy function specification

Store Network Policy function

Function Name	Store Network Policy	Priority	Must
Description	Retrieves a list of network policies related to a distributed application from the policies datastore.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Policy Datastore 		

Success Criteria The policy is stored efficiently in the Policy Datastore.

Table 152: Store Network Policy Function specification

Retrieve Network Policy function

Function Name	Retrieve Network Policy	Priority	Must
Description	Retrieves a list of network policies related to a distributed application from the policies datastore.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Policy Datastore 		
Success Criteria	The policy is retrieved efficiently from the Policy Datastore.		

Table 153: Retrieve Network Policy function specification

Delete Network Policy function

Function Name	Delete Network Policy	Priority	Must
Description	Safely deletes a network policy.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Policy Datastore 		
Success Criteria	The policy is safely removed from the Policy Datastore.		

Table 154: Delete Network Policy function specification

5.17.2 Storage Policies module

Module Name	Storage Policies	Priority	Must
Description	The Storage Policies module is responsible for validating and storing runtime policies related to storage resources. These policies specify the required storage type (such as SSDs, HDDs, or cloud storage), capacity, redundancy, and performance requirements. This module ensures that distributed application owner storage requirements are documented and can be utilised by other components to perform intelligent operations, efficiently allocating storage resources to meet performance and reliability demands.		
Interacts with	Policies Datastore module: stores, retrieves and deletes Storage policies Policy Manager: interact with Policy Manager for any Storage Policy		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validate Storage Policy • Store Storage Policy • Retrieve Storage Policy • Delete Storage Policy 		
Success Criteria	Storage Policies are validated, inserted, retrieved and safely removed from the datastore.		

Table 155: Storage Policies module specification

Validate Storage Policy function

Function Name	Validate Storage Policy	Priority	Must
Description	Validates a storage policy ensuring the policy is well structured.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Policy Datastore 		
Success Criteria	A network policy is checked for any violations.		

Table 156: Validate Storage Policy function specification

Store Storage Policy function

Function Name	Store Storage Policy	Priority	Must
Description	If the policy is valid, it is stored to the policy datastore.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Policy Datastore 		
Success Criteria	The policy is stored successfully.		

Table 157: Store Storage Policy function specification

Retrieve Storage Policy function

Function Name	Retrieve Storage Policy	Priority	Must
Description	Retrieves a list of storage policies related to a distributed application.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Policy Datastore 		
Success Criteria	The policy is retrieved efficiently from the Policy Datastore.		

Table 158: Retrieve Storage Policy function specification

Delete Storage Policy function

Function Name	Delete Storage Policy	Priority	Must
Description	Safely deletes a storage policy.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Policy Datastore 		
Success Criteria	The policy is safely removed from the Policies Datastore.		

Table 159: Delete Storage Policy function specification

5.17.3 Computational Policies module

Module Name	Computational Policies	Priority	Must
Description	The Computational Policies module is responsible for validating and storing runtime policies related to computational resources. These policies specify the required accelerators (such as GPUs, DPUs or SmartNICs), the number of CPU cores, memory allocation, and desired processing power. This module ensures that distributed application owner computational requirements are documented and can be utilised by other components to perform intelligent operations, efficiently allocating resources to meet performance demands.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policies Datastore module • Policy Manager 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validate Compute Policy • Store Compute policy • Retrieve Compute Policy • Delete Compute Policy 		
Success Criteria	Computational Policies are validated, inserted, retrieved and removed in a safe manner from the datastore.		

Table 160: Computational Policies module specification

Validate Compute Policy function

Function Name	Validate Compute Policy	Priority	Must
Description	Validates a storage policy ensuring the policy is well structured.		

Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Policy Datastore
Success Criteria	A network policy is checked for any violations

Table 161: Validate Compute Policy function specification

Store Compute Policy function

Function Name	Store compute Policy	Priority	Must
Description	If the policy is valid, it is stored to the Policy datastore.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Policy Datastore 		
Success Criteria	The policy is stored efficiently in the Policy Datastore.		

Table 162: Store Compute Policy function specification

Retrieve Compute Policy function

Function Name	Retrieve Compute Policy	Priority	Must
Description	Retrieves a compute policy from the datastore.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Policy Datastore 		
Success Criteria	The policy is retrieved efficiently from the Policy Datastore.		

Table 163: Retrieve Compute Policy function specification

Delete Compute Policy function

Function Name	Delete Compute Policy	Priority	Must
Description	Deletes a compute policy from the Policies Datastore.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Policy Datastore 		
Success Criteria	the policy is safely removed from the Policies Datastore.		

Table 164: Delete Compute Policy function specification

5.17.4 Locality Policies module

Module Name	Locality Policies	Priority	Must
Description	The Locality Policies module is responsible for validating and storing runtime policies related to the geographical placement of components across the Edge-to-Cloud continuum. These policies determine where application components should be deployed to optimise latency, bandwidth, and resource utilisation. This module ensures that distributed application owner locality requirements are documented and can be utilised by other components to perform intelligent operations, optimising performance, compliance, and data sovereignty.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policies Datastore module • Policy Manager 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validate Locality Policy • Store Locality Policy • Retrieve Locality Policy • Delete Locality Policy 		

Success Criteria	Locality Policies are validated, inserted, retrieved and removed without causing any integrity issues from the datastore.
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Table 165: Locality Policies module specification

Validate Locality Policy function

Function Name	Validate Locality Policy	Priority	Must
Description	Validates a locality policy ensuring the policy is well structured		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Policy Datastore 		
Success Criteria	A network policy is checked for any violations		

Table 166: Validate Locality Policy function specification

Store Storage Policy function

Function Name	Store Storage Policies	Priority	Must
Description	If the policy is valid, it is stored in the Policy datastore		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Policy Datastore 		
Success Criteria	The policy is stored successfully		

Table 167: Store Storage Locality Policy function specification

Retrieve Locality Policy function

Function Name	Retrieve Locality Policy	Priority	Must
Description	Retrieves a list of locality policies related to a distributed application from the policies datastore		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Policy Datastore 		
Success Criteria	The policy is retrieved efficiently from the Policy Datastore		

Table 168: Retrieve Locality Policy function specification

Delete Locality Policy function

Function Name	Delete Locality Policy	Priority	Must
Description	Safely deletes a network policy		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Policy Datastore 		
Success Criteria	The policy is safely removed from the Policies Datastore.		

Table 169: Delete Locality Policy function specification

5.17.5 Policies Datastore module

Module Name	Policies Datastore	Priority	Must
Description	The Policies Datastore module is responsible for efficiently storing runtime policies related to various resources (i.e., compute, locality, network, storage).		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Network Policies module • Storage Policies module • Computational Policies module • Locality Policies module • Policy Manager 		

Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Store Policy • Retrieve Policy • Delete Policy
Success Criteria	Policies are stored in a failsafe manner to the database ensuring integrity, availability and consistency of information.

Table 170: Policies Datastore module specification

Store Policy function

Function Name	Store Policy	Priority	Must
Description	Stores a policy to the underlying database.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Network Policies module • Storage Policies module • Computational Policies module • Locality Policies module • Policy Manager 		
Success Criteria	A policy is checked for any violations.		

Table 171: Store Policy function specification

Retrieve Policy function

Function Name	Retrieve Policy	Priority	Must
Description	Retrieves policies related to a given distributed application.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Network Policies module • Storage Policies module • Computational Policies module • Locality Policies module • Policy Manager 		
Success Criteria	The policy is successfully retrieved.		

Table 172: Retrieve Policy function specification

Delete Policy function

Function Name	Delete Policy	Priority	Must
Description	Deletes a policy.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Network Policies module • Storage Policies module • Computational Policies module • Locality Policies module • Policy Manager 		
Success Criteria	The policy is safely removed from the Policies Datastore.		

Table 173: Delete Policy function specification

5.17.6 Policy Manager module

Module Name	Policy Manager	Priority	Must
Description	The Policy Manager module acts as an interface between external components and internal modules. It is responsible for receiving policies from external sources, forwarding them to the appropriate module for validation and storage, and providing a unified interface for policy management.		

Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Network Policies module • Storage Policies module • Computational Policies module • Locality Policies module
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inset Policy • Retrieve Policy • List Policies • Delete Policy
Success Criteria	Policies are analysed and forwarded to the corresponding module to perform checks and store them in the datastore.

Table 174: Policy Manager module specification

Insert Policy function

Function Name	Insert Policy	Priority	Must
Description	Receives a new policy and stores it in the datastore.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Network Policies module • Storage Policies module • Computational Policies module • Locality Policies module 		
Success Criteria	Inserts a new policy and efficiently stores in the datastore. Communicates with other modules to performs validation checks on their respective parts.		

Table 175: Insert Policy function specification

Retrieve Policy function

Function Name	Retrieve Policy	Priority	Must
Description	Retrieves a list of policies related to a distributed application.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Network Policies module • Storage Policies module • Computational Policies module • Locality Policies module 		
Success Criteria	Retrieves a policy successfully.		

Table 176: Retrieve Policy function specification

Delete Policy function

Function Name	Delete Policy	Priority	Must
Description	Deletes a policy related to a specified distributed application.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Network Policies module • Storage Policies module • Computational Policies module • Locality Policies module 		
Success Criteria	Safely removes a policy from the datastore.		

Table 177: Delete Policy function specification

6. ENACT Use cases analysis and specifications

This section provides a detailed analysis and specification of the UCs for the ENACT project. Currently, the focus is on two pilots, each illustrating distinct applications and scenarios within the project's scope.

The UC analysis includes comprehensive descriptions, objectives and ENACT's impact for these pilots. Please note that a third pilot will be added to this section and its details will be incorporated in the next iteration of this deliverable. This approach ensures that all relevant UCs are thoroughly documented and updated as new information becomes available.

6.1 Hyper-distributed Media Content Processing by MOG Technologies

6.1.1 Overview

6.1.1.1 Introduction, Opportunities and Barriers

The streaming market for sports has experienced a seismic shift in recent years, transforming how fans consume their favourite games and events. Traditional cable and satellite TV subscriptions are no longer the sole gateway to live sports action; instead, viewers are increasingly turning to streaming platforms for their fix of athletic entertainment.

One of the key drivers behind this shift is the convenience and flexibility offered by streaming services. Unlike traditional TV packages, which often require long-term contracts and come with hefty subscription fees, streaming platforms typically offer more affordable and customizable options. This allows sports fans to pick and choose the specific events or leagues they want to follow, without being tied down by unnecessary channels or packages.

Moreover, streaming services have made it easier for fans to access sports content on a variety of devices, from smartphones and tablets to smart TVs and gaming consoles. This means that viewers can catch the action wherever they are, whether they are at home, on the go, or even abroad.

The rise of streaming has also led to increased competition in the sports broadcasting industry. Tech giants like Amazon, Google, and Facebook have entered the fray, bidding for rights to broadcast live sporting events alongside traditional broadcasters and cable networks. This competition has driven up the value of sports media rights, leading to lucrative deals for leagues and teams around the world.

Another key advantage of streaming platforms is their ability to offer a more interactive viewing experience. Many streaming services provide additional features such as live stats and real-time social media integration, allowing fans to engage more deeply with the action and with each other.

However, despite the many benefits of sports streaming, there are still some challenges and limitations to overcome. One major concern is the issue of automatically detecting in-game events or follow players to provide the user with a more engaging experience (ex: heatmaps, player tracking overlays, search enhanced metadata).

This pilot focuses on adapting a video processing pipeline for automated analysis of live sports to take advantage of the opportunities available in the computing continuum, namely the seamless interplay of edge and cloud resources to minimise the latency, the availability of heterogeneous

devises to optimise the processing and storage capacities, automatic load-balancing and elasticity of applications to address varying demand patterns and dynamic adaptation to accommodate changes in the infrastructure or users behaviours.

6.1.1.2 Motivation

The market size of live sports streaming is huge and continuously growing¹⁵⁶. Figure 6 shows the amount of money companies are paying to secure the transmission of live sports. This means that the broadcasting companies expect to earn a lot more money from streaming the games themselves.

Companies are paying record amounts to stream live sports

Notable recent live sports rights streaming deals

League	Sport	Company	Geography	Total deal value (value per year)	Deal length
National Football League (Thursday Night Football)	American football	Amazon	United States	US\$13.2B (US\$1.2B/year)	11 years 2022–2033
Indian Premier League (Digital rights)	Cricket	Viacom18	India	US\$3B (US\$600M/year)	5 years 2023–2027
Premier League	Football (soccer)	Viaplay	9 European countries	US\$2.7B (US\$450M/year)	6 years 2022–2028
Serie A	Football (soccer)	DAZN	Italy	US\$2.5B (US\$840M/year)	3 years 2021–2024
Major League Soccer	Football (soccer)	Apple	Global	US\$2.5B (US\$250M/year)	10 years 2023–2032
LaLiga	Football (soccer)	DAZN	Spain	US\$2.4B (US\$470M/year)	5 years 2022–2027
Ligue 1	Football (soccer)	Amazon	France	US\$750M (US\$250M/year)	3 years 2021–2024
Major League Baseball (Friday Night Baseball)	Baseball	Apple	8 countries currently	US\$595M (US\$85M/year)	7 years 2022–2029

Notes: Some deal values were converted from euros to US dollars at the September 20, 2022 exchange rate of 1.00 euro = 1.00 US dollar. Value per year is the deal value averaged across the duration of the contract. Source: Multiple public sources.⁸

Deloitte Insights | deloitte.com/Insights

Figure 6: Major sports streaming rights acquisitions

¹⁵⁶ <https://www2.deloitte.com/xe/en/insights/industry/technology/technology-media-and-telecom-predictions/2023/live-sports-streaming-wars.html>

At the same time, the global sports analytics market size was valued at USD 3.19 billion in 2022. It is estimated to reach USD 16.45 billion by 2031, growing at a CAGR of 20.02% during the forecast period¹⁵⁷.

6.1.1.3 Target Objectives

In parallel, the cognitive computing continuum, proposed by ENACT, offers several motivations for utilising it in the context of live streaming, particularly for automatic analysis of sports content:

- (i) **Low Latency:** In live streaming, especially for sports events, minimising latency is crucial to providing viewers with a real-time experience. Edge computing brings processing power closer to the end-user, reducing the time it takes for data to travel between the source (e.g., sports venue) and the viewer's device. By processing and delivering content at the network edge, latency can be significantly reduced, enhancing the viewing experience.
- (ii) **Scalability:** Sports events, especially major tournaments or matches, can attract millions of viewers simultaneously and, therefore, are covered by several cameras. Cloud computing provides scalability, allowing streaming platforms with automatic computer vision analysis to dynamically allocate resources based on demand. Additionally, edge computing can offload processing tasks from centralised data centres to edge nodes, further enhancing scalability (e.g. adding one or more cameras to the analysis)
- (iii) **Enhanced Quality of Service (QoS):** The computing continuum allows for intelligent resource allocation and traffic management, leading to improved Quality of Service (QoS) for live streaming.
- (iv) **Reliability and Resilience:** Distributed computing architectures, such as edge and fog computing, enhance the reliability and resilience of live streaming systems. By decentralising processing and storage capabilities across multiple edge nodes, these architectures reduce single points of failure and improve fault tolerance. In the event of network disruptions or server failures, edge computing ensures continuity of service by seamlessly redirecting traffic to alternate nodes, thereby enhancing overall system reliability.

Overall, the computing continuum offers compelling motivations for leveraging its capabilities in live streaming, particularly for sports content where real-time delivery, scalability, and quality are paramount. By harnessing edge and cloud computing technologies, streaming platforms can deliver immersive, high-quality viewing experiences to sports fans worldwide.

6.1.1.4 Key Research Areas

This pilot concerning the live streaming and automatic analysis of sports content is highly relevant in the context of the following challenges faced in the media industry:

1. Distributed Media Processing;
2. Player Tracking and Recognition;
3. Broadcast Enhancement.

¹⁵⁷ [https://straitresearch.com/report/sports-analytics-market#:~:text=The%20global%20sports%20analytics%20market,period%20\(2023%E2%80%932031\).](https://straitresearch.com/report/sports-analytics-market#:~:text=The%20global%20sports%20analytics%20market,period%20(2023%E2%80%932031).)

6.1.2 Use Case Scenario

6.1.2.1 MOG Technologies

Processing data in heterogeneous platforms is nowadays a reality. The live sports video industry already takes some advantage of connecting the venue equipment, with different architectures, to several clouds. The media industry is known as one of the industries that creates huge amounts of structured and time critical data, with video, audio, and ancillary data that can be forwarded and processed in different clouds.

However, the current solutions that integrate cloud systems in the video workflows are fixed without much margin to be expanded and, sometimes, the cloud platforms cannot handle well the time critical dataflow. These data pipelines issues limit the potential of what heterogeneous platforms could do in professional live content production and broadcast.

The ambition to produce configurable and adaptative data pipelines in the media industry has thrilled the creation of business case 1, MOG's Pilot, that embraces the scenario where sports content annotation is applied, in a heterogeneous and generic processing environment, without human intervention, forming an automatic live sports content annotation strategy.

Several ENACT innovations will help MOG's solution, deployment, facilitating the live content transport between the sports venue and the end broadcaster, and supporting the automatic content annotation, tailored by a custom model that assists the AI in obtaining the annotation data.

MOG's business case with ENACT is designed for the media industry to take advantage of the computing continuum and distinguished platforms to fulfil challenging media data necessities, expecting to be a good example for setting two major challenges that exist in the media business: i) transport live content from the sports venue to the authorised broadcaster; and ii) enrich the content with valuable data during the process, without the need of dedicated and specialised teams during the event.

6.1.2.2 Scenario Description

This UC focuses on addressing the viewers' engagement and experience in the live broadcast events, by automatically annotating large quantities of media data, from various sources. As a result, it is mainly focusing on the processing of high-frequency video and audio streams. In such streams, the data starts from the event venue and flows through the continuum to the broadcaster headquarters or end user. The input and output data of the pipeline is in standardised video and audio stream formats, complying with professional video streaming standards. The processing of the data within the pipeline results in structured and human-friendly text annotation. This annotated and augmented data is then delivered to the final client as metadata (as illustrated on Figure 7).

Highlighting relevant data assets, regarding camera acquisition data, which encompasses video acquisition at a rate of up to 3 Gbits/sec per camera. For a typical setup involving 4-5 cameras (HD cameras per event; the data will be collected from two different sources: video and audio (each one containing different frames)). This results in a substantial amount of data, especially considering the duration of an event like a 90-minute football match. The calculation is as follows: 3 Gbits/sec x number of cameras (typically 4-5) x (90 minutes x 60 seconds). Despite the fluctuation, based on the information that the component can extract, the metadata could represent 2.5 KB of data (XML file) for every frame, and up to 300MB for a whole football match recording.

```

1  <data>
2  <teams>
3  <team id="team_id_1">
4  <name>Team A</name>
5  <equipment_avg_color>
6  <color>blue</color>
7  </equipment_avg_color>
8  </team>
9  <team id="team_id_2">
10 <name>green</name>
11 <equipment_avg_color>
12 <color>3</color>
13 </equipment_avg_color>
14 </team>
15 </teams>
16 <players>
17 <player id="player_id_1">
18 <name>John Doe</name>
19 <jersey_no>10</jersey_no>
20 <team_id>team_id_1</team_id>
21 </player>
22 <player id="player_id_2">
23 <name>Jane Smith</name>
24 <jersey_no>5</jersey_no>
25 <team_id>team_id_2</team_id>
26 </player>
27 </players>
28 <timestamps>
29 <timestamp id="timestamp_1">
30 <n_players>2</n_players>
31 <players>
32 <player>
33 <x>10</x>
34 <y>20</y>
35 <id>player_id_1</id>
36 <team>team_id_1</team>
37 </player>
38 <player>
39 <x>30</x>
40 <y>40</y>
41 <id>player_id_2</id>
42 <team>team_id_2</team>
43 </player>
44 </players>
45 </timestamp>
46 <timestamp id="timestamp_2">
47 <n_players>2</n_players>
48 <players>
49 <player>
50 <x>15</x>
51 <y>25</y>
52 <id>player_id_1</id>
53 <team>team_id_1</team>
54 </player>
55 <player>
56 <x>35</x>
57 <y>45</y>
58 <id>player_id_2</id>
59 <team>team_id_2</team>
60 </player>
61 </players>
62 </timestamp>
63 </timestamps>
64 </data>
    
```

Figure 7: Example of metadata annotations

Additionally, it is expected to provide the right data to other stakeholders, generating specific outcomes, likely:

- **Business domain expert (media manager)** can expect a clear vision about costs and resources involved and tools to support decision making.
- **DataOps Operator** will be able to assist deployments over heterogeneous virtual environments and the deployments won't be attached to a specific public, private or hybrid cloud.
- For a **Data Scientist**, the expected outcomes include access to AI-based tools that support modularisation, enabling the development of experiments for generating new insights. Additionally, the automation of data access and the definition of data sets depending on the experiment are anticipated. There is also need to highlight the easy reconfiguration of resource architecture to carry out data analytics experiments based on the properties of the data sets.

6.1.2.3 High-level architecture

Figure 8 illustrates the use-case data pipeline and its modular components. As depicted in the figure, the data follows through a structured path and is processed or treated by different components, ensuring that a rich and uninterrupted video stream provides a smooth experience to the final user during a sports event.

Figure 8 - High-level architecture of the use-case data pipelines

6.1.2.4 Flow Description

The use-case focuses on the processing of multimedia data in the sports event broadcasting domain. The time-critical scenario of live events broadcast requires a maximum time to process a new data sample. For the European market, the amount of time a frame is on the screen is typically 40 milliseconds (25 fps); that means, one frame stays on the screen 40 milliseconds, and it is replaced by the next frame. This brings the challenge of not only continuous and high-speed data processing in the compute continuum, but also respecting the data pace to ensure that a new video frame is readily available every 40 milliseconds.

Therefore, the multimedia data processing components are very critical for the use-case as the drop of even a few seconds may compromise future services for the end client. To mitigate this risk, the data flow needs to split into various paths with different priorities: main broadcast, AI extraction and annotation, and others that focus on extra ingest/transcode features.

After being captured, media data first goes into the stream split component which distributes it into the various paths. The main broadcast path is critical so it requires reliable resources and prioritisation among the other data paths to ensure that the data will arrive properly at the end-client. Parallel to the broadcast path, another path processes the data and, resorting to AI models, extracts information from the video stream received, following a more flexible expected data processing time. Additional paths may exist if the workflow is arranged in other forms using an additional module to encode the video into different formats. Moreover, other modules to create extra visual content using the metadata extracted could be deployed within the architecture depicted in section 2.1.

Considering the focus on providing enriched media broadcasts of live events, the use-case pipeline is ideally deployed just prior to the initiation of a specific live event. Subsequently, it may be deactivated upon completion of all video processing tasks, with offline processing available as a fallback option in instances of insufficient resources. The use-case, particularly its pipeline components are designed to guarantee that, despite parallel analysis and metadata extraction, the final user will receive an uninterrupted broadcast. Thus, all components along the main broadcast take into account this requirement. Ideally, all components should deploy simultaneously. However, priority components must consistently remain operational, maintaining low latency to

swiftly convey the main video stream to its destination and maintain initial quality. This means that subsequent components may be sacrificed to safeguard the broadcast path's integrity.

Table 178 below describes the technologies and technological modules present in the data processing pipeline - to be used for testing and validation of ENACT solutions.

Module name	Description	Technologies/Format
Camera	Physical video camera, deployed in the sports arena and pointing to the sports field, where its position and field of view is controlled by MOG. The camera will be connected to the "Transcoding Encoding" module with an SDI connection or equivalent.	-
Transcoding Encoding	Physical equipment that receives the uncompressed media data from the professional camera via SDI connection and processes it to compress and wrap the data in standardised IP/UDP protocol to be delivered to the following components.	-
Stream Split	A virtualised module that receives a media-standardised data stream and splits it on each of its media essence streams (Video and Audio). The split essence streams still go through IP/UDP connections.	Nginx RTMP Dockerised Container
Stream Relay	A virtualised module that receives compressed essence streams and wraps them in a standardised data stream to the broadcaster or end user. Different output data streams (e.g. RTMP, HLS, DASH) require different modules.	ffmpeg Dockerised Container
Video Decoder	Virtualised module that handles a compressed video data stream and decodes the video to provide an uncompressed data stream.	ffmpeg Dockerised Container
AI Event Detection	Virtualised module to identify relevant events and information available in the uncompressed video data stream. The ancillary data created by this module is associated with the respective video frame timecode.	Python and CV Libraries Dockerised component
Metadata Enrichment	Virtualised module that grabs all the identified data events and aggregates them in a structured and standardised form to be delivered to the end broadcaster	Dockerised Python container
Video Encoder	Virtualised module that creates a new compressed video data stream, from the uncompressed video stream. This compressed stream can be different from the original one. This module is optional.	ffmpeg Dockerised Container
Visual Enhancer	A virtualised module that uses the metadata extracted to create extra visual content. This module is optional.	Dockerised Python container

Table 178: Technologies and technological modules in the data processing pipeline

As mentioned before, these components will be containerised and deployed across the compute continuum in a distributed manner using the ENACT solutions, with the goal of achieving benefits such as enhanced performance efficiency and reduced latency.

Highlight to the AI Event Detection and Metadata Enhancement modules that represent macro components that are under continuous development, leading to evolving functionalities over the project's course. Despite this overarching description, they can be decomposed into smaller modules responsible for extracting information from the incoming video stream. Nevertheless, the core functionality of this pair remains consistent, ingesting unformatted video input and delivering annotated video output.

6.1.2.5 Datasets and Models

The data utilised within this use-case is primarily based on multimedia and timing information which needs to be processed promptly and according to the respective broadcast standards. High-quality and reliable multimedia streaming implies an assertive decision regarding the chosen video and audio codecs and the respective wrappers. Also, the configuration of the codecs has a huge impact on the amount of data to be processed, the video and audio delays, and the bandwidth needed to transfer the data. The multimedia data that flows through the pipeline exists in both uncompressed and compressed formats. For instance, for a 1080p video captured at 25 frames per second (fps), the uncompressed video stream (only one camera) would require a minimum of approximately 800 Mbps, while the compressed version typically ranges between 10-20 Mbps. This data is shared between the first components of the pipeline and is identified in the high-level architecture (Figure 8). This UC can involve several media streams, that with the appropriate video codecs and wrappers should generate data at a rate of approximately 1GB per second.

All the components described in section 6.1.2.4 process multimedia data, however, AI Event Detection and Metadata Enhancement, also extract and handle information about the live event, such as player classification, player tracking, and team segmentation. This data, identifiable by a video timestamp, is temporarily stored in JSON/XML format, following the structure presented in Figure 7. Subsequently, these components store this information temporarily before shipping it along with the video as metadata to the broadcaster. With further development, the data could start being stored and distributed via cache databases, like a local Redis deployment or through a local data streaming application like Kafka.

For validation purposes, the use-case will create a dataset of sports events videos captured in real-world scenarios that will help create testing simulations. This multi-media dataset will have various formats, codecs, and wrappers to validate the pipeline for different capture scenarios.

On the other hand, the use-case development does not encompass the training of AI models, it rather focuses on utilising models that are already integrated in the use-case. Therefore, the use-case will not build or search large datasets to train AI models. Moreover, new models that may increase the use-case performance and/or speed should be open-source. The current models employed are based on the YOLO architecture and are currently extracting information regarding player positioning (tracking).

6.1.2.6 ENACT Impact

ENACT presents a significant impact across various dimensions, including technological advancements, business enhancements, and environmental sustainability:

Technological Advancements:

- **Integration of Edge-Cloud Continuum:** ENACT introduces innovative aspects through the integration of an Edge-Cloud Continuum in media processing, enabling uninterrupted broadcasting, intelligent annotation, and peak performance across the end-to-end data processing pipeline.
- **Runtime Operation Monitoring:** ENACT monitors the runtime operation of the application - video production workflow - to understand performance drops and changes in QoS or QoE, and to react accordingly.

- **Lower Production Costs in Decentralised Sports Events:** ENACT reduces the cost of covering decentralised sports events by dynamically allocating edge resources when available. This also lowers the end-to-end latency between the acquisition of a frame and the annotated video.

Business Enhancements:

- **Optimising Resource Utilisation and Reducing Operational Costs:** ENACT enhances the value proposition for media streaming providers by optimising resource utilisation and reducing operational costs. This results in cost savings and improved performance for customers while maintaining smooth and uninterrupted service for broadcast consumers.
- **Navigating Increasing Data Complexity:** ENACT's outcomes are expected to have a significant impact on managing Edge/Cloud Computing Continuum infrastructures, making the integration of data pipelines into organisational business processes more accessible to a wider set of stakeholders, including start-ups and SMEs, regardless of hardware infrastructure.

Environmental Sustainability:

- **Reducing Resource Utilisation and Increasing Energy Efficiency:** The technological innovations introduced by ENACT lead to reduced resource utilisation and increased energy efficiency, fostering environmental sustainability in the media sector.

Overall, ENACT aims to enhance the efficiency, intelligence, and sustainability of distributed computing resources within the Cloud-Edge Continuum, benefiting media processing and business operations alike.

6.1.2.7 Current Status

The pipeline's components are currently deployed locally. In ENACT, the data pipeline will be distributed across the compute continuum to test and verify the impact of distributed deployment and adaptive management of components on the key performance parameters. The use-case will evolve in terms of its scalability and AI-based media processing techniques. This will require research on the state-of-the-art distributed media processing and AI techniques, to ensure that the use-case performances meet the constantly updated market performances.

As for the current deployment status, the use-case is ready to run on a virtualised environment, except, of course, for the physical modules. For testing purposes, these physical modules can be simulated through a virtualised module that will simulate the functionality of the real-time video streaming source (camera), which will be developed in the ENACT project. The pipeline's deployment will follow MOG's standard strategy using a Helm Chart on a single Kubernetes cluster (on-prem or AKS) with GPU resources. This means that no edge devices are currently being used which, in a test case scenario, can augment the latency between the video stream and its processing components.

6.1.2.8 ENACT Benefits

ENACT benefits our media streaming application and process by integrating it into the Edge-Cloud Continuum, ensuring seamless transitions of computing tasks, dynamic resource optimisation, and improved communication reliability. Its innovations streamline operations, supports scalability, and

offers potential cost savings. Essentially, these ENACT innovations should allow the application to reach the following KPIs:

- Increase data processing performance by 20%.
- Improve resource utilisation efficiency by 15%.
- Reduce the cloud computing bill by 20%.
- Increase the reliability and quality of cloud-edge node communication by 35%.

For this innovations impact assessment, several parameters are designated for comparison between the status presented in section 6.1.2.7 and the envisioned impact after the integration. These quantifiable characteristics serve as vital benchmarks to gauge the transformative effects of ENACT across various domains. Parameters such as resource utilisation, cloud costs, latency, environmental impact, and custom multimedia processing metrics can be utilised to delineate the existing operational landscape against the anticipated enhancements facilitated by ENACT. By systematically evaluating these metrics, stakeholders can ascertain the efficacy of ENACT in optimising resource allocation, enhancing performance, and reducing costs and environmental impact. Furthermore, these parameters also provide a comprehensive snapshot of the current operational dynamics. 6.1.2.10 presents the essential scenarios and metrics for validating these expected enhancements.

6.1.2.9 ENACT Technologies

ENACT presents a comprehensive array of layers and technologies aimed at enhancing the efficiency and intelligence of distributed computing resources within the Cloud-Edge Continuum (CCC). This use-case intends to extensively leverage ENACT across its various layers and components. In summary, incorporating ENACT's tools into this pilot will enhance infrastructure utilisation, scheduling, orchestration, and security measures, ensuring a positive impact across various components of the enterprise. Regarding scheduling we'll take advantage of the following components:

- **ENACT's AI Orchestrator:** Ensures optimal deployment of the data processing pipeline by effectively utilising resources, enhancing energy efficiency, and maximising the performance of different modules in the end-to-end data processing pipeline.
- **ENACT's Application Programming Models (APM):** Transforms the current pipeline components to ensure their readiness for distributed processing capabilities, allowing efficient use of the available edge-cloud infrastructure.
- **ENACT's Dynamic Graph-Based Modelling and Graph Neural Networks (GNNs):** Provide a comprehensive understanding of our distributed resources, enabling dynamic workload distribution and optimised deployment configurations with predictive insights into service availability, latency, and other performance metrics. This leads to optimised allocation and dynamic resource management for distributed computing, reducing the cloud computing bill and enhancing the reliability and quality of communication between cloud and edge nodes.
- **Reinforcement Learning (RL):** This UC intends to use an approach that will maximise the potential of the RL component that, within the orchestrator, will handle application performance metrics. Since the business case involves different flows of data with varying priorities, dynamic scheduling is essential. This allows the use-case to expose metrics related to end-user media consumption (priority) and AI enhancement processing time, enabling

ENACT to monitor and improve these metrics as necessary, alongside continuum resources metrics.

Regarding security, we'll also benefit from ENACT's Risk and Compliance approach. Additionally, the regulatory compliance component ensures that the application data complies with the AI Act. Furthermore, we'll take advantage of the ENACT techniques for dynamic networking.

- **Security Risk Modeller (SRM):** When deploying our distributed application, the SRM processes the configuration and highlights potential security risks and ensures the network is equipped with security policies to secure communications.
- **Zero-Touch Provisioning (ZTP):** ENACT will present dynamic edge-cloud resources handling, minimising manual intervention and enhancing resource accessibility.

6.1.2.10 Test and Validation

This use-case can be validated with local and live scenarios. In the early testing stages, we intend to provide simulated professional camera streams, using a sports video dataset to replace the physical modules and deploy the remaining modules as expected using ENACT in a real environment.

Later, the use-case should be tested entirely in a real environment depending on available resources.

Various scenarios are proposed to rigorously test and validate the application's and ENACT's capabilities, including its elasticity, load balancing, and environmental impact. There must be a focus on the elasticity and load balancing, to test ENACT's ability to dynamically distribute application components across the edge-cloud continuum to ensure seamless scalability and performance optimisation. This includes stress testing scenarios where services are removed to assess resource prioritisation and verify sustained functionality even under fluctuating workloads. Furthermore, stress tests should also be conducted, using more computationally demanding videos (e.g. higher resolutions, bitrates), and performing additional encodings or AI analysis. Likewise, there should also be testing scenarios focused on the environmental impact scenario that should evaluate the ecological footprint and cost implications of resource distribution, aiming to minimise energy consumption and carbon emissions while maintaining economic efficiency. By aligning testing scenarios with environmental considerations, the application can optimise resource usage and demonstrate its commitment to sustainability and responsible resource management under lighter loads.

This validation should be done considering these scenarios and then compared with similar metrics, aligned with the benefits specified, from the current (before ENACT) deployment, as presented in section 6.1.2.8.

Efficient resource utilisation and load distribution are pivotal for ENACT's impact assessment and are quantified through various metrics. These metrics and parameters help quantify ENACT's impact assessment, guide improvements, and enable superior market value and differentiation. Key parameters and metrics include:

- **Efficient Resource Utilisation and Load Distribution**
 - CPU utilisation
 - Memory usage

- Workload distribution across the Edge-Cloud Continuum
- **Cloud Costs**
 - Monthly bills
 - Resource provisioning expenses
 - Infrastructure costs
- **Latency and Communication Performance**
 - Round-trip time
 - Data transfer rates
- **Environmental Impact Assessment**
 - Resources energy consumption
 - Metrics from resource utilisation and distribution
- **Custom Multimedia and AI Enhancement Metrics**
 - Media processing quality
 - AI model inference speed

6.1.2.11 Expected Computing Continuum Resources for Validation

The challenge for the business case adaptation is considerable. Typically, adaptation means a short period where the data pipeline is on halt, but for the live broadcast, this is not an option. To mitigate the risk that some of the components may accidentally stop, the required resources need to be oversized to reduce the risk of losing part of the stream for a short period. Table 179 below systematises the estimated resources needed for the use-case modular components. Every described component is deployed in 1 container, except for the Metadata Enrichment component, which may include several containers

Tasks	Stream Split (Edge)	Stream Relay (Broadcast module - Edge)	Video Decoder	AI Extractor	Metadata Enrichment	Video Encoder
Resource requirements						
vCPU	2	2	4	16	2	4
RAM	4GB	4GB	4GB	64GB	4GB	8GB
Storage	10GB	10GB	10GB	100GB	10GB	10GB
Network	40Mbps	40Mbps	100Mbps	1Gbps	40Mbps	1Gbps
	out 100Mbps	100Mbps	1Gbps	100Mbps	40Mbps	100Mbps
GPU	-	-	-	Requiring CUDA	-	-

Table 179: Resources needed for the use-case components

The components that are part of the broadcast flow (stream split, stream relay) should be, in theory, deployed in the edge to ensure low latency resulting in an uninterrupted stream to the end user. The others should be deployed through the continuum available (edge or cloud), ensuring the best possible performance, but always prioritising the broadcast reaching the end-user with the QoE necessary.

The infrastructure for this UC should include servers distributed across both the cloud (with GPUs supporting CUDA) and edge devices. While there is no fixed number of servers required, their combined capacity must meet the specified requirements for each component.

6.2 Hyper-distributed Data Processing for Fujitsu's Mobility Digital Twin Initiative

6.2.1 Overview

6.2.1.1 Introduction, Opportunities and Barriers

The goal of this pilot is to develop distributed deployment configurations for Fujitsu's Mobility Digital Twin platform to enable its execution in a cloud-to-edge continuum.

Fujitsu's Mobility Digital Twin platform, also known as Dracena (Dynamically Reconfigurable Asynchronous Consistent Event Processing Architecture), is an innovative real-time digital twin platform designed to address the growing needs of the mobility sector. As the automotive industry undergoes a significant transformation towards connected and autonomous vehicles, there is an increasing demand for platforms that can process and analyse vast amounts of real-time data from multiple sources.

Dracena serves as a cloud-based digital twin platform capable of creating virtual representations of people, things, and contexts from the real world. It is specifically engineered to handle large-scale concurrent stream processing, allowing for the real-time analysis and prediction of events in the mobility domain. The platform's architecture is built to process high-frequency data transmitted from millions of devices such as connected cars, smartphones, and various sensors distributed across the transportation infrastructure.

Key features of the Mobility Digital Twin platform include:

- Real-time data processing: Dracena can handle large volumes of stream data at high speeds, enabling timely decision-making and service delivery.
- Flexible digital twins: The platform abstracts real-world data in real time, providing flexible representations of mobility-related entities that can be easily adapted for various services.
- Seamless upgrading: Dracena allows for dynamic additions or changes to data processing programs without service interruption, ensuring continuous operation of critical mobility services.
- Scalability: The platform is designed to scale efficiently, accommodating the growing number of connected vehicles and devices in the mobility ecosystem.
- Service object architecture: Dracena uses a unique object-oriented approach, separating generic "real-world objects" from service-specific "service objects," allowing for efficient development and event processing.

The Mobility Digital Twin platform has numerous potential applications in the automotive and transportation sectors, including real-time traffic information services, predictive maintenance, autonomous driving support, and enhanced safety features. By collecting and analysing sensor data from large numbers of network-connected vehicles, Dracena can provide valuable insights into traffic patterns, road conditions, and potential hazards, contributing to smarter and safer mobility solutions.

As the mobility sector continues to evolve, platforms like Dracena play a crucial role in enabling the next generation of intelligent transportation systems and services. The integration of such

platforms with edge-cloud computing paradigms, as proposed in the ENACT project, represents a significant step towards more efficient, responsive, and scalable mobility solutions.

In the ENACT project, the Mobility Digital Twin platform will be deployed in the edge-cloud continuum and its functional and non-functional aspects will be validated and compared with current deployment model. Distributed management of data, coming into the Mobility Digital Twin platform from various sources, will be achieved in the edge-cloud continuum by adopting the ENACT innovations represented by the AI Orchestrator and APM paradigms. With UNP we will develop an innovative way to deploy and manage distributed data coverage control function to significantly decrease data duplications in the edge-cloud continuum.

Digital Twin technology has the potential to significantly showcase the ENACT platform capabilities by enabling real-time monitoring, simulation, and optimisation of complex systems like cities.

6.2.1.2 Motivation

In this pilot, we are aiming to leverage Digital Twin technology, the Dracena platform, and the Integra - visualisation tool to create a powerful solution for real-time monitoring, analysis, and optimisation of urban environments.

Key motivation includes:

- Create a virtual replica of the urban environment using Digital Twin technology, which will serve as a dynamic, data-driven model of the city.
- Integrate various data sources and API endpoints to gather real-time data from IoT sensors, environmental monitoring systems, and other relevant city data streams.
- Utilise the Dracena platform to ingest, process, and analyse the massive volumes of streaming data in real-time, enabling the Digital Twin to stay up to date with the current state of the city.
- Leverage advanced analytics and ML models within the Digital Twin to derive insights, predict future states, and optimise city operations.
- Present the insights and predictions generated by the Digital Twin on an interactive, user-friendly dashboard using the Integra visualisation platform.
- Enable city planners, decision-makers, and other stakeholders to explore the city data in a visually intuitive way, drilling down into specific areas of interest and simulating the impact of potential interventions.

By combining the power of Digital Twins, real-time data processing with Dracena, and interactive visualisation with Integra, we aim to provide a visibility, understanding, and control over complex urban systems.

This solution will support data-driven decision making, enable proactive management of city resources and services, and ultimately lead to improvements in key urban sustainability, resilience, and quality of life indicators.

6.2.1.3 Target Objectives

This pilot aims to estimate and validate distributed management of high-frequency, high-volume data, coming from various sources in the mobility domain, such as GPS, mobile phones, roadside sensors, traffic controls systems etc, using Fujitsu's Mobility Digital Twin platform.

The ENACT edge-cloud infrastructure and application programming model would enable the real-time ingestion, processing, and analysis of the massive volumes of streaming sensor data powering the city Digital Twin.

- **Real-time Data Processing:** The mobility sector generates massive amounts of data that need to be processed in real-time to provide valuable insights and services. Dracena's ability to handle large-scale concurrent stream processing makes it ideal for this pilot.
- **Scalability:** As the number of connected vehicles and smart infrastructure elements grows, the system needs to scale seamlessly. Dracena's architecture allows for efficient handling of data from millions of devices without compromising performance which is also backed up by cloud computing.
- **Flexibility and Agility:** The rapidly evolving nature of mobility services requires a platform that can adapt quickly. Dracena's feature of seamless upgrading without service interruption enables agile development and deployment of new services.
- **Distributed Computing Optimisation:** By leveraging the cloud-to-edge continuum, we can optimise data processing by performing certain tasks closer to the data source, reducing latency and bandwidth usage. This is crucial for time-sensitive applications like traffic management or autonomous driving support.
- **Energy Efficiency:** With growing concerns about the environmental impact of digital technologies, it's crucial to optimise energy usage. Testing different deployment configurations will help identify the most energy-efficient setups.
- **Cost Optimisation:** By distributing processing across edge and cloud resources, we can potentially reduce the overall cost of data management and processing, utilizing resources more efficiently.
- **Enhanced Service Quality:** The ability to process data closer to its source can lead to faster response times and improved service quality, which is critical in mobility applications where milliseconds can make a difference.
- **Data Sovereignty and Privacy:** Distributed data management allows for better control over where data is processed and stored, which is increasingly important due to data protection regulations.
- **Resilience and Fault Tolerance:** Testing the platform's resilience and fault tolerance in a distributed environment is crucial for ensuring uninterrupted service in the face of network issues or hardware failures.
- **Futureproofing:** As mobility services evolve towards more autonomous and connected systems, having a flexible, scalable, and efficient data processing platform becomes crucial for future innovations. Overall, a city Digital Twin powered by ENACT would provide a real-time operational view of the urban environment to enable data-driven decision making and smart, proactive management to improve quality of life for citizens. The air pollution

monitoring example illustrates how the Digital Twin could be applied to optimise a city sustainability KPI.

6.2.1.4 Key Research Areas

Distributed deployment configurations: This area focuses on optimizing how the Mobility Digital Twin platform is deployed across the cloud-to-edge continuum. Key aspects:

- Identifying optimal placement of components across cloud, fog, and edge resources
- Developing algorithms for dynamic resource allocation based on workload and network conditions.
- Investigating trade-offs between centralised and decentralised architectures
- Exploring containerisation and serverless computing for flexible deployments
- Designing strategies for seamless migration of services between edge and cloud

Research questions include:

- How can we automatically determine the best deployment configuration for a given set of resources and requirements?
- What are the performance impacts of different distributed configurations on latency, throughput, and resource utilisation?

Distributed data coverage: This area examines how to efficiently manage and process data across distributed locations while maintaining comprehensive coverage. Key aspects:

- Developing techniques for distributed data storage and replication
- Creating mechanisms for ensuring data consistency across distributed nodes
- Designing strategies for efficient data routing and aggregation
- Investigating methods for distributed query processing
- Exploring techniques for handling data heterogeneity from various mobility data sources

Research questions:

- How can we ensure complete data coverage while minimizing redundancy and storage costs?
- What are effective strategies for maintaining data freshness and consistency in a distributed environment?

Hyper-distributed data processing: This area focuses on processing large volumes of data across highly distributed environments. Key aspects:

- Developing algorithms for distributed stream processing
- Creating techniques for distributed ML and AI
- Designing methods for real-time analytics in distributed settings
- Investigating approaches for distributed event detection and pattern recognition
- Exploring techniques for distributed data fusion from multiple mobility data sources

Research questions include:

- How can we optimise data processing algorithms for highly distributed environments?
- What are effective strategies for load balancing and task allocation in hyper-distributed systems?

Testing and validation of Digital Twin: This area involves creating comprehensive methodologies for testing and validating the distributed Mobility Digital Twin platform. Key aspects include:

- Developing benchmarks and metrics for evaluating distributed system performance
- Creating simulation environments for testing various deployment scenarios
- Designing methodologies for stress testing and fault injection
- Investigating approaches for validating data integrity and consistency in distributed settings
- Exploring techniques for end-to-end testing of distributed mobility services

Research questions include:

- How can we effectively simulate real-world conditions to test the platform's performance and reliability?
- What metrics are most relevant for evaluating the success of distributed deployment configurations in the mobility domain?

6.2.2 Use Case Scenario

6.2.2.1 Fujitsu corporation

Fujitsu is a leading global information and communication technology (ICT) company that offers a wide range of technology products, solutions, and services. The Fujitsu Poland Global Delivery Center (GDC) plays a crucial role in driving research and development (R&D) efforts, particularly in the areas of Cloud Computing, Hybrid Cloud, Professional IT Services and Artificial Intelligence (AI). As an R&D hub, the Poland GDC focuses on developing innovative solutions. By leveraging the expertise of the Horizon Europe (HEU) Innovation Hub Poland and the HEU operations core team, the GDC aims to strengthen its IP generation capabilities, foster a customer-centric and entrepreneurial mindset, upskill talent, and enhance its brand positioning. Looking ahead, the Poland GDC seeks to align its R&D efforts with the key research areas outlined in Section 6.2.1.4, while building strategic partnerships with industry players, startups, and academia to extend its capabilities and drive innovation in the ICT domain.

6.2.2.2 Scenario Description

The UC scenario involves leveraging Digital Twin technology, the Dracena platform, and the Integra visualisation tool to create a comprehensive solution for real-time monitoring, analysis, and optimisation of urban environments. The goal is to develop a virtual replica of the city that integrates data from various IoT sensors, environmental monitoring systems, and other relevant city data streams.

The Dracena platform will play a crucial role in ingesting, processing, and analysing the vast amounts of real-time streaming data generated by the city's IoT infrastructure. This data will be used to create a dynamic and accurate representation of the city's current state within the Digital Twin. Advanced analytics and ML models will be applied to the data to derive insights, predict future scenarios, and optimise city operations.

For example, the Digital Twin could focus on monitoring and mitigating air pollution within the city. Real-time air quality data from sensors across the city would be ingested and analysed to identify pollution hotspots, predict pollution levels, and evaluate the impact of potential policy changes or interventions. The Dracena platform's real-time processing capabilities would ensure that the Digital Twin always reflects the most current environmental conditions.

The insights and predictions generated by the Digital Twin will be visualised using the Integra platform, providing an interactive and user-friendly interface for city planners, decision-makers, and other stakeholders. This will enable them to explore the city's data, drill down into specific areas of interest, and simulate the effects of different interventions or policies.

By combining Digital Twin technology, real-time data processing with Dracena, and interactive visualisation with Integra, this UC aims to provide unprecedented visibility, understanding, and control over the complex systems that make up a city. This will support data-driven decision making, enable proactive management of city resources and services, and ultimately lead to improvements in key urban sustainability, resilience, and quality of life indicators.

The air pollution monitoring example demonstrates how this approach can be applied to a specific urban challenge, but the same principles could be extended to optimise energy consumption, traffic management, public safety, and other critical aspects of city operations. The Digital Twin platform's ability to process real-time data and provide actionable insights makes it a valuable tool for various fields, contributing to the overall capabilities and sustainability of the ENACT project.

6.2.2.3 High-level architecture

The Mobility Digital Twin platform leverages containerisation technology and cloud infrastructure for its deployment. The platform consists of various microservices, and components packaged as container images, enabling a modular and scalable architecture.

Figure 9: Fujitsu Mobility Digital Twin setup

Figure 9 above illustrates the Fujitsu Mobility Digital Twin setup, delineating the configurations for both development and production environments. Figure 10 below presents an example of a standalone customer deployment.

Figure 10: A standalone customer deployment

Technology stack

The components of the Mobility Digital Twin platform are developed using the following technologies:

Data Ingestion and Messaging:

- Apache Kafka¹⁵⁸: Distributed streaming platform for high-throughput, fault-tolerant data ingestion
- Zookeeper¹⁵⁹: Coordinates Kafka brokers and manages configuration

Stream Processing:

- Apache Flink¹⁶⁰: Distributed stream processing engine for real-time data analytics
- Java (OpenJDK):¹⁶¹ Programming language for implementing Flink jobs and custom logic.

Storage:

- Elasticsearch¹⁶²/OpenSearch¹⁶³: Distributed search and analytics engine for fast data querying

¹⁵⁸ Apache Kafka: <https://kafka.apache.org/>

¹⁵⁹ Apache ZooKeeper: <https://zookeeper.apache.org/>

¹⁶⁰ Apache Flink: <https://flink.apache.org/>

¹⁶¹ Java: <https://www.java.com/>

- Hadoop¹⁶⁴HDFS (optional): Distributed file system for large-scale data storage
- AWS S3¹⁶⁵(alternative to HDFS): Scalable object storage for resilient file storage

Deployment and Orchestration:

- Kubernetes¹⁶⁶: Container orchestration platform for managing deployments.
- AWS EKS¹⁶⁷: Managed Kubernetes service for easier deployment and scaling
- AWS EC2¹⁶⁸: Virtual servers in the cloud for hosting components

Serverless Computing:

- AWS Lambda¹⁶⁹: Serverless compute service for running code without provisioning servers

Content Delivery and API Management:

- AWS CloudFront¹⁷⁰: Content delivery network for fast and secure content distribution
- AWS API Gateway¹⁷¹: Fully managed service for creating, publishing, and securing APIs

Monitoring and Observability:

- Prometheus¹⁷²: Monitoring system and time series database for metrics collection
- Grafana¹⁷³: Analytics and visualisation platform for collected metrics.

Infrastructure as Code (IaC):

- Terraform¹⁷⁴: Infrastructure as code tool for building and versioning infrastructure
- GitOps¹⁷⁵using Flux Integration

6.2.2.4 Flow Description

As presented in Figure 11, the system utilises edge devices and gateways to collect and pre-process sensor data, which is securely transmitted to AWS IoT Core. Real-time analysis is performed using Kafka and Flink, updating the digital twin core. Processed data is stored in Amazon Timestream for historical analysis and cached in Redis for low-latency access. Spark handles data analytics, providing insights visualised through Grafana. The API layer facilitates interaction with the digital twin, while Prometheus and ELK monitor and log system metrics for operational insights.

¹⁶² Elasticsearch: <https://www.elastic.co/elasticsearch/>

¹⁶³ OpenSearch: <https://opensearch.org/>

¹⁶⁴ Hadoop HDFS: <https://hadoop.apache.org>

¹⁶⁵ Amazon S3: <https://aws.amazon.com/s3/>

¹⁶⁶ Kubernetes: <https://kubernetes.io/>

¹⁶⁷ Amazon EKS: <https://aws.amazon.com/eks/>

¹⁶⁸ Amazon EC2: <https://aws.amazon.com/ec2/>

¹⁶⁹ AWS Lambda: <https://aws.amazon.com/lambda/>

¹⁷⁰ Amazon CloudFront: <https://aws.amazon.com/cloudfront/>

¹⁷¹ Amazon API Gateway: <https://aws.amazon.com/api-gateway/>

¹⁷² Prometheus: <https://prometheus.io/>

¹⁷³ Grafana: <https://grafana.com/>

¹⁷⁴ Terraform: <https://www.terraform.io/>

¹⁷⁵ GitOps: <https://www.gitops.tech/>

Data Flow

- **Edge Devices** → **Edge Gateways**: Raw data from sensors and IoT devices is collected and pre-processed at edge gateways.
- **Edge Gateways** → **IoT Hub**: Aggregated and filtered data is securely transmitted to the cloud IoT hub.
- **IoT Hub** → **Stream Processing**: Data is ingested into a stream processing system for real-time analysis.
- **Stream Processing** → **Digital Twin Core**: Processed data updates the state of digital twin objects in real-time.
- **Digital Twin Core** → **Time Series Database**: Historical data is stored for long-term analysis and trend detection.
- **Digital Twin Core** → **In-Memory Cache**: Frequently accessed data is cached for low-latency access.
- **Digital Twin Core** → **Analytics Engine**: Data is analysed for insights, predictions, and anomaly detection.
- **Analytics Engine** → **Visualisation Layer**: Insights and predictions are visualised for end-users.
- **API Layer** ↔ **All Components**: Provides interfaces for external systems to interact with the Digital Twin.
- **All Components** → **Monitoring & Logging**: System metrics and logs are collected for operational insights.

Figure 11: Following diagram between components

Figure 12: Fujitsu Mobility Digital Twin high level design

Figure 13: Data Ingestion

Deployment details

The deployment process will involve the following steps:

- **Containerisation:** Each microservice and component of the Mobility Digital Twin platform will be packaged into a container image using tools like Docker. These images will encapsulate the application code, dependencies, and runtime environment.
- **Container Registry:** The container images will be pushed to a container registry, such as Amazon Elastic Container Registry (ECR), which serves as a secure and scalable repository for storing and managing container images.

- **Kubernetes Manifest Files:** Kubernetes manifest files (typically in YAML format) will be created to define the desired state of the Mobility Digital Twin platform components. These manifest files will specify the Stateful Set configurations, including the number of replicas, container images, volumes, and network settings.
- **Deployment to AWS EKS:** Using the Kubernetes manifest files, the Mobility Digital Twin platform components will be deployed to the AWS EKS cluster. The Kubernetes control plane will ensure that the desired state specified in the manifest files is achieved and maintained.
- **Scaling and Monitoring:** AWS EKS provides built-in mechanisms for scaling based on resource utilisation or custom metrics. Monitoring and logging solutions, such as Amazon CloudWatch or Elasticsearch, can be integrated to collect and analyse performance metrics and logs from the deployed containers.

The ENACT project's focus on testing and validation will benefit from this deployment approach, as it provides a reliable and reproducible environment for evaluating the platform's functionality, performance, and integration with other ENACT components. The use of AWS EKS aligns with industry best practices and enables seamless integration with other AWS services, such as storage, networking, and security solutions.

Development Environment consists of:

- Locally containerised services (e.g., Local K8s) which serve the purpose of simulating the production environment on a smaller scale, enabling developers to work in isolation.
- Single-node instances of Kafka, Flink, and Elasticsearch which provide the core functionalities for data streaming, processing, and storage in a simplified setup.
- Local IDEs with Scala/Java support which facilitate efficient coding and debugging of the Digital Twin application.
- Git for version control which enables collaborative development and code history tracking.
- CI/CD pipeline with Jenkins or GitLab CI which automates testing and integration processes, ensuring code quality.

Production Environment consists of:

- Cloud-based infrastructure (e.g., AWS) with multi-region setup which ensures high availability and global scalability of the Digital Twin platform.
- Distributed, scalable services including:
 - Kafka cluster for data ingestion which handles high-volume, real-time data streams.
 - Flink cluster on Kubernetes for stream processing which enables scalable, fault-tolerant data processing.
 - Elasticsearch cluster for short-term storage which provides fast data querying capabilities.
 - S3/HDFS for long-term storage which offers cost-effective storage for historical data.
 - API Gateway which provide secure and flexible interfaces for data access and manipulation.
 - Comprehensive security measures (IAM, VPC, encryption) which protect the Digital Twin platform and its data from unauthorised access and breaches.

- Robust monitoring and logging (ELK stack, CloudWatch) which offer deep insights into system performance and aid in troubleshooting.
- CI/CD for automated deployments which ensures consistent and reliable updates to the production environment.
- Edge computing integration which enables local processing of data, reducing latency and bandwidth usage.

Deployment constraints

There are several potential constraints that need to be considered to ensure a successful implementation. Here are some key deployment constraints to keep in mind:

- *Infrastructure Limitations:* Digital Twin require significant computational power to process and analyse large amounts of data in real-time. Ensuring sufficient computational resources, such as servers or cloud instances with adequate CPU, memory, and storage capacity, is crucial.
- *Data Integration and Interoperability:* System often involves integrating data from various sources, such as sensors, devices, and enterprise systems. Ensuring compatibility and interoperability among these diverse data sources can be challenging, requiring data standardisation and integration.
- *Scalability and Performance:* As the number of connected devices and the volume of data grow, the Digital Twin system should be able to scale horizontally and vertically to accommodate increased workload. The architecture should be designed to handle scalability requirements, leveraging technologies like containerisation (e.g. EKS) and distributed computing (like autoscaling groups in AWS)

Execution pattern

The platform is designed for real-time processing of large volumes of data from various sources in a distributed environment.

The execution pattern of a Digital Twin involves the continuous synchronisation and interaction between the physical entity and its digital counterpart. Here's a detailed explanation of the execution pattern:

- **Data Acquisition:** Sensors, devices, and other data sources collect real-time data from the physical entity. The data can include various parameters such as temperature, pressure, position, velocity, etc., depending on the nature of the physical entity.
- **Data Ingestion and Storage:** The digital twin receives the data from the physical entity which is ingested into the platform and stored in a structured format, typically in a database or a data store.
- **Data Processing and Analysis:** The platform processes and analyses the ingested data using various techniques, such as data transformation, filtering, and aggregation. Advanced analytics, ML algorithms, and rules engines can be applied to extract meaningful insights and detect patterns or anomalies in the data. The processed data is used to update the state of the digital twin, reflecting the current conditions and behaviour of the physical entity.
- **State Synchronisation:** DT synchronises state with the physical entity based on the processed data. The state includes the current values of relevant parameters, historical data,

and derived insights. The digital twin platform ensures that the state is consistently updated in real-time or near-real-time, depending on the data acquisition frequency and processing latency.

- **Simulation and Prediction:** The platform can simulate the behaviour of the physical entity under different conditions or scenarios. Predictive models and simulation engines can be employed to forecast future states, performance, or potential issues based on the current state and historical data. Simulations help in understanding the impact of different control strategies, optimising processes, and making informed decisions.
- **Visualisation and Interaction:** DT provides a user interface or API for visualising the state and behaviour of the physical entity. Users can interact with the digital twin, such as querying data, setting parameters, or triggering actions.
- Visualisation techniques, such as 3D models, dashboards, or augmented reality, can be used to represent the digital twin objects in an intuitive and meaningful way (**using optional 'Integra' component**)
- **Action and Control:** Based on the insights derived from the digital twin, actions can be taken to control or optimise the behaviour of the physical entity. Control commands or settings can be sent from the digital twin platform to the physical entity to modify its operation or performance. It can also trigger automated actions or alerts based on predefined rules or thresholds.
- **Continuous Learning and Improvement:** The digital twin continuously learns and improves over time as more data is collected and analysed. ML models can be retrained or updated based on new data to enhance the accuracy and effectiveness of predictions and decision-making.

Figure 14: High Level Overview of Dracena

The execution pattern of a digital twin is a continuous loop of data acquisition, processing, analysis, state synchronisation, simulation, visualisation, action, and learning. This pattern enables real-time monitoring, optimisation, and control of the physical entity through its digital representation.

The specific implementation of the execution pattern may vary depending on the UC, the complexity of the physical entity, and the technologies used. However, the core principles of data-

driven synchronisation, real-time processing, and continuous learning remain fundamental to the execution of digital twins.

Data Ingestion:

- IoT devices and other data sources send data to Kafka topics.
- Zookeeper manages Kafka cluster coordination.

Stream Processing:

- Flink jobs, written in Java, consume data from Kafka topics.
- Flink processes the streams in real-time, updating digital twin states.

State Management:

- Processed data and digital twin states are stored in Elasticsearch/OpenSearch for fast querying.
- Long-term storage or large datasets can be stored in HDFS or S3

Deployment:

- The entire platform is containerised and orchestrated using Kubernetes.
- AWS EKS manages the Kubernetes cluster.
- EC2 instances serve as the underlying compute resources.

Serverless Extensions:

- AWS Lambda functions can be used for event-driven processing or extending platform capabilities.

API and Data Access:

- AWS API Gateway exposes APIs for external service integration
- CloudFront can be used to distribute data or content to end-users efficiently.

Monitoring:

- Prometheus collects metrics from all components.
- Grafana provides dashboards and visualisations of the collected metrics.

Infrastructure Management:

- AWS CDK or terraform is used to define and manage the cloud infrastructure.
- Configuration management tools ensure consistent configuration across the platform.

Figure 15: Example of Internals workflow of Digital Twin

Monitoring resource utilisation

The solution bundles Grafana with Prometheus for monitoring. We can also use deployment-based solutions, e.g. AWS Cloudwatch.

Current Monitoring Setup:

Prometheus:

- Used for collecting and storing time-series data from various components
- Scrapes metrics from HTTP endpoints exposed by services

Grafana:

- Provides visualisation of metrics collected by Prometheus
- Allows creation of customised dashboards for different aspects of the system

AWS CloudWatch:

- Monitors AWS resources and applications running on AWS
- Collects logs, metrics, and events for analysis

Table 180 below presents the list of available metrics per category.

Category	Metric
Resource Utilisation	CPU usage
	Memory usage
	Disk I/O
	Network I/O
Data Storage	Storage capacity usage

	Read/Write operations per second
	Latency of read/write operations
Network	Network throughput
	Connection count
Kafka	Message throughput
	Consumer lag

Table 180: List of metrics per category

6.2.2.5 Datasets and Models

In the context of a Digital Twin system, datasets and models play a crucial role in enabling the accurate representation, simulation, and prediction of the physical entity's behaviour.

Fujitsu's Mobility Digital Twin platform introduces a data management approach that treats each piece of data from real-world devices as individual objects. These objects can be grouped together to define and manage data processing programs called Plugins. Objects can belong to multiple groups simultaneously. The platform allows the creation of new objects from real-world data or the results of Plugin processing. For example, road information can be extracted from vehicle data to create new road objects.

Plugins can be added or modified without disrupting the constant data upload, enabling quick modifications and logic verification without affecting other Plugins. The platform also supports external system linkage, allowing stream data and Plugin processing results to be connected to external systems. Data can be temporarily stored in the digital space for analysis in combination with external system processing results.

Datasets

Historical Data:

- Description: Historical data represents the past state and behaviour of the physical entity over time. It includes sensor readings, operational data, performance metrics, and other relevant information captured from the physical entity.
- Purpose: Historical data is used to train and validate models, identify patterns and trends, and gain insights into the past performance of the physical entity.

Real-time Data:

- Description: Real-time data refers to the current state and behaviour of the physical entity, collected in real-time or near-real-time from sensors, devices, and other data sources.
- Purpose: Real-time data is used to update the Digital Twin's state, monitor the physical entity's current condition, and enable real-time decision-making and control.
- Depending on source data format and particular UC we have identified following data patterns.

Depending on source data format and particular UC we have identified following data patterns.

Traffic and Road Condition Data:

- Data: Traffic flow, congestion levels, road closures, accidents, weather conditions, etc.
- Format: JSON, XML, or CSV
- Frequency: Real-time or near-real-time updates
- Volume: Moderate to high, depending on the coverage area and the number of data sources

Sensor Data:

- Data: Environmental sensors (temperature, humidity), occupancy sensors, etc.
- Format: JSON, CSV, or binary formats
- Frequency: Real-time or periodic updates
- Volume: Low to moderate, depending on the number and type of sensors

Geospatial Data:

- Data: Maps, POIs, geofences, etc.
- Format: GeoJSON, Shapefile, or other geospatial data formats
- Frequency: Relatively static, with occasional updates
- Volume: Moderate, depending on the level of detail and coverage area

Data Models

The following example shows the data structure used by Fujitsu Digital Twin:

```

{
  "mversion": "2.0",
  "oid": "car001",
  "stage": 0,
  "eventTime": 1562658762151,
  "body": {
    "speed": 45.32,
    "position_lat": 35.679603,
    "position_lng": 139.757313
  }
}
    
```

Table 181 below presents the Dracena data structures. “Body” has a flexible schema, dependent on the type of object.

Name	Type	Default Value	Summary
mversion	string	“2.0”	Message format version Only “2.0” available
oid	string	(required)	Destination Object ID
stage	number	0	Destination Object Stage
eventTime	number	0	Event occurrence time (UNIX milliseconds) of the corresponding sensor data
body	Map	(required)	Key-value data to store in the state of the object

Table 181: Dracena data structures

Data Structures types:

- Entity Structure: Hierarchical decomposition of physical entities and their relationships
- Attribute Structure: Static and dynamic properties associated with each entity
- Time-series Data Structure: Historical and real-time sensor data over time
- Metadata Structure: Descriptive information about entities, attributes, relationships

Data Storage:

- Short-term: In-memory storage in Apache Flink

- Medium-term: Elasticsearch/OpenSearch clusters
- Long-term: Centralised HDFS or AWS S3 with potential for multi-datacentre distribution

Data Processing Patterns:

- Real-time data ingestion using Apache Kafka
- Stateful stream processing with Apache Flink
- Complex event processing for pattern detection
- In-memory state management with checkpointing
- Continuous real-time analytics and aggregation
- Publish-subscribe data distribution
- Write-behind caching for data persistence
- Periodic batch processing for heavy computations
- Time-based data lifecycle management
- Feedback loop for closed-loop control
- Multi-tenancy via logical data/processing separation
- Edge processing for distributed computing

Access to Data:

- Self-managed service with full data access
- Real-world challenges: data localisation, ownership, sharing, access control

6.2.2.6 ENACT Impact

In the scope of the use-case, ENACT introduces technological advancements, particularly through the integration of an Edge-Cloud Continuum in data processing.

It also promotes business enhancements, considering that by optimising resource utilisation and reducing operational costs, ENACT enhances not only the value proposition for data streaming providers but also the customer experience, offering cost savings and improved performance to their customers while maintaining a smooth service.

Naturally, the discussed technological innovation aspects and their potential impact on the media business (across all stakeholders involved) also results in reduced resource utilisation and increase energy efficiency, which fosters environmental sustainability in the sector.

Technological Advancements:

1. Enabling real-time processing and analysis of massive volumes of vehicle sensor data across the edge-cloud continuum.
2. Implementing data reduction and replication strategies to optimise storage and bandwidth utilisation.
3. Leveraging AI and ML for intelligent workload placement and adaptive performance optimisation.

Business Enhancements:

1. Improved scalability to support a rapidly growing fleet of connected vehicles and increasing data volumes.
2. Faster time-to-market for new mobility services and features by leveraging a flexible and adaptive platform.

3. Increased competitiveness in the market by offering advanced capabilities like predictive maintenance, real-time traffic insights, and intelligent route optimisation.
4. Unlocking new revenue streams and business models based on data-driven services and partnerships.
5. Contributing to sustainability goals by optimising resource consumption and minimising environmental impact of data processing.

6.2.2.7 Current Status

Fujitsu's Mobility Digital Twin solution and framework is currently operational in at least two deployments within the European region. As part of the ENACT project, we aim to significantly enhance and expand this technology through several key initiatives:

- Infrastructure Modernisation: Developing a new, state-of-the-art infrastructure to support advanced functionalities.
- Plugin Development: Creating new plugins to extend the platform's capabilities and adaptability.
- Containerisation: Implementing container-based architecture to improve scalability and deployment flexibility.
- EU Ecosystem Alignment: Adapting the system to align with European digital infrastructure standards and requirements.
- Distribution Optimisation: Enhancing the distributed nature of the platform to improve performance and resilience.
- Data Integration:
 - Expanding data ingestion capabilities to incorporate diverse sources, including urban environments and IoT devices.
 - Implementing robust data sanitisation and standardisation processes to ensure data quality and consistency.
- Unification: Integrating the platform with the INTEGRA component to enhance overall system cohesion.
- Visualisation Enhancements: Developing advanced visualisation tools to improve data interpretation and user experience.

These initiatives aim to elevate the Fujitsu Mobility Digital Twin platform, ensuring its continued relevance and effectiveness in the rapidly evolving digital landscape of Europe's mobility sector.

6.2.2.8 ENACT Benefits

The Fujitsu Mobility Digital Twin platform aims to provide distributed data access, analysis, and decision support functionalities to enable the creation of high-precision maps, development of autonomous vehicles, and better understanding of driving conditions. However, the increasing number of connected vehicles and the associated data volume poses significant challenges in efficiently handling, orchestrating, and managing the underlying distributed compute and storage infrastructure.

ENACT aims to deliver the following key performance improvements in the UC, as outlined in the proposal:

- Reduce the cloud computing bill through optimised resource utilisation across the edge-cloud continuum.
- Increase reliability and quality of communication between cloud and edge nodes.
- Improve overall system performance through efficient distributed data processing.

These benefits will be achieved through the application of ENACT technologies such as:

- Techniques for seamless networking and dynamic discovery of edge-cloud resources to ensure reliable communication.
- Distributed data processing capabilities to parallelise compute-intensive tasks like video analysis across available resources.

6.2.2.9 ENACT Technologies

ENACT's innovative technologies can significantly benefit the Fujitsu Mobility Digital Twin in the following ways:

- **Scalable and Efficient Data Processing:** ENACT's APM and Cognitive Orchestrator can enable the Mobility Digital Twin to efficiently process and manage the massive volumes of streaming vehicle data across the edge-cloud continuum. This will lead to improved scalability, reduced latency, and optimised resource utilisation.
- **Enhanced Situational Awareness:** The ENACT DGM can provide a real-time, unified view of the entire mobility ecosystem, integrating data from vehicles, infrastructure, and external systems. This will enable the Mobility Digital Twin to maintain a highly accurate and up-to-date digital representation of the real-world driving environment.
- **Intelligent Workload Distribution:** ENACT's AI-driven orchestration capabilities can dynamically distribute the Mobility Digital Twin's workloads across the edge-cloud continuum based on factors like data locality, resource availability, and application requirements. This will result in optimised performance, reduced data transfer costs, and improved energy efficiency.
- **Seamless Scalability and Evolution:** ENACT's ZTP and dynamic discovery mechanisms will allow the Mobility Digital Twin to seamlessly incorporate new vehicles, devices, and data sources as the ecosystem grows and evolves over time. This will provide the necessary flexibility and scalability to support the platform's long-term growth and expansion.

Computing Continuum

In the Digital Twin platform, the computing continuum, which spans from edge to cloud, plays a crucial role in enabling real-time data processing, scalability, and efficient resource utilisation. Here's how the edge and cloud continuum are currently being used and how it can be further leveraged to provide more benefits:

Edge Computing:

- *Data Preprocessing:* Edge devices, such as gateways or smart sensors, perform initial data preprocessing tasks, such as filtering, aggregation, and compression. This reduces the volume of data transmitted to the cloud and minimises network bandwidth consumption.
- *Real-time Analytics:* Edge nodes can execute real-time analytics and ML models to provide immediate insights and enable low-latency decision-making. This is particularly important for time-critical applications that require fast response times.
- *Local Data Storage:* Edge devices can store data locally for short-term persistence and offline access. This ensures data availability even in scenarios with intermittent network connectivity.

Cloud Computing:

- *Centralised Data Storage:* The cloud provides scalable and reliable storage infrastructure to store and manage large volumes of data generated by the Digital Twin platform. It offers high availability, data replication, and backup capabilities.
- *Batch Processing and Analytics:* The cloud enables the execution of complex batch processing and analytics workloads on the collected data. It provides powerful computing resources and parallel processing capabilities to handle computationally intensive tasks.
- *Model Training and Deployment:* The cloud is used for training advanced ML models using aggregated data from multiple sources. These models can then be deployed to edge devices for real-time inference and decision making.

6.2.2.10 Test and Validation

The Intelligent City Digital Twin Platform will be validated through a combination of simulated and real-world scenarios. In the early testing stages, the platform will be tested using simulated data generated from various sources, such as IoT sensors, environmental monitoring systems, and city data streams. This simulated data will be used to create a virtual replica of the urban environment and test the platform's capabilities in a controlled setting.

6.2.2.11 Expected Computing Continuum Resources for Validation

effectively validate the Fujitsu Intelligent City Digital Twin Platform, a diverse range of computing resources spanning the edge-cloud continuum will be required. These resources will be used to test the platform's ability to process and analyse large volumes of real-time data from various city data sources and IoT sensors.

Edge Devices and Gateways:

- IoT sensors and devices deployed across the city, such as environmental sensors, traffic cameras, and smart meters.
- Edge gateways and micro data centres that aggregate and preprocess data from IoT devices before sending it to the cloud.
- Edge computing resources, such as Raspberry Pi or Intel NUC, to run local data processing and analytics.

Table 182 below presents the estimated resources needed for the use-case components.

Component	CPU	Memory	Storage	Network
Lambda Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Varies based on workload Burstable CPU performance 	512 MB – 4GB of RAM	Ephemeral storage up to 1 GB	High-speed, low-latency connectivity to event sources and services
Apache Flink	2 - 4 cores per task manager	1GB - 32GB of RAM per task manager	30GB	High-bandwidth, low-latency connectivity between Flink nodes
Containers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Varies based on application requirements. 1 – 4 vCPU per container 	1-4 GB of RAM per container	Ephemeral and persistence storage	Fast, reliable networking between containers
Edge Devices	1 vCPU	1GB – 4GB	10GB	100Mbps
Document Database – OpenSearch/ElasticSearch	2-4 vCPU	32 GB of RAM	100GB - 500GB (depending on data)	High-bandwidth, low-latency connectivity between cloud services

Table 182: Resources needed for the use-case components

The infrastructure for this UC should include servers distributed across both the cloud and edge devices. While there is no fixed number of servers required, their combined capacity must meet the specified requirements for each component.

7. ENACT Vision

This section presents the goals and aspirations for the ENACT platform and the vision for each of the Pilots in their industries and domains of focus.

7.1 ENACT platform goals and aspirations

The ENACT platform’s overall objective is to provide a cognitive, highly adaptable and distributed solution tailored to meet the special needs of the Cloud-Edge Continuum such as dynamic environment changes, node heterogeneity, and resource and application constraints.

To this end, ENACT aims to create a holistic platform that brings together cutting-edge concepts and technological solutions to enable continuous network and infrastructure monitoring, resource modelling, risk assessment, automated resource provisioning, cognitive scheduling, orchestration, adaptive application deployment, distributed learning and sovereign data storage.

Figure 16: ENACT Project phases

The above aim of the ENACT project is realised through in the following phases (as also illustrated in Figure 16 above):

1. In the first phase, different types of edge and cloud resources are interlinked through innovative networking and remote configuration techniques to establish the connectivity underpinning the compute continuum. This phase concerns with realising the connected infrastructure that allows for orchestration and deployment of applications and services on suitable resources, from edge to the cloud.
2. The connected resources are modelled using innovative dynamic graph modelling techniques, allowing for greater visibility and understanding of available resources and the (application deployment and orchestration) opportunities available in the distributed edge-cloud continuum. In this respect, this phase is concerned with the development of dynamic graph models that provide greater awareness and insight into the opportunities available for distributed deployment of applications.
3. The dynamic graph model, representing the connected or interlinked edge-cloud resources are analysed through graph neural network and deep reinforcement learning techniques to determine the best deployment configurations for distributed applications.
4. AI optimisation techniques are also by the ENACT orchestrator to optimise the performance (in terms of resource utilisation, energy efficiency, cost, etc.) of the underlying edge-cloud resources through the management and adaptation of application deployment configurations. AI optimisation techniques are also used at the application level, where the application can make their own decisions about the optimal deployment and execution behaviour based on the analysis of monitoring data coming from the underlying resources and the application performance or execution behaviour.

5. The adaptation actions suggested by the AI-based optimisation techniques (within the ENACT orchestrator) are implemented through the use of state-of-the-art container orchestration and management solutions operating at the edge and cloud levels.
6. To take full advantage of the edge-cloud continuum and the dynamism in such distributed environment, ENACT develops an innovative application programming model. This programming model provides the libraries and constructs that enable the development of adaptive applications, capable of monitoring their performance or execution behaviour and suggesting possible adaptation actions that can help improve the performance related aspects.

To realise the various phases associated with the ENACT vision, the project will leverage recent technological advancements such as zero-touch provisioning, AI scheduling optimisation algorithms, Graphic Neural Networks, virtual training capabilities, application-level adaptation and Data Spaces.

The developed concepts and technological solutions will be tested and validated in 3 different domains, where distributed applications are expected to make significant economic and ecologic impacts. Pending the finalisation of the third ENACT Pilot introduction, the ENACT Vision for the two (2) other pilot domains and use-case scenarios are described in the next section.

7.2 Hyper-distributed Media Content Processing by MOG Technologies

ENACT aims to elevate the media streaming use-case across technological, security, and environmental efficiency domains. The integration of an Edge-Cloud Continuum in the media processing domain marks a significant technological advancement, enabling uninterrupted broadcasting and intelligent annotation, facilitating seamless transitions of computing tasks between edge devices and cloud servers. This integration ensures dynamic resource optimisation, enhancing efficiency and performance while improving communication reliability between cloud and edge nodes. Such innovation not only streamlines operations but also fosters further scalability and innovation with potential cost savings.

In terms of secure communications, integrating with ENACT, underscores the imperative of robust security measures. With proprietary data flowing through the pipeline, access controls and authentication mechanisms become pivotal to safeguard against unauthorised access and data breaches. This proactive security approach protects intellectual property and cultivates stakeholder trust. From a business perspective, introducing an application within a dynamic and intelligent Edge-Cloud Continuum presents a compelling opportunity. By optimising resource utilisation and reducing operational costs, ENACT enhances the value proposition for MOG's customers. Leveraging the continuum effectively translates into tangible cost savings, minimising infrastructure overheads while maximising performance, thus bolstering competitiveness and market positioning.

Last, but certainly not least, the environmental impact is vital. ENACT's efficient distribution of infrastructure resources minimises energy consumption and reduces carbon footprint. This optimisation ensures that computing resources are utilised carefully, minimising unused resources and, therefore, the environmental impact. Furthermore, by prioritising environmental sustainability, the application can capitalise on the growing market demand for sustainable solutions, thereby enhancing MOG's brand reputation and market positioning.

7.3 Hyper-distributed Data Processing for Fujitsu's Mobility Digital Twin Initiative

Digital Twin technology has the potential to significantly impact the ENACT project by enabling real-time monitoring, simulation, and optimisation of complex systems like cities.

Cities can leverage **Digital Twins** to create a virtual replica of the urban environment that integrates real-time data from various IoT sensors and systems. This allows city planners and managers to visualise, analyse and run simulations on city operations. For example, a city Digital Twin could ingest real-time air pollution data from sensors across the city and use advanced data analytics and ML models to identify pollution hotspots, predict pollution levels, evaluate the impact of policy changes, and optimise traffic flows to minimise emissions.

The **Integra** visualisation platform could be used to create interactive visualisations and dashboards of the city Digital Twin. This would allow stakeholders to intuitively explore the air pollution, traffic data in the context of the virtual city model, drilling down to street level to see hyper-local variations.

The ENACT edge-cloud infrastructure and application programming model would enable the real-time ingestion, processing, and analysis of the massive volumes of streaming sensor data powering the city Digital Twin. The cognitive orchestrator could dynamically allocate computing resources to ensure the Digital Twin simulations and visualisations always have sufficient performance.

Overall, a city Digital Twin powered by ENACT would provide a real-time operational view of the urban environment to enable data-driven decision making and smart, proactive management to improve quality of life for citizens. The air pollution monitoring example illustrates how the Digital Twin could be applied to optimise a city sustainability KPI.

In this UC, Digital Twin technology, the Dracena platform, and the Integra visualisation tool will be leveraged to create a powerful solution for real-time monitoring, analysis, and optimisation of urban environments, which enable the development of a comprehensive virtual replica of the urban environment, integrating a variety of data sources and endpoints that collect real-time data from IoT sensors, environmental monitoring systems, and other pertinent city data streams. The created model will serve as a dynamic, data-driven representation of the city.

The Dracena platform will be employed to ingest, process, and analyse the vast amounts of streaming data in real-time, ensuring the Digital Twin reflects the current state of the city accurately. Advanced analytics and ML models will be utilised within the Digital Twin to derive insights, predict future states, and optimise city operations.

The insights and predictions generated by the Digital Twin will be presented on an interactive, user-friendly manner using the Integra visualisation platform. This will enable city planners, decision-makers, and other stakeholders to explore city data in a visually intuitive manner, allowing them to drill down into specific areas of interest and simulate the impact of potential interventions.

By combining the power of Digital Twins, real-time data processing with Dracena, and interactive visualisation with Integra, the aim is to provide an visibility, understanding, and control over complex urban systems.

This solution will support data-driven decision making, enable proactive management of city resources and services, and ultimately lead to improvements in key urban sustainability, resilience, and quality of life indicators.

The air pollution monitoring example showcases how this approach could be applied to track and mitigate a critical environmental challenge, but the same principles could be extended to optimise energy consumption, traffic management, public safety, and other vital aspects of city operations.

Additionally, the Digital Twin technology is providing real-time data processing which can be used for usage scenarios in various fields that will utilise the ENACT project results, hence contributing to the ENACT platform capabilities and sustainability.

Reduced data duplications and optimised data distribution: The Digital Twin platform in ENACT can address the challenge of data duplications and enable optimised data distribution across the system. By employing intelligent data deduplication techniques, such as data hashing and content-based addressing, the platform can identify and eliminate redundant data storage across different nodes and devices. This reduces storage costs, improves data consistency, and streamlines data management. Additionally, the Digital Twin platform optimises data distribution by leveraging edge computing and distributed storage mechanisms. Data can be strategically placed closer to the points of consumption, minimising latency and network congestion. Intelligent data replication and synchronisation techniques ensure that critical data is available where and when needed, while minimising unnecessary data transfers and duplications.

Advanced hyper-distributed data processing: ENACT can leverage the Digital Twin platform to enable advanced hyper-distributed data processing capabilities. The platform supports the seamless distribution and parallel processing of data across multiple nodes, edge devices, and cloud resources. By employing distributed computing frameworks, such as Apache Spark or Flink, the Digital Twin platform can efficiently process large volumes of data in real-time, enabling complex analytics, ML, and AI applications. The hyper-distributed architecture allows for the optimal utilisation of computing resources, load balancing, and scalability. Data processing tasks can be intelligently partitioned and assigned to different nodes based on their capabilities, locality, and workload characteristics. This enables the Digital Twin platform to handle the growing volume, velocity, and variety of data generated in the ENACT ecosystem, providing real-time insights and actionable intelligence.

8. Conclusions

This deliverable presented the first iteration of the SotA analysis, the specification of the ENACT platform components, the definitions and specifications of the ENACT UCs, and the Impact and Vision for the ENACT platform and the ENACT Pilots.

A comprehensive SotA analysis was presented in fourteen (14) distinct innovation topics and subtopics that are highly relevant to ENACT scopes and developments, including an in-depth analysis of the current research directions and related work, a presentation of the most relevant and commonly used market-read, commercial and industrial solutions and standards. The advancements that are foreseen within the frame of ENACT project were also detailed, accompanied with information about the relevant ENACT platform components. Finally, the relevant projects and technologies (along with their TRL) were identified.

The specification of the ENACT platform components included the detailed definition of seventeen (17) components, forty-three (43) modules, one hundred and eighteen (118) functions and three (3) data models to be developed within the frame of ENACT project. For each of these components, the internal modules, workflow, interactions with other components, prototypical GUI mock-ups, TRLs, relevance and applicability in the ENACT Pilots, relevance with the difference layers of the ENACT provisional architecture, and implementation details, such as technologies, frameworks, libraries and tools envisioned to be used, high-level interfaces, deployment type, authorisation details and licensing information were provided. Additionally, the functional specifications of each component's modules and functions were defined, including, a comprehensive description, implementation priority, interactions and success criteria.

The two (2) current ENACT Pilots were defined in detail, including the description of each Pilot, opportunities and barriers, motivation, target objectives and key research areas, and the UC scenario were specified, including their description, high-level architecture, involved components, information flows, datasets and models, ENACT impact and benefits. Further information was provided regarding the current status, and testing and validation details. As already mentioned, the partners associated with Pilot 3 of the ENACT proposal withdrew in the early stages of the project, and the introduction of a replacement Pilot is currently in process and being finalised. As such, the definition and specifications of the new Pilot and the related UC(s) will be reported in the next iteration of this deliverable and taken into account for the update of affected content, as needed.

This deliverable will serve as input for the first iteration of user and system requirements analysis (to be provided in deliverable D2.2 at Month 08 of the project) and the specification of the initial ENACT platform architecture (to be provided in D2.3 at Month 09). The revised and final work presented in this deliverable will be provided in **D2.4 (State of the Art Analysis, Vision, & ENACT Specifications - Final)** at Month 18.

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